

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Estrone

CHID: 22367 CASRN: 53-16-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J11

M4ID: 30006168

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -4.13	MAX_MED: -2.19	BMAD: 2.23
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COFF: 22.3	HIT-CALL: -1	FITC: 2	ACTP: NA
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-Androstene-3,17-dione

CHID: 24523 CASRN: 63-05-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N10

M4ID: 30006073

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.878 MAX_MED: 2.02 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dimethomorph

CHID: 34545 CASRN: 110488-70-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I22

M4ID: 30006181

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.04 MAX_MED: 3.58 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Tebufenozide

CHID: 34948 CASRN: 112410-23-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C03

M4ID: 30006344

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.06 MAX_MED: 1.74 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Testosterone propionate

CHID: 36515 CASRN: 57-85-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C07

M4ID: 30006724

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.43	MAX_MED:	3.09	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	-1	FITC:	2	ACTP:	NA
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: DMSO.POS (spid not in DB)

CHID: NA CASRN: NA

SPID(S): DMSO.POS

M4ID: 30006779

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.537 MAX_MED: 0 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Acetaminophen

CHID: 20006 CASRN: 103-90-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P21

M4ID: 30006398

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	144.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.45	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	2.47	MAX_MED:	3.13	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Acifluorfen

CHID: 20022 CASRN: 50594-66-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J03

M4ID: 30006176

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	184.41	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.75	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-2.23	MAX_MED:	-1.72	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Allantoin

CHID: 20043 CASRN: 97-59-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P11

M4ID: 30006408

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	156.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.02	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.74 MAX_MED: 2.58 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Amitrole

CHID: 20076 CASRN: 61-82-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078020

M4ID: 30006423

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	154.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.82 MAX_MED: 4 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Aniline hydrochloride

CHID: 20091 CASRN: 142-04-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L10

M4ID: 30006505

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	182.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.58	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-1.15	MAX_MED:	-1.86	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-Methoxyaniline hydrochloride

CHID: 20093 CASRN: 20265-97-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G07

M4ID: 30006628

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	127	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.84	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.03 MAX_MED: 0.835 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Aspartame

CHID: 20107 CASRN: 22839-47-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K12

M4ID: 30006143

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	169.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	1.6	MAX_MED:	1.23	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Atrazine

CHID: 20112 CASRN: 1912-24-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N11

M4ID: 30006072

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	185.81	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.03	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.306	MAX_MED:	0.769	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Sodium azide

CHID: 20121 CASRN: 26628-22-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D11

M4ID: 30006312

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	165.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.62	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.57 MAX_MED: 5.16 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 3'-Azido-3'-deoxythymidine

CHID: 20127 CASRN: 30516-87-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L14

M4ID: 30006117

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	188.64	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.98	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.775 MAX_MED: -0.414 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Sodium benzoate

CHID: 20140 CASRN: 532-32-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K11

M4ID: 30006528

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	131.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.08	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.11 MAX_MED: 2.36 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2,3-Benzofuran

CHID: 20141 CASRN: 271-89-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D21

M4ID: 30006302

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	137.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.4	MAX_MED:	3.6	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Benzoic acid

CHID: 20143 CASRN: 65-85-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G12

M4ID: 30006623

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	160.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.35	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	5.68	MAX_MED:	4.84	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1,2,3-Benzotriazole
CHID: 20147 CASRN: 95-14-7
SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N21
M4ID: 30006446

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	142.07	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.356 MAX_MED: 0.253 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Benzyl acetate

CHID: 20151 CASRN: 140-11-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D23

M4ID: 30006684

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	139.58	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	2.88	MAX_MED:	4.29	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Benzyl alcohol

CHID: 20152 CASRN: 100-51-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N07

M4ID: 30006460

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	140.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.133 MAX_MED: 0.278 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Bis(2-chloroethyl) ether

CHID: 20168 CASRN: 111-44-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K03

M4ID: 30006536

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	153.85	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.632 MAX_MED: 0.137 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-Butyrolactone

CHID: 20224 CASRN: 96-48-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N12

M4ID: 30006071

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	186.52	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.05	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0422 MAX_MED: 0.224 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Caffeine

CHID: 20232 CASRN: 58-08-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K18

M4ID: 30006521

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	161.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.73 MAX_MED: 2.35 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1-Chloro-4-nitrobenzene

CHID: 20281 CASRN: 100-00-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B05

M4ID: 30006750

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	180.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.42	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	5.74	MAX_MED:	5.88	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 3-Chloro-4-methylaniline

CHID: 20286 CASRN: 95-74-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F09

M4ID: 30006650

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	157.85	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.04	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.76	MAX_MED:	-0.822	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-Chloroaniline

CHID: 20295 CASRN: 106-47-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H15

M4ID: 30006212

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	157.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.68 MAX_MED: 2.17 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Monuron

CHID: 20311 CASRN: 150-68-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J12

M4ID: 30006551

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	140.23	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.61	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.87 MAX_MED: 6.54 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Citric acid

CHID: 20332 CASRN: 77-92-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H23

M4ID: 30006588

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	158.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.99	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.5 MAX_MED: -1.71 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Coumaphos

CHID: 20347 CASRN: 56-72-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K21

M4ID: 30006134

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	157.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.08	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.5 MAX_MED: 4.57 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-Methoxy-5-methylaniline

CHID: 20350 CASRN: 120-71-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E10

M4ID: 30006289

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	164.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.49	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.35 MAX_MED: 5.06 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Propyzamide

CHID: 20420 CASRN: 23950-58-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K12

M4ID: 30006527

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	156.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.07	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.37 MAX_MED: 3.58 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1,4-Dichlorobenzene

CHID: 20431 CASRN: 106-46-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091014

M4ID: 30006045

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	185.31	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.72	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.888 MAX_MED: 0.99 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dichlorprop

CHID: 20440 CASRN: 120-36-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B13

M4ID: 30006742

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	164.91	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.4	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.3 MAX_MED: 5.09 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dichlorvos

CHID: 20449 CASRN: 62-73-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D14

M4ID: 30006309

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	162.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.95 MAX_MED: 5.33 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dimethyl hydrogen phosphite

CHID: 20493 CASRN: 868-85-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J19

M4ID: 30006160

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	133.58	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.01	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.326 MAX_MED: 0.162 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dimethyl methylphosphonate

CHID: 20494 CASRN: 756-79-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M20

M4ID: 30006087

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	141.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	1.26	MAX_MED:	2.16	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dimethylaminoethanol
 CHID: 20505 CASRN: 108-01-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H24
 M4ID: 30006203

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	123.31	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.78	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.02 MAX_MED: 0.946 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1,1-Dimethylhydrazine
 CHID: 20516 CASRN: 57-14-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H06
 M4ID: 30006605

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	143.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.6	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.71 MAX_MED: 5.94 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2,4-Dinitrotoluene

CHID: 20529 CASRN: 121-14-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L02

M4ID: 30006129

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	139.71	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	1.56	MAX_MED:	1.89	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Sodium erythorbate (1:1)

CHID: 20570 CASRN: 6381-77-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H14

M4ID: 30006213

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	173.94	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.9	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.16 MAX_MED: -2.71 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Ethoxyquin

CHID: 20582 CASRN: 91-53-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G19

M4ID: 30006616

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	164.53	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.71	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.6 MAX_MED: 4.29 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-Vinyl-1-cyclohexene dioxide

CHID: 20604 CASRN: 106-87-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078006

M4ID: 30006437

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	144.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.49	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	4.67	MAX_MED:	5.04	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-Ethyl-1-hexanol

CHID: 20605 CASRN: 104-76-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078021

M4ID: 30006422

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	151.94	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.77	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-1.38	MAX_MED:	-1.15	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 5-Fluorouracil

CHID: 20634 CASRN: 51-21-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I02

M4ID: 30006201

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	145.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.47	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	2.68	MAX_MED:	3.19	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Glycidol

CHID: 20666 CASRN: 556-52-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N20

M4ID: 30006447

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	148.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.61	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.95	MAX_MED:	3.79	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Hexachloro-1,3-butadiene

CHID: 20683 CASRN: 87-68-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I18

M4ID: 30006569

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	149.23	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.78	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.72 MAX_MED: 0.657 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Hexachlorocyclopentadiene

CHID: 20688 CASRN: 77-47-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F06

M4ID: 30006269

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	147.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.59	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.83	MAX_MED:	3.77	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Methenamine

CHID: 20692 CASRN: 100-97-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G08

M4ID: 30006243

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	138.24	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	2.46	MAX_MED:	2.52	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: dl-Menthol

CHID: 20805 CASRN: 89-78-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I14

M4ID: 30006573

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	170.98	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.76	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	2.36	MAX_MED:	3.22	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Methyl methanesulfonate

CHID: 20845 CASRN: 66-27-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N15

M4ID: 30006068

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	187.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.85	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.71 MAX_MED: -1.83 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 6-Methyl-2-thiouracil
 CHID: 20890 CASRN: 56-04-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F19
 M4ID: 30006640

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	160.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.31 MAX_MED: 3.84 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Busulfan

CHID: 20910 CASRN: 55-98-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P15

M4ID: 30006020

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	176.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.03 MAX_MED: -1.12 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Naphthalene

CHID: 20913 CASRN: 91-20-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M02

M4ID: 30006105

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	127.98	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.89	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	2.28	MAX_MED:	2.26	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1-Naphthaleneacetic acid

CHID: 20915 CASRN: 86-87-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F05

M4ID: 30006270

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	139.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	2.26	MAX_MED:	2.73	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Nicotine

CHID: 20930 CASRN: 54-11-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D07

M4ID: 30006700

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	167.54	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.55	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.63 MAX_MED: 4.96 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Nicotinic acid

CHID: 20932 CASRN: 59-67-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J10

M4ID: 30006553

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	194.45	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.44	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.23 MAX_MED: 1.25 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-Methoxy-5-nitroaniline

CHID: 20943 CASRN: 99-59-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I11

M4ID: 30006576

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	152.42	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.87	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	4.48	MAX_MED:	5.33	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-Methyl-5-nitroaniline

CHID: 20959 CASRN: 99-55-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G18

M4ID: 30006233

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	135.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.82	MAX_MED:	3.89	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Nitrobenzene

CHID: 20964 CASRN: 98-95-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E23

M4ID: 30006276

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	124.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.83	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	2.49	MAX_MED:	2.01	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-Nitrobenzoic acid

CHID: 20966 CASRN: 62-23-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I03

M4ID: 30006200

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	168.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.83	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-1.11	MAX_MED:	-1.68	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: N-Nitrosodipropylamine
CHID: 21032 CASRN: 621-64-7
SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J14
M4ID: 30006165

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	171.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.78	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.584 MAX_MED: 0.522 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Oxytetracycline hydrochloride

CHID: 21097 CASRN: 2058-46-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P02

M4ID: 30006033

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	154.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.93	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	4.91	MAX_MED:	4.98	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Prednisone

CHID: 21185 CASRN: 53-03-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I05

M4ID: 30006582

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	164.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.53	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	6.13	MAX_MED:	5.44	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Propazine

CHID: 21196 CASRN: 139-40-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E18

M4ID: 30006281

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	192.18	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	11.79	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	20.4	MAX_MED:	6.39	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Pebulate

CHID: 21199 CASRN: 1114-71-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H11

M4ID: 30006600

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	117.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.61	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.16 MAX_MED: 2.01 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Retinol acetate

CHID: 21240 CASRN: 127-47-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G05

M4ID: 30006630

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	175.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.08	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.15 MAX_MED: 6.53 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Sulfasalazine

CHID: 21256 CASRN: 599-79-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M05

M4ID: 30006486

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	142.68	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.41	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.91	MAX_MED:	3.36	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Sodium chlorite

CHID: 21272 CASRN: 7758-19-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J11

M4ID: 30006552

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	122.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.81	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.54 MAX_MED: 3.46 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2E,4E-Hexadienoic acid
CHID: 21277 CASRN: 110-44-1
SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K24
M4ID: 30006515

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	145.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.51	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.08 MAX_MED: 3.65 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Thiourea

CHID: 21348 CASRN: 62-56-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L17

M4ID: 30006114

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	147.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.75	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.69 MAX_MED: 4.97 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Triethylene glycol

CHID: 21393 CASRN: 112-27-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078017

M4ID: 30006426

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	187.76	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.81	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.58 MAX_MED: -3.23 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Trimethyl phosphate

CHID: 21403 CASRN: 512-56-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F18

M4ID: 30006257

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	151.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	9.59	MAX_MED:	5.15	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Urethane

CHID: 21427 CASRN: 51-79-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M11

M4ID: 30006096

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	192.58	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.4	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-3.24	MAX_MED:	-1.91	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Fumaric acid

CHID: 21518 CASRN: 110-17-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P23

M4ID: 30006396

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	158.23	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.08 MAX_MED: 2.46 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Heptanoic acid

CHID: 21600 CASRN: 111-14-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P03

M4ID: 30006032

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	179.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.56	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.0355	MAX_MED:	-1.33	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Hexanoic acid

CHID: 21607 CASRN: 142-62-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N06

M4ID: 30006461

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	123.82	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.84	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.89	MAX_MED:	4.43	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Nonanoic acid

CHID: 21641 CASRN: 112-05-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M21

M4ID: 30006470

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	150.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.78	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.113	MAX_MED:	0.741	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Octadecanoic acid

CHID: 21642 CASRN: 57-11-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K07

M4ID: 30006148

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	134.85	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.314 MAX_MED: 1.14 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1-Propanol

CHID: 21739 CASRN: 71-23-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N24

M4ID: 30006443

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	158.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.08	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.54 MAX_MED: 4.67 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 5,5-Dimethylhydantoin

CHID: 21754 CASRN: 77-71-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J07

M4ID: 30006556

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	132.53	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.05	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.195 MAX_MED: -0.239 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1-Naphthol

CHID: 21793 CASRN: 90-15-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F01

M4ID: 30006274

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	137.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.31 MAX_MED: 3.42 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Quinoline

CHID: 21798 CASRN: 91-22-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I10

M4ID: 30006193

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	172.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.03	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.612 MAX_MED: 2.19 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: N,N-Diethylaniline

CHID: 21800 CASRN: 91-66-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N02

M4ID: 30006081

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	138.75	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.47 MAX_MED: 4.08 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: o-Cresol

CHID: 21808 CASRN: 95-48-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N23

M4ID: 30006444

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	156.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.04	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	4.2	MAX_MED:	5.05	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 3,4-Dichloroaniline

CHID: 21815 CASRN: 95-76-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L22

M4ID: 30006109

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	124.71	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.93	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.51 MAX_MED: 5.24 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-Butanone oxime

CHID: 21821 CASRN: 96-29-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H21

M4ID: 30006206

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	100.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	0.401	MAX_MED:	1.11	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Acetophenone

CHID: 21828 CASRN: 98-86-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H08

M4ID: 30006603

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	116.82	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.59	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.03	MAX_MED:	2.91	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 3-Nitrotoluene

CHID: 21831 CASRN: 99-08-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B16

M4ID: 30006355

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	160.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.45	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.03 MAX_MED: 6.09 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: N,N,4-Trimethylaniline

CHID: 21832 CASRN: 99-97-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078018

M4ID: 30006425

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	181.39	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.39	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.371 MAX_MED: 0.154 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Cyclohexanone oxime
CHID: 21842 CASRN: 100-64-1
SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M10
M4ID: 30006097

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	180.15	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.82	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	1.29	MAX_MED:	1.39	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: N-Ethyl-3-methylaniline

CHID: 21848 CASRN: 102-27-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N18

M4ID: 30006449

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	175.76	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.99	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.48 MAX_MED: 1.44 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Diethyl propanedioate

CHID: 21863 CASRN: 105-53-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F20

M4ID: 30006255

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	159.73	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.94 MAX_MED: 5.42 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2,4-Dimethylphenol

CHID: 21864 CASRN: 105-67-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M08

M4ID: 30006099

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	149.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.93	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	2.74	MAX_MED:	1.53	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-Pentanone

CHID: 21888 CASRN: 107-87-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P12

M4ID: 30006023

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	188.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.21	MAX_MED: 2.88	BMAD: 2.23
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COFF: 22.3	HIT-CALL: 0	FITC: 4	ACTP: 0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Propanedinitrile

CHID: 21907 CASRN: 109-77-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F19

M4ID: 30006256

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	135.53	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.08	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	1.23	MAX_MED:	0.935	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 5-Methyl-2-hexanone

CHID: 21914 CASRN: 110-12-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K20

M4ID: 30006135

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	137.5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.33	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	2.05	MAX_MED:	1.69	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-(Ethylamino)ethanol

CHID: 21922 CASRN: 110-73-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G04

M4ID: 30006631

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	150.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.15 MAX_MED: 6.06 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Ethylene glycol monoethyl ether acetate

CHID: 21928 CASRN: 111-15-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J20

M4ID: 30006543

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	131.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	4.2	MAX_MED:	3.19	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Hexanedinitrile

CHID: 21936 CASRN: 111-69-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M14

M4ID: 30006093

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	184	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.67	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.963 MAX_MED: -0.0536 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1-Octanol

CHID: 21940 CASRN: 111-87-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F21

M4ID: 30006638

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	154.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.89	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.08 MAX_MED: 4.97 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-Undecanone

CHID: 21943 CASRN: 112-12-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L07

M4ID: 30006508

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	125.41	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.85	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.819 MAX_MED: 1.04 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1-Decanol

CHID: 21946 CASRN: 112-30-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I22

M4ID: 30006565

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	134.26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.49	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	4.1	MAX_MED:	1.81	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Ethyl hexanoate

CHID: 21980 CASRN: 123-66-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M03

M4ID: 30006488

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	148.91	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.75	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	0.548	MAX_MED:	0.964	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dibenzofuran

CHID: 21993 CASRN: 132-64-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P14

M4ID: 30006021

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	178.59	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.49	MAX_MED:	2.67	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Ethanolamine

CHID: 22000 CASRN: 141-43-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H21

M4ID: 30006590

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	126.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.82	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.672 MAX_MED: 0.577 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1-Nonanol

CHID: 22008 CASRN: 143-08-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M22

M4ID: 30006469

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	147.78	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.59	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.25 MAX_MED: 1.65 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Bromacil

CHID: 22020 CASRN: 314-40-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G10

M4ID: 30006241

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	166.51	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.73	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	0.609	MAX_MED:	2.11	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 3,4-Dichloro-1-butene

CHID: 22113 CASRN: 760-23-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H24

M4ID: 30006587

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	147.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.61	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.9	MAX_MED:	2.95	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: (Z)-3-Hexen-1-ol

CHID: 22137 CASRN: 928-96-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M18

M4ID: 30006473

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	168.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.59	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.184 MAX_MED: -0.378 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4,4'-Methylenebis(2,6-di-t-butylphenol)

CHID: 22411 CASRN: 118-82-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I02

M4ID: 30006585

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	134.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.04	MAX_MED:	2.91	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Melatonin

CHID: 22421 CASRN: 73-31-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E07

M4ID: 30006676

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	146.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.56	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.38	MAX_MED:	3.91	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Butylbenzene

CHID: 22472 CASRN: 104-51-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C21

M4ID: 30006326

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	140.77	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.4	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.1	MAX_MED:	2.55	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Corticosterone

CHID: 22474 CASRN: 50-22-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091005

M4ID: 30006054

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	165.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.36 MAX_MED: 6.47 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Lactose
 CHID: 23193 CASRN: 63-42-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M01
 M4ID: 30006490

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	173.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.89	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.514 MAX_MED: -0.478 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Letrozole

CHID: 23202 CASRN: 112809-51-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K22

M4ID: 30006133

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	144.18	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.47	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.89	MAX_MED:	5.02	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Pyridoxine

CHID: 23541 CASRN: 65-23-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G01

M4ID: 30006250

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	123.84	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.76	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.427 MAX_MED: 0.137 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Retinol

CHID: 23556 CASRN: 68-26-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H14

M4ID: 30006597

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	147.5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.62	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	1.34	MAX_MED:	1.66	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Butanedioic acid

CHID: 23602 CASRN: 110-15-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I07

M4ID: 30006196

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	153.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.97	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.118 MAX_MED: 0.353 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Tetracycline

CHID: 23645 CASRN: 60-54-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C11

M4ID: 30006720

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	159.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	6.16	MAX_MED:	5.68	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Tromethamine

CHID: 23723 CASRN: 77-86-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M15

M4ID: 30006476

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	138.42	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.45 MAX_MED: 2.84 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: D-Xylose

CHID: 23745 CASRN: 58-86-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J12

M4ID: 30006167

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	174.38	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	0.372	MAX_MED:	-0.171	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Acephate

CHID: 23846 CASRN: 30560-19-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C19

M4ID: 30006712

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	186.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.74	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.2 MAX_MED: 6.43 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-Anisidine

CHID: 23877 CASRN: 90-04-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I10

M4ID: 30006577

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	167.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.57	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	2.27	MAX_MED:	2.53	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Clofentezine

CHID: 23881 CASRN: 74115-24-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M05

M4ID: 30006102

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	163.38	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	0.663	MAX_MED:	0.854	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Asulam

CHID: 23890 CASRN: 3337-71-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F10

M4ID: 30006649

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	153.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.22 MAX_MED: 2.29 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Benfluralin

CHID: 23899 CASRN: 1861-40-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L04

M4ID: 30006127

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	168.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.88	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	5.75	MAX_MED:	6.4	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Bentazone

CHID: 23901 CASRN: 25057-89-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F04

M4ID: 30006271

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	140.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.42	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	4.65	MAX_MED:	4.88	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Benzo(b)fluoranthene

CHID: 23907 CASRN: 205-99-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I23

M4ID: 30006180

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	157.76	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.83	MAX_MED:	3.84	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Cyromazine

CHID: 23999 CASRN: 66215-27-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091007

M4ID: 30006052

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	178.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.35	MAX_MED: -1.93	BMAD: 2.23
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COFF: 22.3	HIT-CALL: 0	FITC: 4	ACTP: 0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Diethyl sulfate

CHID: 24045 CASRN: 64-67-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M20

M4ID: 30006471

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	147.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.8	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	4.95	MAX_MED:	4.49	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Diisopropyl methylphosphonate

CHID: 24051 CASRN: 1445-75-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091015

M4ID: 30006044

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	190.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.8 MAX_MED: -3.25 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dimethyl sulfate

CHID: 24055 CASRN: 77-78-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D03

M4ID: 30006320

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	132.54	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.01	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	2.49	MAX_MED:	2.32	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dimethylamine

CHID: 24057 CASRN: 124-40-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J05

M4ID: 30006174

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	176.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.07	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-2.64	MAX_MED:	-2.66	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-Butoxyethanol

CHID: 24097 CASRN: 111-76-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M12

M4ID: 30006479

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	136.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.18 MAX_MED: 3.6 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Fomesafen

CHID: 24112 CASRN: 72178-02-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A16

M4ID: 30006379

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	192.49	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.6	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.12 MAX_MED: 5.96 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Lactofen

CHID: 24160 CASRN: 77501-63-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I01

M4ID: 30006202

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	162.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.64 MAX_MED: 4.16 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Methacrylonitrile

CHID: 24176 CASRN: 126-98-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C20

M4ID: 30006327

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	174.38	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.92	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	5.98	MAX_MED:	5.24	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: MCPB

CHID: 24193 CASRN: 94-81-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K13

M4ID: 30006142

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	161.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.154 MAX_MED: 0.0193 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Mecoprop

CHID: 24194 CASRN: 93-65-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P03

M4ID: 30006416

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	161.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.39	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.29	MAX_MED: 2.93	BMAD: 2.23
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COFF: 22.3	HIT-CALL: 0	FITC: 4	ACTP: 0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: m-Cresol

CHID: 24200 CASRN: 108-39-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I19

M4ID: 30006184

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	144.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.47	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.05 MAX_MED: 2.46 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Molinate

CHID: 24206 CASRN: 2212-67-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I13

M4ID: 30006574

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	162.39	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.85 MAX_MED: 3.32 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Nitrapyrin

CHID: 24216 CASRN: 1929-82-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G04

M4ID: 30006247

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	150.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.74	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.98 MAX_MED: 1.77 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Pyrene

CHID: 24289 CASRN: 129-00-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M23

M4ID: 30006084

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	165.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.49	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.36 MAX_MED: 5.56 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Hexythiazox

CHID: 24299 CASRN: 78587-05-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I24

M4ID: 30006179

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	139.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.88 MAX_MED: 4.01 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Sethoxydim

CHID: 24304 CASRN: 74051-80-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D09

M4ID: 30006314

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	180.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.54	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.36 MAX_MED: 6.36 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Tebuthiuron

CHID: 24316 CASRN: 34014-18-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M04

M4ID: 30006103

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	165.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.85	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0383 MAX_MED: 0.156 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1,2,4,5-Tetrachlorobenzene

CHID: 24320 CASRN: 95-94-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C24

M4ID: 30006323

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	173.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.97	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.23 MAX_MED: 6.12 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Thiophanate-methyl
 CHID: 24338 CASRN: 23564-05-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I19
 M4ID: 30006568

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	129.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.91	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.26 MAX_MED: 2.89 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Tri-allate

CHID: 24344 CASRN: 2303-17-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K16

M4ID: 30006139

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	166.71	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.86	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.11 MAX_MED: 3.52 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Acetic acid

CHID: 24394 CASRN: 64-19-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078023

M4ID: 30006420

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	169.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.66	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.48 MAX_MED: -1.47 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-Aminobenzoic acid

CHID: 24466 CASRN: 150-13-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C13

M4ID: 30006718

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	147.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.62	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.36 MAX_MED: 4.05 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Diethylene glycol dimethyl ether

CHID: 24621 CASRN: 111-96-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G03

M4ID: 30006632

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	150.51	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.79	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	1.08	MAX_MED:	1.54	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 3-Bromo-1-propanol

CHID: 24657 CASRN: 627-18-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E05

M4ID: 30006294

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	120.76	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.73	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	1.79	MAX_MED:	1.38	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: tert-Butylamine

CHID: 24681 CASRN: 75-64-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P18

M4ID: 30006017

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	144.58	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.52	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	4.37	MAX_MED:	3.72	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: D-Camphor

CHID: 24721 CASRN: 464-49-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G14

M4ID: 30006621

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	165.91	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.62	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.16 MAX_MED: 5.14 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Carbendazim

CHID: 24729 CASRN: 10605-21-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P06

M4ID: 30006029

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	173.98	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.07	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.93 MAX_MED: 4.7 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1,6-Hexanediamine

CHID: 24922 CASRN: 124-09-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L20

M4ID: 30006111

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	137.71	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	2.17	MAX_MED:	3.87	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Di-tert-butyl peroxide

CHID: 24955 CASRN: 110-05-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F23

M4ID: 30006252

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	130.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.05	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.752 MAX_MED: 0.462 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Benzal chloride

CHID: 25014 CASRN: 98-87-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D05

M4ID: 30006318

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	156.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.07	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.6 MAX_MED: 5.62 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Diethylene glycol monomethyl ether

CHID: 25049 CASRN: 111-77-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I24

M4ID: 30006563

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	152.71	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.89	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	5.23	MAX_MED:	5.99	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Diethylenetriamine

CHID: 25050 CASRN: 111-40-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N03

M4ID: 30006464

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	151.19	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.8	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.739 MAX_MED: 0.898 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dimethyl adipate

CHID: 25096 CASRN: 627-93-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K16

M4ID: 30006523

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	153.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.03	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	4.53	MAX_MED:	2.89	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dimethyl glutarate

CHID: 25122 CASRN: 1119-40-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J22

M4ID: 30006541

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	144.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.48	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.56	MAX_MED:	3.33	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1,2-Dimethyl-3-nitrobenzene

CHID: 25132 CASRN: 83-41-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L01

M4ID: 30006130

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	124.41	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.81	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.72 MAX_MED: 2.03 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1,3-Dimethylolurea

CHID: 25141 CASRN: 140-95-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M12

M4ID: 30006095

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	185.68	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-1.1	MAX_MED:	1.58	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Divinylbenzene

CHID: 25216 CASRN: 1321-74-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K04

M4ID: 30006535

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	144.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.64	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	4.38	MAX_MED:	3.27	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: (2-Dodecenyl)succinic anhydride

CHID: 25217 CASRN: 19780-11-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J02

M4ID: 30006561

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	163.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.41	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	2.49	MAX_MED:	1.64	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-Ethylhexanoic acid

CHID: 25293 CASRN: 149-57-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L12

M4ID: 30006503

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	131.81	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.04	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.72 MAX_MED: 3.81 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 5-Ethylidene-2-norbornene

CHID: 25306 CASRN: 16219-75-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H22

M4ID: 30006205

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	164.85	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.58 MAX_MED: 6.09 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Formamide

CHID: 25337 CASRN: 75-12-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K20

M4ID: 30006519

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	132.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	4.12	MAX_MED:	4.99	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Hexamethyldisilazane

CHID: 25395 CASRN: 999-97-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N23

M4ID: 30006060

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	163.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-1.2	MAX_MED:	-1.54	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-Hydroxy-2-methylpropanenitrile

CHID: 25427 CASRN: 75-86-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G20

M4ID: 30006231

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	140.73	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.32	MAX_MED:	3.11	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Hydroxyurea

CHID: 25438 CASRN: 127-07-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F24

M4ID: 30006251

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	116.52	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.72	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.1 MAX_MED: 2.63 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 3-Methylbutyl acetate

CHID: 25453 CASRN: 123-92-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M17

M4ID: 30006474

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	168.55	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.57	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-1.42	MAX_MED:	-1.43	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Isopentyl alcohol

CHID: 25469 CASRN: 123-51-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N19

M4ID: 30006448

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	125.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.78	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.00778 MAX_MED: 0.388 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Linalool

CHID: 25502 CASRN: 78-70-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G23

M4ID: 30006612

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	167.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.886 MAX_MED: 0.581 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Methyl 2-aminobenzoate
CHID: 25567 CASRN: 134-20-3
SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H04
M4ID: 30006223

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	158.45	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.407 MAX_MED: 0.956 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: N,N'-Methylenebisacrylamide

CHID: 25595 CASRN: 110-26-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I15

M4ID: 30006188

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	175.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.03	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	5.86	MAX_MED:	5.59	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Myrcene

CHID: 25692 CASRN: 123-35-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E16

M4ID: 30006283

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	115.5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.44 MAX_MED: 3.44 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-Nitroaniline

CHID: 25726 CASRN: 88-74-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N01

M4ID: 30006082

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	140.58	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.35	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.552 MAX_MED: -0.355 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Ethyl 3-phenylglycidate

CHID: 25886 CASRN: 121-39-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D01

M4ID: 30006706

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	158.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.06	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.34	MAX_MED:	3.54	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Tetrachlorophthalic anhydride

CHID: 26102 CASRN: 117-08-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I03

M4ID: 30006584

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	171.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-1.08	MAX_MED:	0.0436	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Tolyltriazole

CHID: 26171 CASRN: 29385-43-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N11

M4ID: 30006456

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	112.76	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.53	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.19 MAX_MED: 1.21 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Triethylene glycol dimethyl ether

CHID: 26224 CASRN: 112-49-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M01

M4ID: 30006106

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	132.48	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.04	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0525 MAX_MED: 0.301 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Trimellitic anhydride

CHID: 26235 CASRN: 552-30-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G16

M4ID: 30006619

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	159.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.43	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	6.81	MAX_MED:	6.02	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Camphene

CHID: 26488 CASRN: 79-92-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C23

M4ID: 30006708

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	141.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	4.25	MAX_MED:	4.06	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1,2,3,6-Tetrahydrophthalimide

CHID: 26513 CASRN: 85-40-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M16

M4ID: 30006475

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	148.84	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.72	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.91 MAX_MED: 4.08 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Phthalimide

CHID: 26514 CASRN: 85-41-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P08

M4ID: 30006027

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	162.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.39	MAX_MED:	3.41	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Symclosene

CHID: 26523 CASRN: 87-90-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I04

M4ID: 30006199

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	163.85	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.43	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.25 MAX_MED: 2.25 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-tert-Butylcyclohexanol

CHID: 26623 CASRN: 98-52-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B13

M4ID: 30006358

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	174.24	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.04	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.05 MAX_MED: 4.73 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1,3-Diisopropylbenzene

CHID: 26640 CASRN: 99-62-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P19

M4ID: 30006400

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	141.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.35	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	2.02	MAX_MED:	1.46	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1,3-Benzenedicarbonyl dichloride

CHID: 26641 CASRN: 99-63-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P07

M4ID: 30006028

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	162.91	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.885	MAX_MED:	-1.58	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: p-Cymene

CHID: 26645 CASRN: 99-87-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L09

M4ID: 30006122

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	171.14	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.97	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.849	MAX_MED:	0.682	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-Hydroxybenzoic acid

CHID: 26647 CASRN: 99-96-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L14

M4ID: 30006501

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	169.26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.64	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0561 MAX_MED: 0.506 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Triacetin

CHID: 26691 CASRN: 102-76-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K22

M4ID: 30006517

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	145.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.63	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.79	MAX_MED:	2.22	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-Ethylhexyl acetate

CHID: 26694 CASRN: 103-09-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D03

M4ID: 30006704

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	182.68	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.57	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.94 MAX_MED: 5.4 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-Methyl-2-pentanol

CHID: 26781 CASRN: 108-11-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H19

M4ID: 30006592

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	127.68	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.84	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.71 MAX_MED: 2.7 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 3-Methylaniline

CHID: 26792 CASRN: 108-44-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L18

M4ID: 30006497

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	164.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.43	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	0.259	MAX_MED:	0.468	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Benzenethiol

CHID: 26811 CASRN: 108-98-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M04

M4ID: 30006487

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	153.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.42	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	6.64	MAX_MED:	3.68	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Methyl decanoate
 CHID: 26842 CASRN: 110-42-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P21
 M4ID: 30006014

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	128.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.97	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.09 MAX_MED: 1.75 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Methyl octanoate

CHID: 26864 CASRN: 111-11-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J21

M4ID: 30006158

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	115.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.59	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.29 MAX_MED: 1.8 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Hexamethyleneimine

CHID: 26879 CASRN: 111-49-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M19

M4ID: 30006088

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	138.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.939	MAX_MED:	-0.703	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1,2-Ethanedio1 diacetate

CHID: 26880 CASRN: 111-55-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N18

M4ID: 30006065

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	134.59	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.05	MAX_MED:	3.15	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-[2-(2-Methoxyethoxy)ethoxy]ethanol

CHID: 26912 CASRN: 112-35-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H17

M4ID: 30006594

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	148.76	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.76	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.455 MAX_MED: 0.776 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1-Undecanol

CHID: 26915 CASRN: 112-42-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G15

M4ID: 30006236

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	158.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.05	MAX_MED: 2.26	BMAD: 2.23
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COFF: 22.3	HIT-CALL: 0	FITC: 4	ACTP: 0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Pentaerythritol

CHID: 26943 CASRN: 115-77-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M13

M4ID: 30006478

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	185.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.69	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-2.61	MAX_MED:	-2.78	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-Methoxybenzaldehyde
 CHID: 26997 CASRN: 123-11-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B23
 M4ID: 30006732

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	180.59	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.41	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.63 MAX_MED: 5.77 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Sodium phenolate

CHID: 27072 CASRN: 139-02-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F07

M4ID: 30006268

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	152.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.85	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	4.32	MAX_MED:	3.96	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1H-1,2,4-Triazole

CHID: 27131 CASRN: 288-88-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078015

M4ID: 30006428

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	143.31	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.29 MAX_MED: 1.29 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1,3-Cyclopentadiene

CHID: 27191 CASRN: 542-92-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J20

M4ID: 30006159

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	156.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.95	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.98 MAX_MED: 4.42 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Methyl isothiocyanate

CHID: 27204 CASRN: 556-61-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G24

M4ID: 30006227

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	138.94	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.31 MAX_MED: 2.42 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2,6-Diethylaniline

CHID: 27218 CASRN: 579-66-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091001

M4ID: 30006058

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	147.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.64	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.941	MAX_MED:	-1.2	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-Pyrrolidinone

CHID: 27246 CASRN: 616-45-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H19

M4ID: 30006208

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	141.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.117 MAX_MED: -0.0984 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Isopropyl formate

CHID: 27258 CASRN: 625-55-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F03

M4ID: 30006656

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	119.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.83	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.13 MAX_MED: 2.28 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Pentyl acetate

CHID: 27263 CASRN: 628-63-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J23

M4ID: 30006540

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	157.58	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.96	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.93 MAX_MED: -1.84 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Phenyl phosphorus dichloride

CHID: 27282 CASRN: 644-97-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D20

M4ID: 30006303

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	171.73	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.9	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	5.75	MAX_MED:	4.82	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1-Phenoxy-2-propanol

CHID: 27312 CASRN: 770-35-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H20

M4ID: 30006207

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	133.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.01	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.05 MAX_MED: 2.8 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Ammonium carbamate

CHID: 27360 CASRN: 1111-78-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N05

M4ID: 30006462

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	120.26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.65	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.501 MAX_MED: 0.872 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Phenolsulfonic acid

CHID: 27390 CASRN: 1333-39-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B07

M4ID: 30006364

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	180.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	4.97	MAX_MED:	5.18	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Thiocarbazide

CHID: 27461 CASRN: 2231-57-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I20

M4ID: 30006183

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	150.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.65	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	1.95	MAX_MED:	3.45	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2,4-D sodium salt

CHID: 27496 CASRN: 2702-72-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H18

M4ID: 30006593

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	146.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.55	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	2.98	MAX_MED:	3.42	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Potassium 2-ethylhexanoate

CHID: 27525 CASRN: 3164-85-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G19

M4ID: 30006232

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	141.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.08 MAX_MED: 1.4 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Sodium chloroacetate

CHID: 27550 CASRN: 3926-62-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091020

M4ID: 30006039

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	151.49	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.81	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.83 MAX_MED: 2.32 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-Chlorobenzotrifluoride

CHID: 27593 CASRN: 5216-25-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P01

M4ID: 30006034

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	147.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.6	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.5 MAX_MED: 3.22 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-Acrylamido-2-methyl-1-propanesulfonic acid

CHID: 27770 CASRN: 15214-89-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L18

M4ID: 30006113

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	117.31	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.55	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.83 MAX_MED: 1.56 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dicyclohexyl sodium sulfosuccinate

CHID: 27826 CASRN: 23386-52-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M16

M4ID: 30006091

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	181.24	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.61	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.977	MAX_MED:	0.146	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: tert-Nonanethiol

CHID: 27868 CASRN: 25360-10-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K23

M4ID: 30006132

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	148.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.63	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.525 MAX_MED: 1.02 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Calcium dodecylbenzene sulfonate

CHID: 27891 CASRN: 26264-06-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G13

M4ID: 30006238

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	198.07	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.92	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-3.48	MAX_MED:	-3.18	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Neodecanoic acid

CHID: 27916 CASRN: 26896-20-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H07

M4ID: 30006220

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	151.58	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.78	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.794 MAX_MED: -0.761 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether

CHID: 27983 CASRN: 34590-94-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F23

M4ID: 30006636

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	123.18	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.76	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.621 MAX_MED: 0.474 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dichlormid
 CHID: 27997 CASRN: 37764-25-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D11
 M4ID: 30006696

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	172.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.98	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.61 MAX_MED: 6.43 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Tetrahydrofurfuryl alcohol

CHID: 29128 CASRN: 97-99-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078004

M4ID: 30006439

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	163.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.45	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	4.94	MAX_MED:	4.41	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Cyclopentanone

CHID: 29154 CASRN: 120-92-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I04

M4ID: 30006583

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	128.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	5	MAX_MED:	3.44	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2,6,8-Trimethyl-4-nonanol

CHID: 29159 CASRN: 123-17-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J15

M4ID: 30006548

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	143.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.4	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.03 MAX_MED: 3.16 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 3-Bromo-1-chloro-5,5-dimethylhydantoin

CHID: 29162 CASRN: 126-06-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E07

M4ID: 30006292

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	146.64	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.57	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	4.8	MAX_MED:	5.66	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Triethoxyoctylsilane

CHID: 29246 CASRN: 2943-75-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091008

M4ID: 30006051

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	166.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.47	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	2.39	MAX_MED:	2.72	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Tripropylene glycol monomethyl ether

CHID: 29329 CASRN: 25498-49-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K04

M4ID: 30006151

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	161.42	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.68	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.599 MAX_MED: 0.65 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Diazolidinyl urea

CHID: 29559 CASRN: 78491-02-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J18

M4ID: 30006161

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	136.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.81	MAX_MED:	3.35	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Methacrylamide

CHID: 29600 CASRN: 79-39-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J19

M4ID: 30006544

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	102.49	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.77 MAX_MED: 3.14 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Limonene

CHID: 29612 CASRN: 138-86-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I23

M4ID: 30006564

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	167.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.58	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.606 MAX_MED: -0.312 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Thiocyanic acid, ammonium salt

CHID: 29653 CASRN: 1762-95-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M24

M4ID: 30006083

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	151.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.8	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	0.965	MAX_MED:	0.599	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 3,5,5-Trimethyl-1-hexanol

CHID: 29661 CASRN: 3452-97-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C23

M4ID: 30006324

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	143.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.21 MAX_MED: 4.66 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Sodium persulfate

CHID: 29698 CASRN: 7775-27-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M07

M4ID: 30006100

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	167.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.54	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.917 MAX_MED: 0.222 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1,2-Propanediol monobutyl ether

CHID: 29755 CASRN: 29387-86-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I15

M4ID: 30006572 BRK

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	188.24	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	101.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	185	MAX_MED:	1.37	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Glycoluril

CHID: 31380 CASRN: 496-46-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G02

M4ID: 30006633

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	144.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.73	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	5.78	MAX_MED:	6.6	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Perfluorooctanoic acid
 CHID: 31865 CASRN: 335-67-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G02
 M4ID: 30006249

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	143.71	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.51	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.43 MAX_MED: 4.18 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dichlobenil

CHID: 32365 CASRN: 1194-65-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L21

M4ID: 30006494

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	137.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.97 MAX_MED: 4.18 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dimethenamid

CHID: 32376 CASRN: 87674-68-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G23

M4ID: 30006228

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	153.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.84	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.709 MAX_MED: 0.303 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Formetanate hydrochloride

CHID: 32405 CASRN: 23422-53-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I16

M4ID: 30006187

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	174.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.08	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	4.04	MAX_MED:	3.85	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Profenofos

CHID: 32464 CASRN: 41198-08-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K05

M4ID: 30006150

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	163.81	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.67	MAX_MED:	3.76	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-Hydroxyethyl octyl sulfide

CHID: 32516 CASRN: 3547-33-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F16

M4ID: 30006259

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	170.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.77	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.26 MAX_MED: 5.79 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Tefluthrin

CHID: 32577 CASRN: 79538-32-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078013

M4ID: 30006430

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	180.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.4	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	4.96	MAX_MED:	6.49	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Cyproconazole

CHID: 32601 CASRN: 94361-06-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J03

M4ID: 30006560

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	154.53	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.05	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	6.07	MAX_MED:	6.31	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Pymetrozine

CHID: 32637 CASRN: 123312-89-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I20

M4ID: 30006567

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	129.31	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	5.11	MAX_MED:	4.65	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-(Thiocyanomethylthio)benzothiazole

CHID: 32647 CASRN: 21564-17-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K10

M4ID: 30006145

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	176.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.63	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	0.867	MAX_MED:	2.58	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Tetramethrin

CHID: 32649 CASRN: 7696-12-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091004

M4ID: 30006055

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	166.5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.76	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	2.89	MAX_MED:	2.76	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-Chlorophenoxyacetic acid

CHID: 34282 CASRN: 122-88-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N08

M4ID: 30006075

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	175.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.06	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.208 MAX_MED: -0.774 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Denatonium saccharide
 CHID: 34361 CASRN: 90823-38-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D19
 M4ID: 30006304

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	164.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.41	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.39 MAX_MED: 3.68 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Boscalid

CHID: 34392 CASRN: 188425-85-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B21

M4ID: 30006350

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	177.91	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	5.74	MAX_MED:	5.74	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Butachlor

CHID: 34402 CASRN: 23184-66-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P11

M4ID: 30006024

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	186.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	2.76	MAX_MED:	3.09	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Fluazifop-butyl

CHID: 34612 CASRN: 69806-50-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I17

M4ID: 30006186

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	153.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.85	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.53 MAX_MED: 4.22 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Flufenpyr-ethyl

CHID: 34618 CASRN: 188489-07-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I07

M4ID: 30006580

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	127.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.86	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.14 MAX_MED: 0.572 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Imazamox

CHID: 34664 CASRN: 114311-32-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J07

M4ID: 30006172

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	169.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.75	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-1.65	MAX_MED:	-0.368	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Isoxaflutole

CHID: 34723 CASRN: 141112-29-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091024

M4ID: 30006035

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	153.85	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.82	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	2.05	MAX_MED:	2.21	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Milbemectin (mixture of 70% Milbemcin A4, 30% I

CHID: 34742 CASRN: NOCAS_34742

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D01

M4ID: 30006322

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	156.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	2.04	MAX_MED:	2.4	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Monocrotophos

CHID: 34816 CASRN: 6923-22-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091009

M4ID: 30006050

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	182.52	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.89	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.85 MAX_MED: 3.36 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Propamocarb hydrochloride

CHID: 34849 CASRN: 25606-41-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F17

M4ID: 30006258

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	112.26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.394 MAX_MED: 0.235 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Spiromesifen

CHID: 34929 CASRN: 283594-90-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G01

M4ID: 30006634

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	144.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	0.94	MAX_MED:	1.29	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Fosthiazate

CHID: 34930 CASRN: 98886-44-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091022

M4ID: 30006037

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	118.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.66	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.49	MAX_MED:	3.09	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Sodium warfarin
 CHID: 35010 CASRN: 129-06-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L17
 M4ID: 30006498

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	151.55	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.74	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.36 MAX_MED: 3.24 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1-(Hydroxymethyl)-5,5-dimethylhydantoin

CHID: 35152 CASRN: 116-25-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D17

M4ID: 30006306

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	117.51	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.6	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.17 MAX_MED: 1.91 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: alpha-Ionone

CHID: 35160 CASRN: 127-41-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D14

M4ID: 30006693

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	159.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.45	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	7.89	MAX_MED:	6.63	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1,4-Dimethylnaphthalene

CHID: 35423 CASRN: 571-58-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K21

M4ID: 30006518

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	153.19	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.86	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.06 MAX_MED: 5.3 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-(8-Heptadecenyl)-2-imidazoline-1-ethanol

CHID: 36112 CASRN: 95-38-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K24

M4ID: 30006131

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	161.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.48 MAX_MED: 5.51 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Sodium decyl sulfate

CHID: 36229 CASRN: 142-87-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H23

M4ID: 30006204

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	182.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.59	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.78 MAX_MED: -2.23 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Citralva

CHID: 36286 CASRN: 5146-66-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F12

M4ID: 30006263

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	137.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.44	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.06 MAX_MED: 3.4 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Deisopropylatrazine

CHID: 37495 CASRN: 1007-28-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E03

M4ID: 30006296

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	144.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.7	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.21 MAX_MED: 4.44 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Fenuron

CHID: 37551 CASRN: 101-42-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K08

M4ID: 30006531

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	138.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.53 MAX_MED: 3.35 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Potassium perfluorohexanesulfonate

CHID: 37709 CASRN: 3871-99-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091002

M4ID: 30006057

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	136.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	2.89	MAX_MED:	3.35	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 3-Phenoxybenzoic acid

CHID: 38321 CASRN: 3739-38-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M15

M4ID: 30006092

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	177.48	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-1.82	MAX_MED:	-1.81	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-Methoxy-4-nitroaniline

CHID: 38700 CASRN: 97-52-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G09

M4ID: 30006626

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	183.31	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.61	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-2.85	MAX_MED:	-1.94	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1,4-Cyclohexanedicarboxylic acid

CHID: 38788 CASRN: 1076-97-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H12

M4ID: 30006215

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	184.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.81	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.5 MAX_MED: 0.634 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: C.I. Acid Orange 7

CHID: 38881 CASRN: 633-96-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091011

M4ID: 30006048

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	199.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-3.9	MAX_MED:	-1.17	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Ethyl propionate

CHID: 40110 CASRN: 105-37-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B03

M4ID: 30006752

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	199.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.11 MAX_MED: 6 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Ethyl butyrate

CHID: 40111 CASRN: 105-54-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H02

M4ID: 30006609

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	141.54	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.39	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.16 MAX_MED: 2.9 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Trifloxysulfuron-sodium

CHID: 40222 CASRN: 199119-58-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P23

M4ID: 30006012

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	157.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.213 MAX_MED: 0.384 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Butylene carbonate

CHID: 40342 CASRN: 4437-85-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L19

M4ID: 30006112

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	133.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.09	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.526	MAX_MED:	0.142	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Isoxadifen-ethyl

CHID: 40360 CASRN: 163520-33-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H13

M4ID: 30006214

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	161.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.73	MAX_MED:	3.22	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Trimethoxyphenylsilane
CHID: 40700 CASRN: 2996-92-1
SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D16
M4ID: 30006307

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	135.13	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	4.69	MAX_MED:	4.06	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Sodium iodide

CHID: 41125 CASRN: 7681-82-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L12

M4ID: 30006119

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	183.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.75	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.135	MAX_MED:	-0.794	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1,3,5-Triisopropylbenzene

CHID: 41232 CASRN: 717-74-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G12

M4ID: 30006239

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	159.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	0.653	MAX_MED:	2.14	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1,4-Diaminoanthraquinone

CHID: 41252 CASRN: 128-95-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N07

M4ID: 30006076

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	152.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.86	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	0.133	MAX_MED:	0.0227	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-Hexyl-1-decanol

CHID: 41265 CASRN: 2425-77-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091012

M4ID: 30006047

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	178.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.55	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	1.38	MAX_MED:	3.01	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1-Phenyl-1H-pyrrole-2,5-dione

CHID: 41274 CASRN: 941-69-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C01

M4ID: 30006730

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	157.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.99	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	4	MAX_MED:	4.57	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1-Monolaurin

CHID: 41275 CASRN: 142-18-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L23

M4ID: 30006108

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	145.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.48	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.01	MAX_MED:	2.5	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: R(-)-Carvone

CHID: 41413 CASRN: 6485-40-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E12

M4ID: 30006287

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	124.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.05	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	4.69	MAX_MED:	5.75	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-Methylbutyl isovalerate

CHID: 41440 CASRN: 2445-77-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F11

M4ID: 30006648

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	154.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.93	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	4.11	MAX_MED:	5.01	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: (3Z)-3-Hexenyl acetate

CHID: 41484 CASRN: 3681-71-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E23

M4ID: 30006660

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	122.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.82	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	1.09	MAX_MED:	1.52	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 3-Phenylhexane

CHID: 41492 CASRN: 4468-42-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I09

M4ID: 30006578

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	184.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.69	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-2.89	MAX_MED:	-1.84	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 7-Ethyl-2-methyl-4-undecanoate sulfate, sodium salt

CHID: 41530 CASRN: 139-88-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N19

M4ID: 30006064

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	144.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.45	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.47 MAX_MED: 1.62 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dihydromyrcenol

CHID: 41557 CASRN: 53219-21-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L16

M4ID: 30006499

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	146.41	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.77	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	4.96	MAX_MED:	3.45	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Arabinose

CHID: 41610 CASRN: 147-81-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C07

M4ID: 30006340

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	148.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.58	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.86	MAX_MED:	4.02	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Sodium m-xylene-4-sulfonate

CHID: 41639 CASRN: 827-21-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G20

M4ID: 30006615

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	170.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.67	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.24 MAX_MED: 5.73 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: C.I. Acid Yellow 34, monosodium salt

CHID: 41646 CASRN: 6359-90-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E14

M4ID: 30006669

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	148.71	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.91	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.89 MAX_MED: 6.53 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-Hydroxybenzonitrile
CHID: 41661 CASRN: 611-20-1
SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G07
M4ID: 30006244

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	146.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.59	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	4.79	MAX_MED:	3.98	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Butylphthalenesulfonic acid sodium salt

CHID: 41703 CASRN: 25638-17-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F05

M4ID: 30006654

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	141.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.58	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.26 MAX_MED: 4.33 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: C.I. Acid Yellow 3 disodium salt

CHID: 41721 CASRN: 8004-92-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F14

M4ID: 30006261

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	142.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.45	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.31 MAX_MED: 1.17 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Citronellal

CHID: 41790 CASRN: 106-23-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C03

M4ID: 30006728

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	171.53	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.81	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.34 MAX_MED: 5.4 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Diethyl phosphite

CHID: 41861 CASRN: 762-04-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N15

M4ID: 30006452

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	156.19	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.03	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.7 MAX_MED: 4.14 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dimethylbenzylcarbinyll acetate

CHID: 41877 CASRN: 151-05-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L15

M4ID: 30006500

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	159.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	4.92	MAX_MED:	5.74	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Ethyl diethanolamine

CHID: 41955 CASRN: 139-87-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E19

M4ID: 30006280

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	154.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.93	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.43 MAX_MED: 3.87 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Ethyl orthoformate

CHID: 41957 CASRN: 122-51-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P05

M4ID: 30006414

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	146.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.65	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1.95 MAX_MED: 2.32 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Flufenoxuron

CHID: 41978 CASRN: 101463-69-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E01

M4ID: 30006682

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	172.71	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.57	MAX_MED:	3.87	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Glyceryl monoricinoleate

CHID: 42007 CASRN: 1323-38-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M07

M4ID: 30006484

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	135.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 3.94 MAX_MED: 3.98 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Isoborneol

CHID: 42060 CASRN: 124-76-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091021

M4ID: 30006038

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	108.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.45	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.184 MAX_MED: 0.273 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: N,N'-Dibutylthiourea
 CHID: 42187 CASRN: 109-46-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D12
 M4ID: 30006311

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	134.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.86 MAX_MED: 4.7 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: N,N-Diisopropylaniline

CHID: 42189 CASRN: 4107-98-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N08

M4ID: 30006459

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	149.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.79	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	5.61	MAX_MED:	4.87	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: N,N'-Dimethylthiourea

CHID: 42191 CASRN: 534-13-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091016

M4ID: 30006043

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	183.09	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.6	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.19 MAX_MED: -1.03 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Propylbenzene

CHID: 42219 CASRN: 103-65-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B11

M4ID: 30006744

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	181.55	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.56	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	7.38	MAX_MED:	5.96	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dimethoxydimethylsilane
CHID: 42379 CASRN: 1112-39-6
SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I12
M4ID: 30006191

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	174.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.405 MAX_MED: 0.885 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Sulfosuccinic acid
 CHID: 42426 CASRN: 5138-18-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P19
 M4ID: 30006016

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	143.64	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.59	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 1 MAX_MED: 1.36 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Tetradecanoic acid, 2,3-dihydroxypropyl ester

CHID: 42454 CASRN: 589-68-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E14

M4ID: 30006285

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	182.48	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.73	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.48 MAX_MED: 6.29 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2,6,10-Trimethyl-2,6,10-triazaundecane

CHID: 44564 CASRN: 3855-32-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L15

M4ID: 30006116

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	159.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.14 MAX_MED: 0.741 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Glycidyl trimethylammonium chloride

CHID: 44643 CASRN: 3033-77-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F21

M4ID: 30006254

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	126.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.89	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.041 MAX_MED: 1.52 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Acid Red 337

CHID: 44713 CASRN: 67786-14-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L07

M4ID: 30006124

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	191.59	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.02 MAX_MED: 0.198 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Terpinyl propionate

CHID: 44833 CASRN: 80-27-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P15

M4ID: 30006404

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	172.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.95	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.85 MAX_MED: 5.86 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Isopropyl triethanolamine titanate

CHID: 44928 CASRN: 36673-16-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C10

M4ID: 30006337

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	174.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	4.63	MAX_MED:	6.22	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: tert-Butylbenzene

CHID: 47138 CASRN: 98-06-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F02

M4ID: 30006657

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	148.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.83	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	5.8	MAX_MED:	6.4	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: CI-1018

CHID: 47248 CASRN: NOCAS_47248

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F13

M4ID: 30006262

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	169.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.87	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.52 MAX_MED: -0.475 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: CP-409092

CHID: 47276 CASRN: 194098-25-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J01

M4ID: 30006562

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	132.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.03	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.968 MAX_MED: 1.68 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: CP-457677

CHID: 47278 CASRN: 214535-77-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N01

M4ID: 30006466

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	140.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	0.987	MAX_MED:	1.63	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: CP-671305

CHID: 47282 CASRN: 445295-04-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K07

M4ID: 30006532

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	136.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.41	MAX_MED:	3.23	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: PHA-00543613

CHID: 47284 CASRN: 478149-53-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H01

M4ID: 30006226

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	129.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.91	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0796 MAX_MED: -0.224 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: CP-422935

CHID: 47299 CASRN: NOCAS_47299

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J01

M4ID: 30006178

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	120.35	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	1.66	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.922 MAX_MED: 0.667 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: CP-608039

CHID: 47305 CASRN: NOCAS_47305

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M02

M4ID: 30006489

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	146.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.72	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	2.44	MAX_MED:	3.34	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: UK-156819

CHID: 47309 CASRN: 162706-14-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N09

M4ID: 30006074

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	181.52	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.81	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-1.77	MAX_MED:	0.0147	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: SSR162369

CHID: 47346 CASRN: NOCAS_47346

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C05

M4ID: 30006726

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	165.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.49	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	5.31	MAX_MED:	5.25	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: AVE3295

CHID: 47372 CASRN: 478263-98-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K02

M4ID: 30006537

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	156.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	3.38	MAX_MED:	1.68	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Potassium chlorate

CHID: 47448 CASRN: 3811-04-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H16

M4ID: 30006211

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	181.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-1.72	MAX_MED:	-2.03	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Hexanedioic acid, di-C7-9-branched and linear ;

CHID: 47517 CASRN: 68515-75-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K09

M4ID: 30006146

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	167.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.83	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 4.61 MAX_MED: 3.33 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Trioctyl trimellitate

CHID: 47533 CASRN: 89-04-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L03

M4ID: 30006128

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	157.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.07	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 2.86 MAX_MED: 2.95 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1,4-Heptanolid

CHID: 47611 CASRN: 105-21-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J13

M4ID: 30006166

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	172.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.82	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-1.76	MAX_MED:	-1.78	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Cremophor EL

CHID: 47696 CASRN: 61791-12-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L02

M4ID: 30006513

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	174.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.98	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 5.61 MAX_MED: 5.72 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Methyl abietate

CHID: 48190 CASRN: 127-25-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I14

M4ID: 30006189

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	156.19	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.06	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	0.813	MAX_MED:	1.01	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Isopropyl phenyl ketone

CHID: 48202 CASRN: 611-70-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G15

M4ID: 30006620

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	128.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.06	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	1.18	MAX_MED:	1.58	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-Chloropentylbenzene

CHID: 48206 CASRN: 79098-20-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C14

M4ID: 30006333

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	172.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.99	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.55 MAX_MED: 6.63 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Methyl 2-methylbenzoate

CHID: 48208 CASRN: 89-71-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N04

M4ID: 30006463

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	156.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.4	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	6.67	MAX_MED:	6.63	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	4	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Auramine hydrochloride

CHID: 20114 CASRN: 2465-27-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J09

M4ID: 30006554

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	238.71	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	11.89	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-2.34	MAX_MED:	-3.07	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: tert-Butylhydroquinone

CHID: 20220 CASRN: 1948-33-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C21

M4ID: 30006710

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	231.98	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	12.99	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 33.7 MAX_MED: 33.4 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Cyclohexanone

CHID: 20359 CASRN: 108-94-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I17

M4ID: 30006570

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	159.39	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.18	MAX_MED:	-0.66	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dibenzo(a,h)anthracene
 CHID: 20409 CASRN: 53-70-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H04
 M4ID: 30006607

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.02e-05	2.77	5.55
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.31	-0.134	6.89	0.137	11.6
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	222.83	228.83	232.59
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	9.07	9.07	9.04

MAX_MEAN: 5.5 MAX_MED: 5.96 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dichlone

CHID: 20425 CASRN: 117-80-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E09

M4ID: 30006674

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.39e-09	1.91	1.12
sd:	5.57e-05	1130	61700

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.24e-09	1.42	1.54	1.88	5.83
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	188.72	194.72	198.72
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	6.59	6.59	6.59

MAX_MEAN: -0.728 MAX_MED: 0.777 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 17alpha-Ethinylestradiol

CHID: 20576 CASRN: 57-63-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J08

M4ID: 30006171 BRK

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	338.5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	61.77	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 95.4 MAX_MED: 93.1 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10; 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Fluometuron

CHID: 20628 CASRN: 2164-17-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078012

M4ID: 30006431

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.00195	2.79	7.92
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.83	1.01	8	1.26	18
sd:	4.87	0.0621	32.9	0.107	50.4

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	169.59	175.59	180.66
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0
RMSE:	3.78	3.78	3.82

MAX_MEAN: 5.32 MAX_MED: 5.47 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Glycerol

CHID: 20663 CASRN: 56-81-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C17

M4ID: 30006714 BRK

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	295.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	34.79	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 80.2 MAX_MED: 77.6 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10; 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: FD&C Green No. 3

CHID: 20673 CASRN: 2353-45-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N22

M4ID: 30006445

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.23e-07	2.8	3.1
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	8.42e-10	1.71	7.93	2.23	7.65
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	220.84	226.84	230.84
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	8.82	8.82	8.82

MAX_MEAN: 3.81 MAX_MED: 3.87 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 8-Hydroxyquinoline
 CHID: 20730 CASRN: 148-24-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N06
 M4ID: 30006077

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.21e-08 2.5 1.87
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 5.96e-10 1.85 0.818 2.38 1.78
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	218.24	224.24	228.24
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	8.52	8.52	8.52

MAX_MEAN: 0.603 MAX_MED: 1.19 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Maleic hydrazide

CHID: 20792 CASRN: 123-33-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C04

M4ID: 30006343

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	174.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.92 MAX_MED: 7.6 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Methyl carbamate

CHID: 20834 CASRN: 598-55-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A22

M4ID: 30006373

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	224.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	9.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 12.5 MAX_MED: 10.7 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2,2'-Methylenebis(4-methyl-6-tert-butylphenol)

CHID: 20870 CASRN: 119-47-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P16

M4ID: 30006403

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.218	2.8	7.97
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.63	0.178	2.37	0.428	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	254.46	260.46	264.45
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	15.1	15.1	15.1

MAX_MEAN: 10.6 MAX_MED: 11.1 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Nitrofurazone

CHID: 20944 CASRN: 59-87-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078005

M4ID: 30006438

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	211.59	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	9.04	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.621 MAX_MED: -0.561 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: N-Nitrosodimethylamine

CHID: 21029 CASRN: 62-75-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P13

M4ID: 30006406

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.34	2	8
sd:	2.22	0.118	12.7

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.42e-08	0.0228	2.36	0.304	6.22
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	182.15	183.81	192.15
PROB:	0.69	0.3	0
RMSE:	4.62	4.32	4.62

MAX_MEAN: 4.42 MAX_MED: 2.58 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.31

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Oxazepam

CHID: 21087 CASRN: 604-75-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A15

M4ID: 30006764

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	218.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.04	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 10.5 MAX_MED: 9.86 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1,3-Benzenediamine
 CHID: 21137 CASRN: 108-45-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A21
 M4ID: 30006758 BRK

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	265.82	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	21.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 52.1 MAX_MED: 48.5 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Phenylmercuric acetate
 CHID: 21150 CASRN: 62-38-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E09
 M4ID: 30006290 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 4.09e-08 2.68 1.67
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 9.15e-10 1.95 2.39 2.31 6.4
 sd: 3.53e-05 6390 173000 5740 534000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	247.81	253.81	257.81
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	14.14	14.14	14.14

MAX_MEAN: 2.68 MAX_MED: 2.71 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Rifampicin
 CHID: 21244 CASRN: 13292-46-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P17
 M4ID: 30006018

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 9.07e-10 1.85 1.04
 sd: 3.31e-05 1360 58700

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 2.01e-09 1.62 2.85 1.92 4.86
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	167.23	173.23	177.23
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	3.84	3.84	3.84

MAX_MEAN: 1.18 MAX_MED: 0.46 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: dl-alpha-Tocopheryl acetate

CHID: 21356 CASRN: 52225-20-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D08

M4ID: 30006699

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	205.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.67	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 11.3 MAX_MED: 10.1 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1,2,4-Trimethylbenzene
 CHID: 21402 CASRN: 95-63-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I08
 M4ID: 30006195 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 5.85 2.38 8
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 9.11e-07 0.234 7.97 0.504 18
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	251.95	257.61	261.95
PROB:	0.94	0.06	0.01
RMSE:	33.81	33.81	33.81

MAX_MEAN: 61 MAX_MED: 89.9 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Triphenyltin hydroxide

CHID: 21409 CASRN: 76-87-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I21

M4ID: 30006566

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	267.45	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	18.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-1.23	MAX_MED:	-0.898	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: FD&C Yellow 5

CHID: 21455 CASRN: 1934-21-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C18

M4ID: 30006329

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	177.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 8.07 MAX_MED: 7.53 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-(2-Butoxyethoxy)ethanol

CHID: 21519 CASRN: 112-34-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N17

M4ID: 30006450

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.76	2.3	8
sd:	59	1.1	22.1

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	8.85e-06	-0.59	7.96	-0.31	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	174.48	178.66	184.48
PROB:	0.88	0.11	0.01
RMSE:	3.93	3.83	3.93

MAX_MEAN: 2.8 MAX_MED: 3.19 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.12

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-[2-(2-Butoxyethoxy)ethoxy]ethanol

CHID: 21520 CASRN: 143-22-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F16

M4ID: 30006643

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	170.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.06	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	8.67	MAX_MED:	8.42	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Decanal

CHID: 21553 CASRN: 112-31-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E24

M4ID: 30006659

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	155.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	7.78	MAX_MED:	7.99	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Decanoic acid

CHID: 21554 CASRN: 334-48-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D21

M4ID: 30006686

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	201.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.92	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	15.3	MAX_MED:	15.9	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dalapon

CHID: 21575 CASRN: 75-99-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P22

M4ID: 30006397

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	168.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.93	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 8.04 MAX_MED: 7.86 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Tetradecanoic acid

CHID: 21666 CASRN: 544-63-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L23

M4ID: 30006492

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	185.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.73	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.912 MAX_MED: -0.309 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Tris(2-butoxyethyl) phosphate

CHID: 21758 CASRN: 78-51-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078022

M4ID: 30006421

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.0192	2.8	7.98
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.39	0.658	7.92	1.69	18
sd:	1.59	1.24	170	0.126	280

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	175.31	181.31	182.93
PROB:	0.93	0.05	0.02
RMSE:	4.21	4.21	4.08

MAX_MEAN: 4.6 MAX_MED: 3.79 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.07

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 3-Trifluoromethyl-4-nitrophenol

CHID: 21788 CASRN: 88-30-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091023

M4ID: 30006036

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	196.48	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.98	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-1.64	MAX_MED:	-1.2	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dichlorophen

CHID: 21824 CASRN: 97-23-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N13

M4ID: 30006070

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	253.53	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	14.79	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-3.73	MAX_MED:	-3.52	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Cyclohexanol

CHID: 21894 CASRN: 108-93-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F17

M4ID: 30006642

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	170.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	9.78	MAX_MED:	9.27	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Tributyl phosphate
 CHID: 21986 CASRN: 126-73-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K01
 M4ID: 30006154

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.08e-10	2.07	1.27
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	6.91e-12	1.58	1.55	1.97	5.57
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	140.82	146.82	150.82
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	2.6	2.6	2.6

MAX_MEAN: 0.265 MAX_MED: 0.697 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: DEET

CHID: 21995 CASRN: 134-62-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A08

M4ID: 30006387

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	224.45	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	9	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 9.95 MAX_MED: 10.1 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1,3-Dichlorobenzene

CHID: 22056 CASRN: 541-73-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C22

M4ID: 30006325

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	181.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.6	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.98 MAX_MED: 7.79 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: gamma-Decanolactone
CHID: 22109 CASRN: 706-14-9
SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D17
M4ID: 30006690

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	268.38	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	22.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 53.1 MAX_MED: 51.5 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Propanil
 CHID: 22111 CASRN: 709-98-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N24
 M4ID: 30006059

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 5.78e-09 2.56 1.55
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 8.49e-10 1.35 0.647 1.83 5.69
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	201.35	207.35	211.35
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	6.56	6.56	6.56

MAX_MEAN: 1.81 MAX_MED: 1.57 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Bromoxynil
 CHID: 22162 CASRN: 1689-84-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E21
 M4ID: 30006278

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 3.77e-09 2.6 1.29
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 1.11e-10 1.81 2.67 2.56 5.59
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	172.21	178.21	182.21
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.16	4.16	4.16

MAX_MEAN: 1.91 MAX_MED: 1.63 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 17alpha-Estradiol

CHID: 22377 CASRN: 57-91-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K06

M4ID: 30006533 BRK

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	357.17	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	81.41	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 106 MAX_MED: 103 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10; 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Digoxin

CHID: 22934 CASRN: 20830-75-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F14

M4ID: 30006645

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.00313	2.8	7.37
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	9.68	-0.44	5.77	0.149	13.3
sd:	210	104	1070	50.6	1520

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	253.98	259.98	262.28
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	14.7	14.7	14.39

MAX_MEAN: 9.55 MAX_MED: 10.1 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 6-Thioguanine

CHID: 23652 CASRN: 154-42-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E05

M4ID: 30006678

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.000302	2.8	7.59
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.14e-09	0.647	5.03	0.973	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	205.59	211.59	215.59
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	7.05	7.05	7.05

MAX_MEAN: 5.54 MAX_MED: 6.36 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-Nitrotoluene

CHID: 23792 CASRN: 99-99-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D06

M4ID: 30006701

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	208.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.91	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 11.1 MAX_MED: 9.61 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Isophorone diisocyanate
 CHID: 23826 CASRN: 4098-71-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B08
 M4ID: 30006747

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	203.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.79	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 12.3 MAX_MED: 9.83 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Acetochlor
 CHID: 23848 CASRN: 34256-82-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E24
 M4ID: 30006275

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.66e-07 2.78 3.94
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 2.45 -0.224 7.32 0.598 17.5
 sd: 44.8 39.6 513 1.09 3950

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	184.83	190.83	193.04
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.02
RMSE:	5.32	5.32	5.26

MAX_MEAN: 3.45 MAX_MED: 3.38 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Aldoxycarb

CHID: 23862 CASRN: 1646-88-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078001

M4ID: 30006442

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	171.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.93	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.82	MAX_MED:	-1.15	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Cyclohexylamine

CHID: 23996 CASRN: 108-91-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F08

M4ID: 30006651

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	161.55	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.67	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 8.9 MAX_MED: 9.25 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dimethipin

CHID: 24052 CASRN: 55290-64-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K13

M4ID: 30006526

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	209.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.86	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.86 MAX_MED: -1.85 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1,3-Dinitrobenzene

CHID: 24065 CASRN: 99-65-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N14

M4ID: 30006069

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	214.76	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.72	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.428 MAX_MED: -0.726 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Flutolanil
 CHID: 24109 CASRN: 66332-96-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G17
 M4ID: 30006234

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 4.86e-11 1.59 1.02
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 4.77e-09 1.48 0.937 1.76 5.65
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	178.08	184.08	188.08
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.71	4.71	4.71

MAX_MEAN: 0.0359 MAX_MED: 0.0463 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Methamidophos

CHID: 24177 CASRN: 10265-92-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A04

M4ID: 30006391

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	222.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.65	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 10.7 MAX_MED: 10.6 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Oxyfluorfen
 CHID: 24241 CASRN: 42874-03-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L08
 M4ID: 30006123

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.24e-08 2.56 1.76
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 1.44e-09 2.09 1.48 2.41 6.63
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	163.92	169.92	173.92
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	3.66	3.66	3.66

MAX_MEAN: 1.56 MAX_MED: 2.13 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Phosphoric acid
 CHID: 24263 CASRN: 7664-38-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K14
 M4ID: 30006141

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 3.41e-10 -1.5 1.12
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 6.99e-08 -1.71 1.52 -1.44 6.9
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	169	175	179
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	3.95	3.95	3.95

MAX_MEAN: 0.808 MAX_MED: 0.717 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Prometryn
 CHID: 24272 CASRN: 7287-19-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G16
 M4ID: 30006235

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.29e-07 2.69 4.99
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 3.17e-09 2.3 7.99 3.04 0.62
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	205.7	211.7	215.7
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	6.68	6.68	6.68

MAX_MEAN: 1.76 MAX_MED: 3.01 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Propargite
 CHID: 24276 CASRN: 2312-35-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D06
 M4ID: 30006317

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 2.1e-09 2.7 1.33
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 2.17e-09 2.2 2.3 2.69 4.6
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	224.02	230.02	234.02
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	9.26	9.26	9.26

MAX_MEAN: 3.62 MAX_MED: 2.39 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Sodium fluoroacetate

CHID: 24311 CASRN: 62-74-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N13

M4ID: 30006454

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	199.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.9	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-3.65	MAX_MED:	-3.5	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Myclobutanil

CHID: 24315 CASRN: 88671-89-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G24

M4ID: 30006611

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.0648	2.79	7.99
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.03e-09	2.29	7.44	3.57	0.333
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	196.92	202.92	206.92
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	6.47	6.47	6.47

MAX_MEAN: 7.55 MAX_MED: 6.83 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2,4,5-Trichlorophenol
 CHID: 24359 CASRN: 95-95-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J22
 M4ID: 30006157

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.81e-09	2.24	0.311
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.64	0.656	0.3	1.03	17.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	197.06	203.06	205.15
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.02
RMSE:	6.04	6.04	5.92

MAX_MEAN: 3.63 MAX_MED: 3.9 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 5-Amino-2-methylphenol
 CHID: 24489 CASRN: 2835-95-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N10
 M4ID: 30006457

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.67e-08	2.62	2.83
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	6.22e-11	2.08	6.09	2.38	4.64
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	199.32	205.32	209.32
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	6.04	6.04	6.04

MAX_MEAN: 1.77 MAX_MED: 3.3 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Benzothiazole

CHID: 24586 CASRN: 95-16-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A02

M4ID: 30006777

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	240.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	11.63	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 12.9 MAX_MED: 13.6 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Colchicine
 CHID: 24845 CASRN: 64-86-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J06
 M4ID: 30006173

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 2.97e-09 1.49 1.5
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 3.45e-08 1.2 2.15 1.5 5.65
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	237.58	243.58	247.58
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	11.1	11.1	11.1

MAX_MEAN: -0.381 MAX_MED: 0.284 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Cycloheximide
 CHID: 24882 CASRN: 66-81-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D09
 M4ID: 30006698

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 2.44e-08 2.46 1.81
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 2.3e-08 2.12 2.92 2.38 3.19
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	260.61	266.61	270.61
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	16.59	16.59	16.59

MAX_MEAN: 1.53 MAX_MED: 1.15 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 3,4-Diaminotoluene

CHID: 24930 CASRN: 496-72-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M03

M4ID: 30006104

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	177.81	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	0.0737	MAX_MED:	-0.941	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4,4'-Dichlorodiphenyl sulfone

CHID: 24986 CASRN: 80-07-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B22

M4ID: 30006349

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	188.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.42	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	10.5	MAX_MED:	8.23	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dimethyl succinate

CHID: 25152 CASRN: 106-65-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A24

M4ID: 30006755

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	243.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	12.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 17.5 MAX_MED: 19.7 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Isopropyl acetate

CHID: 25478 CASRN: 108-21-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P20

M4ID: 30006399

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	169.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	7.1	MAX_MED:	8.51	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Isoproterenol hydrochloride
 CHID: 25486 CASRN: 51-30-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H10
 M4ID: 30006601

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.05e-08	2.68	2.7
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	9.48e-10	1.16	2.6	1.59	4.52
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	189.58	195.58	199.58
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	5.27	5.27	5.27

MAX_MEAN: 0.265 MAX_MED: 1.49 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Maltol

CHID: 25523 CASRN: 118-71-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B21

M4ID: 30006734 BRK

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	258.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	20.4	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 55.2 MAX_MED: 59.7 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Methylene bis(thiocyanate)

CHID: 25599 CASRN: 6317-18-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M19

M4ID: 30006472

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	159.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.41	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.261 MAX_MED: -0.636 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Octhilinone

CHID: 25805 CASRN: 26530-20-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L06

M4ID: 30006125

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	238.52	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	11.94	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.45 MAX_MED: -1.26 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1,10-Phenanthroline
 CHID: 25857 CASRN: 66-71-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H18
 M4ID: 30006209

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	8.97e-10	1.8	1.73
sd:	2.16e-05	1100	98600

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.56e-09	1.17	2.21	1.49	5.58
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	212.29	218.29	222.29
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	7.53	7.53	7.53

MAX_MEAN: 2.04 MAX_MED: 1.74 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Sodium dodecyl sulfate
 CHID: 26031 CASRN: 151-21-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H22
 M4ID: 30006589

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.0253	2.79	7.94
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.16e-09	2.25	6.26	3.44	9.51
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	220.18	226.18	230.18
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	9.78	9.78	9.78

MAX_MEAN: 4.95 MAX_MED: 3.48 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Terephthalic acid

CHID: 26080 CASRN: 100-21-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B14

M4ID: 30006741

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	189.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.75	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	13.2	MAX_MED:	10.6	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Theobromine
 CHID: 26132 CASRN: 83-67-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P14
 M4ID: 30006405

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 3.58e-11 -0.586 3.63
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 5.76e-09 -0.738 5 -0.333 4.12
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	176.23	182.23	186.23
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.22	4.22	4.22

MAX_MEAN: 2.95 MAX_MED: 2.92 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Triclocarban
 CHID: 26214 CASRN: 101-20-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L21
 M4ID: 30006110

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.93e-08 2.72 1.81
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 4.46 -0.198 0.3 0.664 16.8
 sd: 17.3 11.4 1.28 0.99 263

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	197.22	203.22	205.04
PROB:	0.93	0.05	0.02
RMSE:	5.87	5.87	5.73

MAX_MEAN: 2.73 MAX_MED: 2.97 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.07

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Triglycidyl isocyanurate

CHID: 26262 CASRN: 2451-62-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I06

M4ID: 30006197

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	186.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.29	MAX_MED:	-0.185	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 3-Pyridinecarbonitrile
CHID: 26665 CASRN: 100-54-9
SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B18
M4ID: 30006353

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	183.51	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.66	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 8.62 MAX_MED: 9.09 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Isopropyl tetradecanoate

CHID: 26838 CASRN: 110-27-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B06

M4ID: 30006749

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	219.24	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.44	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 13.1 MAX_MED: 11.2 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Tetraethylene glycol
 CHID: 26922 CASRN: 112-60-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E17
 M4ID: 30006666

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	231.94	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	12.67	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 31.7 MAX_MED: 29.9 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2,4-Di-tert-pentylphenol
 CHID: 26974 CASRN: 120-95-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L16
 M4ID: 30006115

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 8.31e-10 1.21 1.23
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 2.07e-08 0.38 1.87 1.09 6.08
 sd: 0.000888 40400 65700 24300 462000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	236.08	242.08	246.08
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	11.61	11.61	11.61

MAX_MEAN: -0.515 MAX_MED: 0.11 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Sodium dimethyldithiocarbamate

CHID: 27050 CASRN: 128-04-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P10

M4ID: 30006409

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.0477	2.79	7.99
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.66e-09	2.22	7.41	3.11	1.11
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	194.2	200.2	204.2
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	5.66	5.66	5.66

MAX_MEAN: 3.52 MAX_MED: 4.38 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: N-Methylphthalimide

CHID: 27198 CASRN: 550-44-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P08

M4ID: 30006411

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	172.48	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.05	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	8.2	MAX_MED:	8.76	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Octamethylcyclotetrasiloxane

CHID: 27205 CASRN: 556-67-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G14

M4ID: 30006237

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	168.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.74	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.577	MAX_MED:	-0.434	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dibutyltin dichloride

CHID: 27292 CASRN: 683-18-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H06

M4ID: 30006221

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	260.18	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	16.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-1.09	MAX_MED:	-0.995	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2,3-Diaminotoluene
 CHID: 27494 CASRN: 2687-25-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M10
 M4ID: 30006481

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 9.73 2.32 8
 sd: 205 1.93 20.3

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 2.92e-08 -0.536 1.64 -0.13 7.21
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	209.15	213.91	219.15
PROB:	0.91	0.08	0.01
RMSE:	7.21	7.1	7.21

MAX_MEAN: 4.05 MAX_MED: 2.71 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.09

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Malic acid

CHID: 27640 CASRN: 6915-15-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P12

M4ID: 30006407

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	167.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	10.5	MAX_MED:	11.7	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Ammonium xylene sulfonate

CHID: 27899 CASRN: 26447-10-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C04

M4ID: 30006727

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	220.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.91	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 11.7 MAX_MED: 7.29 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 3-Iodo-2-propynyl-N-butylcarbamate

CHID: 28038 CASRN: 55406-53-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M23

M4ID: 30006468

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	257.85	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	15.88	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-1.96	MAX_MED:	-3.09	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Clopyralid

CHID: 29221 CASRN: 1702-17-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D04

M4ID: 30006319

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	166.85	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.65	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.98 MAX_MED: 7.15 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

Percent Activity

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2,4-Bis(1-methyl-1-phenylethyl)phenol

CHID: 29241 CASRN: 2772-45-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J04

M4ID: 30006175

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.55e-08	2.61	2.08
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.01	0.609	7.94	1.26	14.4
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	232.91	238.91	242.02
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	11.27	11.27	11.18

MAX_MEAN: 4.05 MAX_MED: 2.73 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Sodium lauryl polyoxyethylene ether sulfate

CHID: 29298 CASRN: 9004-82-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J21

M4ID: 30006542

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.69	-0.13	6.91
sd:	1.72	13.8	728

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	6.05	0.653	1.07	1.88	18
sd:	3.96	0.789	1.81	0.0646	25.3

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	219.55	224.59	220.51
PROB:	0.59	0.05	0.36
RMSE:	9.76	10.21	9.31

MAX_MEAN: 5.34 MAX_MED: 5.93 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.41

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Acetyl cedrene
 CHID: 29353 CASRN: 32388-55-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B17
 M4ID: 30006738 BRK

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	325.5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	50.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 95.4 MAX_MED: 89.7 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10; 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Chlorhexidine diacetate
 CHID: 32345 CASRN: 56-95-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J10
 M4ID: 30006169 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 7.9e-10 2.15 1.25
 sd: 1.11e-05 9130 54300

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 2.3e-09 1.17 2.1 1.51 5.44
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	242.94	248.94	252.94
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	13.33	13.33	13.33

MAX_MEAN: -0.544 MAX_MED: 1.23 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Triclosan

CHID: 32498 CASRN: 3380-34-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091006

M4ID: 30006053

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.35e-09	2.32	1.72
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.52e-10	2.05	2.54	2.48	4.73
sd:	2.51e-05	12200	819000	6910	1400000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	225.12	231.12	235.12
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	9.89	9.89	9.89

MAX_MEAN: 0.659 MAX_MED: 1.79 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4,5-Dichloro-3H-1,2-dithiol-3-one

CHID: 32518 CASRN: 1192-52-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F24

M4ID: 30006635

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	139.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.71	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	7.11	MAX_MED:	7.5	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1,2-Benzisothiazolin-3-one

CHID: 32523 CASRN: 2634-33-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E22

M4ID: 30006661

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	192.58	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.53	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	8.57	MAX_MED:	7.55	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Bifenazate

CHID: 32525 CASRN: 149877-41-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G22

M4ID: 30006229

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	9.29e-08	2.77	2.82
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.71	1.09	0.3	1.35	9.24
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	198.77	204.77	206.32
PROB:	0.93	0.05	0.02
RMSE:	6.28	6.28	6.14

MAX_MEAN: 4.07 MAX_MED: 4.72 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.07

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Fenpyroximate (Z,E)

CHID: 32550 CASRN: 111812-58-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E11

M4ID: 30006288

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	245.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	13.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.227	MAX_MED:	-0.187	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Fluazinam

CHID: 32551 CASRN: 79622-59-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A01

M4ID: 30006394

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.00529	2.79	7.91
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.26e-09	2.26	0.392	4.1	0.374
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	214.47	220.47	224.47
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	7.76	7.76	7.76

MAX_MEAN: 8.63 MAX_MED: 8.32 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Flufenacet
 CHID: 32552 CASRN: 142459-58-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N16
 M4ID: 30006451

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 0.0195 2.8 7.97
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 2.02e-09 2.3 6.85 3.35 8.19
 sd: NA NA NA NA NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	181.93	187.93	191.93
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	5.02	5.02	5.02

MAX_MEAN: 6.59 MAX_MED: 7.45 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Prallethrin

CHID: 32572 CASRN: 23031-36-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078019

M4ID: 30006424

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.82e-10	1.8	1.34
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	9.43e-09	1.86	1.82	2.23	4.97
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	203.37	209.37	213.37
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	7.43	7.43	7.43

MAX_MEAN: 0.361 MAX_MED: 0.668 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Pyridaben

CHID: 32573 CASRN: 96489-71-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M09

M4ID: 30006098

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	244.5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.93 MAX_MED: -0.176 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Trifloxystrobin
 CHID: 32580 CASRN: 141517-21-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J24
 M4ID: 30006155

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 2.89e-08 2.57 2
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 8.14e-10 1.36 1.15 1.76 5.4
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	232.04	238.04	242.04
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	10.44	10.44	10.44

MAX_MEAN: 0.996 MAX_MED: 1.22 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Flumetsulam

CHID: 32615 CASRN: 98967-40-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078016

M4ID: 30006427

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	155.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.06	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	5.86	MAX_MED:	7.3	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Pyraclostrobin

CHID: 32638 CASRN: 175013-18-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L24

M4ID: 30006107

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.51e-10	0.614	1.45
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	6.03e-09	0.736	1.17	1.04	5.68
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	234.46	240.46	244.46
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	10.72	10.72	10.72

MAX_MEAN: 0.903 MAX_MED: 0.644 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Z-Tetrachlorvinphos
 CHID: 32648 CASRN: 22248-79-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N21
 M4ID: 30006062

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 2.58e-10 1.13 1.54
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 2.87e-09 1.18 2.17 1.62 4.89
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	190.18	196.18	200.18
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	5.67	5.67	5.67

MAX_MEAN: 0.267 MAX_MED: 0.462 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Indoxacarb

CHID: 32690 CASRN: 173584-44-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H09

M4ID: 30006602

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.13e-10	2.57	0.508
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.77	1.02	8	1.58	6.39
sd:	3.36	0.26	62.3	0.885	42.5

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	115.06	121.06	121.86
PROB:	0.92	0.05	0.03
RMSE:	3.55	3.55	3.34

MAX_MEAN: 3.69 MAX_MED: 3.69 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.08

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Cyclopentanol

CHID: 33371 CASRN: 96-41-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A05

M4ID: 30006774

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	218.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.33	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 10.6 MAX_MED: 9.34 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Tebufenpyrad
 CHID: 34223 CASRN: 119168-77-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G06
 M4ID: 30006245

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	254.48	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	14.75	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.154 MAX_MED: -0.736 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Metconazole

CHID: 34497 CASRN: 125116-23-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078011

M4ID: 30006432

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.0877	2.8	7.98
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.07	1.04	7.93	1.68	17.6
sd:	3.71	0.619	107	0.176	118

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	219.15	225.15	228.07
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	9.98	9.98	9.92

MAX_MEAN: 3.01 MAX_MED: 4.3 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Diclosulam

CHID: 34528 CASRN: 145701-21-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K23

M4ID: 30006516

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	207.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -1.82 MAX_MED: -1.94 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Ethofumesate
 CHID: 34580 CASRN: 26225-79-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K17
 M4ID: 30006138

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 3.02e-09 1.95 1.05
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 1.27e-11 1.71 1.11 2.31 5.98
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	180.65	186.65	190.65
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.93	4.93	4.93

MAX_MEAN: 0.817 MAX_MED: 0.467 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Fluoxastrobin

CHID: 34625 CASRN: 361377-29-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J05

M4ID: 30006558

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.18e-09	1.54	0.781
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.21e-09	1.44	1.21	1.84	5.68
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	245.62	251.62	255.62
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	13.07	13.07	13.07

MAX_MEAN: 0.633 MAX_MED: 0.722 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Hexaconazole

CHID: 34653 CASRN: 79983-71-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078003

M4ID: 30006440

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	228.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	10.77	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-1.05	MAX_MED:	-1.49	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Azamethiphos

CHID: 34818 CASRN: 35575-96-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K03

M4ID: 30006152

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	195.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.883	MAX_MED:	-0.871	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Thiamethoxam

CHID: 34962 CASRN: 153719-23-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A17

M4ID: 30006378

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	203.69	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	7.55	MAX_MED:	8.89	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Tralkoxydim
 CHID: 34973 CASRN: 87820-88-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L10
 M4ID: 30006121

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 6.07e-10 2.14 1
 sd: 1.38e-05 8950 44900

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 2.74e-11 1.82 2.06 2.16 4.81
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	187.72	193.72	197.72
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	5.55	5.55	5.55

MAX_MEAN: -0.771 MAX_MED: 0.785 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Allethrin

CHID: 35180 CASRN: 584-79-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P05

M4ID: 30006030

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.89e-09	2.25	1.62
sd:	2.24e-05	5050	43900

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.21	1.1	7.97	1.36	17.9
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	185.94	191.94	195.26
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.97	4.97	4.94

MAX_MEAN: 1.95 MAX_MED: 2.3 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Disiquonium chloride
 CHID: 35589 CASRN: 68959-20-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J17
 M4ID: 30006162

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 6.19e-09 2.74 1.43
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 1.35 0.322 8 1.32 18
 sd: 1.13 1.94 51.5 0.323 367

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	171.83	177.83	180.15
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.52	4.52	4.47

MAX_MEAN: 1.43 MAX_MED: 2.26 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Methylbenzethonium chloride

CHID: 35708 CASRN: 25155-18-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D10

M4ID: 30006313

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.205	2.79	7.97
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	6.33	-0.222	0.3	0.585	12.5
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	247.65	253.65	257.09
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	14.18	14.18	14.1

MAX_MEAN: 5.05 MAX_MED: 6.6 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Disodium 4,4'-bis(2-sulfostyryl)biphenyl

CHID: 36467 CASRN: 27344-41-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C12

M4ID: 30006335

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	149.76	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	2.88	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	6.38	MAX_MED:	7.64	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide

CHID: 37028 CASRN: 57-09-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J13

M4ID: 30006550

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	220.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	9.5	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.667 MAX_MED: -0.652 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Amiodarone hydrochloride
 CHID: 37185 CASRN: 19774-82-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091017
 M4ID: 30006042

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 2.76e-09 2.47 1.58
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 4.1e-10 1.91 1.8 2.21 6.06
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	177.86	183.86	187.86
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.71	4.71	4.71

MAX_MEAN: 1.62 MAX_MED: 1.39 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Perfluoroheptanoic acid

CHID: 37303 CASRN: 375-85-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N16

M4ID: 30006067

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	194.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.64	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.896	MAX_MED:	-1.36	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Potassium perfluorooctanesulfonate

CHID: 37706 CASRN: 2795-39-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E06

M4ID: 30006293

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.41	1.14	8
sd:	1.27	0.21	11.1

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.38	1.14	8	2.16	18
sd:	1.34	0.227	12.1	0.567	69.3

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	209.86	210.61	214.04
PROB:	0.55	0.38	0.07
RMSE:	8.43	9.63	8.97

MAX_MEAN: 4.53 MAX_MED: 5.31 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.45

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1,4-Dihydroxy-2-naphthoic acid

CHID: 37730 CASRN: 31519-22-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L09

M4ID: 30006506

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	250.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	15.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.911	MAX_MED:	-2.84	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 5-Chlorosalicylanilide
 CHID: 37749 CASRN: 4638-48-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I21
 M4ID: 30006182

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.17e-07	2.72	3.68
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	7.21e-09	1.69	7.9	1.99	4.26
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	202.69	208.69	212.69
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	6.38	6.38	6.38

MAX_MEAN: 2.08 MAX_MED: 2.89 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Fluorescein

CHID: 38887 CASRN: 2321-07-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D24

M4ID: 30006683

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	193.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.51	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 9.62 MAX_MED: 10.8 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Basic Blue 7

CHID: 38888 CASRN: 2390-60-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K11

M4ID: 30006144

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	259.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	16.54	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-3.03	MAX_MED:	-2.65	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Ethyl heptanoate

CHID: 40112 CASRN: 106-30-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I16

M4ID: 30006571

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	160.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.45	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	6.33	MAX_MED:	7.21	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dinocap
 CHID: 40352 CASRN: 39300-45-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E22
 M4ID: 30006277

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 2.61e-07 2.77 3.23
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 1.21e-08 2.29 6.33 2.75 1.25
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	226.33	232.33	236.33
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	9.39	9.39	9.39

MAX_MEAN: 4.66 MAX_MED: 2.82 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Niclosamide

CHID: 40362 CASRN: 50-65-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A24

M4ID: 30006371

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.78e-05	2.78	6.25
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	6.31e-09	2.3	8	2.92	2.93
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	241.36	247.36	251.36
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	11.93	11.93	11.93

MAX_MEAN: 8.99 MAX_MED: 7.85 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Diniconazole

CHID: 40363 CASRN: 83657-24-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C06

M4ID: 30006341

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.18e-09	2.16	2.34
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	17	0.889	3.6	1.14	17.9
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	237.53	243.53	242.42
PROB:	0.88	0.04	0.08
RMSE:	11.77	11.77	11.12

MAX_MEAN: 12.1 MAX_MED: 11.8 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.12

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Forskolin

CHID: 40484 CASRN: 66575-29-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J23

M4ID: 30006156

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	218.68	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.15 MAX_MED: -2.29 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Octyl gallate

CHID: 40713 CASRN: 1034-01-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K19

M4ID: 30006136

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	202.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	6.6	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.049	MAX_MED:	-0.232	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: (2-Nitro-1-propenyl)benzene

CHID: 41188 CASRN: 705-60-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F04

M4ID: 30006655

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	6.39e-09	2.62	4.05
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.87	1.03	7.96	1.66	17.9
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	200.49	206.49	208.81
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	7.44	7.44	7.38

MAX_MEAN: 8.11 MAX_MED: 5.72 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1,3-Diphenyl-1,3-propanedione

CHID: 41247 CASRN: 120-46-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A17

M4ID: 30006762 BRK

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	351.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	74.51	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 116 MAX_MED: 112 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10; 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 5-Ethyl-5-methylhydantoin

CHID: 41368 CASRN: 5394-36-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C16

M4ID: 30006715

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	215.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.07	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 14.4 MAX_MED: 13.7 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-Morpholinepropanamine

CHID: 41521 CASRN: 123-00-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B10

M4ID: 30006745

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	217.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 9.7 MAX_MED: 10.7 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Bromophenol blue

CHID: 41682 CASRN: 115-39-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C02

M4ID: 30006729

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.3e-06	2.8	5.15
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.15e-09	2.28	8	3.2	12.6
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	213.56	219.56	223.56
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	8.22	8.22	8.22

MAX_MEAN: 10.1 MAX_MED: 12.5 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: C.I. Acid Violet 12, disodium salt

CHID: 41715 CASRN: 6625-46-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K14

M4ID: 30006525

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.59e-08	2.67	3.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	9.14e-10	0.866	4.52	1.13	2.88
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	213.4	219.4	223.4
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	7.59	7.59	7.59

MAX_MEAN: 2.49 MAX_MED: 2.35 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Fluoroacetic acid

CHID: 41981 CASRN: 144-49-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B20

M4ID: 30006351

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	161.45	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	7.41	MAX_MED:	7	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Butyl lactate

CHID: 42196 CASRN: 138-22-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A01

M4ID: 30006778

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	229.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	9.77	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	11.8	MAX_MED:	12.4	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: N-Butyl-p-toluenesulfonamide

CHID: 42198 CASRN: 1907-65-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A16

M4ID: 30006763

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	246.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	12.97	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	18.9	MAX_MED:	19.2	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS: 8

Percent Activity

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1-Dodecyl-2-pyrrolidinone

CHID: 42206 CASRN: 2687-96-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M11

M4ID: 30006480

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.1e-08	2.8	0.306
sd:	0.000305	11300	7980

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.16e-09	2.27	2.2	2.73	5.38
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	215.17	221.18	225.17
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	9.2	9.2	9.2

MAX_MEAN: 3.04 MAX_MED: 3.2 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Oleyl sarcosine

CHID: 42243 CASRN: 110-25-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I11

M4ID: 30006192

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	219.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	8.76	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.64 MAX_MED: -2.67 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Sodium (2-pyridylthio)-N-oxide
 CHID: 42390 CASRN: 3811-73-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E11
 M4ID: 30006672

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.54e-07 2.79 4.29
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 1.52e-09 2.23 1.32 2.65 7.32
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	191.57	197.57	201.57
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	5.41	5.41	5.41

MAX_MEAN: 3.9 MAX_MED: 3.51 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Sodium 4-methylbenzenesulfonate

CHID: 42415 CASRN: 657-84-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C10

M4ID: 30006721

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	190.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.65	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 6.44 MAX_MED: 8.34 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Sodium tridecyl sulfate
 CHID: 42418 CASRN: 3026-63-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P04
 M4ID: 30006415 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 3.16e-07 2.75 4.14
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 5.78e-08 0.848 7.94 1.14 7.64
 sd: 0.00132 3540 312000 2130 3e+05

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	240.04	246.04	250.04
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	12.87	12.87	12.87

MAX_MEAN: 8.33 MAX_MED: 7.19 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: N,N-Dibutyl-N-methylbutan-1-aminium chloride

CHID: 44443 CASRN: 56375-79-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P09

M4ID: 30006410

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.52e-09	0.781	1.87
sd:	5.08e-05	505	124000

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.57e-09	0.0864	2.35	0.388	5.08
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	190.94	196.94	200.94
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	5.45	5.45	5.45

MAX_MEAN: 1.95 MAX_MED: 1.77 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 6:2 Fluorotelomer alcohol

CHID: 44572 CASRN: 647-42-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D02

M4ID: 30006321

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	174.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	6.49	MAX_MED:	7.34	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: MON-4660

CHID: 44575 CASRN: 71526-07-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L13

M4ID: 30006502

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	196.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.61	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -3.12 MAX_MED: -2.86 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-tert-Butyl-4-ethylphenol

CHID: 44581 CASRN: 96-70-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N04

M4ID: 30006079

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.46e-11	1.88	1.36
sd:	2.86e-06	220	123000

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.13e-10	1.57	1.64	2.23	6.23
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	192.11	198.11	202.11
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	5.94	5.94	5.94

MAX_MEAN: 0.505 MAX_MED: 0.734 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2,2'-(Tetradecylimino)diethanol

CHID: 44865 CASRN: 18924-66-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D10

M4ID: 30006697

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	12.1	2.8	7.98
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	17.3	1.22	0.3	1.49	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	252.91	258.92	257.65
PROB:	0.87	0.04	0.08
RMSE:	15.33	15.33	14.58

MAX_MEAN: 10.6 MAX_MED: 9.35 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.13

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Octadecyl sulfate sodium salt

CHID: 47103 CASRN: 1120-04-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091013

M4ID: 30006046

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	200.48	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.98	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-3.58	MAX_MED:	-3.86	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: CP-457920

CHID: 47254 CASRN: 220860-50-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N14

M4ID: 30006453

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.00764	2.79	7.93
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.26e-11	0.541	7.98	0.826	1.42
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	195.93	201.93	205.93
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	5.64	5.64	5.64

MAX_MEAN: 3.51 MAX_MED: 3.79 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: PharmaGSID_47263

CHID: 47263 CASRN: 349495-42-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078024

M4ID: 30006419

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	173.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.04	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	7.38	MAX_MED:	7.23	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: CI-959

CHID: 47268 CASRN: 104795-68-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J09

M4ID: 30006170

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.00162	2.79	7.81
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.73e-09	2.3	4.83	4.28	16.1
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	213.09	219.09	223.09
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	9.31	9.31	9.31

MAX_MEAN: 12.1 MAX_MED: 9.77 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: CP-607366

CHID: 47280 CASRN: 289716-94-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L01

M4ID: 30006514

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	180.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.88	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.426	MAX_MED:	-0.212	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: UK-416244

CHID: 47290 CASRN: 402910-27-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M13

M4ID: 30006094

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	191.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -2.38 MAX_MED: -2.9 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: CP-863187
 CHID: 47294 CASRN: 668981-02-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J14
 M4ID: 30006549

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 3.86e-08 2.73 3.17
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 4.78e-10 0.175 5.26 0.491 5.29
 sd: 6.4e-05 50700 774000 9440 620000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	178.47	184.47	188.47
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.24	4.24	4.24

MAX_MEAN: 2.18 MAX_MED: 3.03 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: MK-812

CHID: 47335 CASRN: 851916-42-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A18

M4ID: 30006377

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	216.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.79	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 10.1 MAX_MED: 10.4 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: SSR180711

CHID: 47359 CASRN: 298198-52-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P24

M4ID: 30006395

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	166.53	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	3.99	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	9.32	MAX_MED:	9.65	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Volinanserin

CHID: 47363 CASRN: 139290-65-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P13

M4ID: 30006022

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	187.23	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	4.82	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-2.22	MAX_MED:	-3.54	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: SSR 103800
 CHID: 47364 CASRN: 1075752-90-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P01
 M4ID: 30006418

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.15e-09 1.69 1.1
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 2.2e-10 1.83 1.33 2.14 4.72
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	211.27	217.27	221.27
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	8.13	8.13	8.13

MAX_MEAN: 0.562 MAX_MED: 0.317 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: SAR377142

CHID: 47385 CASRN: NOCAS_47385

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N17

M4ID: 30006066

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.3e-10	1.87	1.29
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.31e-10	1.8	1.55	2.57	5.62
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	164.46	170.46	174.46
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	3.55	3.55	3.55

MAX_MEAN: -0.0276 MAX_MED: 0.716 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: SAR 150640

CHID: 47389 CASRN: 433212-21-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M17

M4ID: 30006090

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.06e-09	2.64	2.32
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.08	1.05	1.17	1.68	18
sd:	28.3	4.57	5.63	0.117	73.1

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	200.5	206.5	207.24
PROB:	0.92	0.05	0.03
RMSE:	6.93	6.93	6.78

MAX_MEAN: 3.35 MAX_MED: 3.97 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.08

FLAGS:

Percent Activity

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 9-Phenanthroline
CHID: 47592 CASRN: 484-17-3
SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L04
M4ID: 30006511 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):
tp ga gw
val: 2.42e-08 2.71 1.9
sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
tp ga gw la lw
val: 1.32e-06 -0.714 2.31 -0.419 8.06
sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	263.66	269.66	273.66
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	17.73	17.73	17.73

MAX_MEAN: 4.93 MAX_MED: 3.82 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: FR167356

CHID: 48174 CASRN: 174185-16-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G05

M4ID: 30006246

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	212.77	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	7.48	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-3.19	MAX_MED:	-1.68	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Lauryl gallate
 CHID: 48189 CASRN: 1166-52-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H01
 M4ID: 30006610

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.01e-11	1.8	1.27
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.8e-09	1.52	1.44	2.38	5.31
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	176.72	182.72	186.72
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.66	4.66	4.66

MAX_MEAN: -0.043 MAX_MED: 0.52 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-Propylcyclohexanone

CHID: 48198 CASRN: 40649-36-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C14

M4ID: 30006717

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	185.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	5.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	11.1	MAX_MED:	9.27	BMAD:	2.23
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COFF:	22.3	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Cyclobutyl phenyl ketone
 CHID: 48201 CASRN: 5407-98-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078014
 M4ID: 30006429

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.79e-11	-1.74	1.22
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.846	-2.46	0.326	-1.59	9.5
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	186.92	192.92	196.89
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	4.87	4.87	4.87

MAX_MEAN: 0.379 MAX_MED: 0.525 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: PharmaGSID_48505
 CHID: 48505 CASRN: NOCAS_48505
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078007
 M4ID: 30006436

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.67e-09 2.49 0.389
 sd: 2.09e-05 17100 8420

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 4.59e-09 1.97 1.22 2.4 3.01
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	207.86	213.86	217.86
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	7.04	7.04	7.04

MAX_MEAN: 0.681 MAX_MED: 1.16 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Ziram

CHID: 21464 CASRN: 137-30-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A08

M4ID: 30006771

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	10.3	2.8	8
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	24.8	-0.179	0.3	0.609	3.71
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	263.69	269.69	269.45
PROB:	0.9	0.05	0.05
RMSE:	17.4	17.4	16.48

MAX_MEAN: 13.2 MAX_MED: 12.2 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 10 ACTP: 0.1

FLAGS: 8

Percent Activity

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: N-Butylbenzenesulfonamide
 CHID: 27540 CASRN: 3622-84-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H09
 M4ID: 30006218 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	23.7	2.8	7.99
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.351	1.99	8	2.24	17.8
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	229.59	235.59	239.58
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	24.02	24.02	23.98

MAX_MEAN: 51.7 MAX_MED: 54.3 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 10 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Methyltrioctylammonium chloride

CHID: 44487 CASRN: 5137-55-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A09

M4ID: 30006770

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	11.5	2.8	8
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	24.3	-1.07	0.3	-0.0147	16.4
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	276.51	282.52	284.51
PROB:	0.94	0.05	0.02
RMSE:	21.4	21.4	20.85

MAX_MEAN: 14.5 MAX_MED: 15.6 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 10 ACTP: 0.06

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Aspirin

CHID: 20108 CASRN: 50-78-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D13

M4ID: 30006694

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	12.3	2.01	0.959
sd:	6.74	0.523	0.45

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	12.3	2.01	0.958	4.29	3.54
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	176.97	122.54	126.54
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	4.32	1.58	1.58

MAX_MEAN: 8.16 MAX_MED: 7.8 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Benzydine

CHID: 20137 CASRN: 92-87-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G13

M4ID: 30006622

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	7.02	1.18	2.88
sd:	0.997	0.157	2.35

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	7.02	1.18	2.88	3.34	11.4
sd:	0.997	0.157	2.35	32400	355000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	195.23	159.69	163.69
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	5.88	3.1	3.1

MAX_MEAN: 9.91 MAX_MED: 10.6 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Biphenyl

CHID: 20161 CASRN: 92-52-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I06

M4ID: 30006581

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	8.41	1.97	8
sd:	1.39	0.0263	4.88

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	15.5	2.03	8	2.3	17.9
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	168.91	141.23	143.35
PROB:	0	0.74	0.26
RMSE:	4.14	2.4	2.4

MAX_MEAN: 8.85 MAX_MED: 7.71 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-Methyl-2-tert-butylphenol

CHID: 20212 CASRN: 2409-55-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078002

M4ID: 30006441

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.72	1.68	8
sd:	1.01	0.117	11.7

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	6.65	-3.16	0.589	-2.09	7.15
sd:	2230	394	506	603	3970

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	175.06	169.44	181.77
PROB:	0.06	0.94	0
RMSE:	4.11	3.54	3.89

MAX_MEAN: 5.22 MAX_MED: 4.97 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 0.94

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: N,N-Dimethylaniline
 CHID: 20507 CASRN: 121-69-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E08
 M4ID: 30006675

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 5.62 -3.7 7.03
 sd: 0.532 248 1750

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 8.69 0.225 0.3 2.37 16
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	200.88	155.88	164.38
PROB:	0	0.99	0.01
RMSE:	6.1	2.67	3.06

MAX_MEAN: 7.72 MAX_MED: 7.84 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 7,12-Dimethylbenz(a)anthracene
 CHID: 20510 CASRN: 57-97-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E10
 M4ID: 30006673

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 17 1.19 8
 sd: 1.73 0.086 5.17

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 17.7 1.2 8 2.33 17.6
 sd: 1.89 0.0843 5.77 0.0439 24

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	240.61	187.28	190.56
PROB:	0	0.84	0.16
RMSE:	12.64	4.78	4.77

MAX_MEAN: 18.5 MAX_MED: 20.2 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Endrin

CHID: 20561 CASRN: 72-20-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F15

M4ID: 30006260

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	9.61	0.728	1.28
sd:	1.71	0.235	0.935

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	9.61	0.728	1.28	3.35	8.37
sd:	1.71	0.235	0.935	2270	18100

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	213.43	164.21	168.21
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	7.9	3.27	3.27

MAX_MEAN: 13.6 MAX_MED: 15.3 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Isophorone
 CHID: 20759 CASRN: 78-59-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L05
 M4ID: 30006510

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 9.65 1.92 5.83
 sd: 0.868 0.0257 3.73

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 12.9 1.97 4.33 2.35 9.43
 sd: 12.6 0.198 3.11 0.0966 16.9

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	169.23	109.81	112.97
PROB:	0	0.83	0.17
RMSE:	4.19	1.23	1.21

MAX_MEAN: 9.28 MAX_MED: 9.57 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Nitrofurantoin
 CHID: 20972 CASRN: 67-20-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H02
 M4ID: 30006225

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	12	2.18	7.36
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	12.7	2.19	6.46	4.21	2.47
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	71.22	67.87	71.87
PROB:	0.14	0.76	0.1
RMSE:	3.76	2.33	2.33

MAX_MEAN: 10.6 MAX_MED: 10.6 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 0.86

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 6-Propyl-2-thiouracil
 CHID: 21209 CASRN: 51-52-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A20
 M4ID: 30006759

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	9.6	-3.7	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	8.99	-3.7	5.42	3.42	6.42
sd:	0.757	306	1660	417	2370

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	232.85	182.59	186.45
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	10.51	4.68	4.51

MAX_MEAN: 13 MAX_MED: 12.6 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Trifluralin

CHID: 21395 CASRN: 1582-09-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B08

M4ID: 30006363

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	14.5	0.499	0.951
sd:	1.35	0.163	0.353

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	14.5	0.499	0.951	4.26	4.77
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	237.88	167.21	171.21
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	11.33	3.56	3.56

MAX_MEAN: 15 MAX_MED: 15.2 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Diethyl phthalate
 CHID: 21780 CASRN: 84-66-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J16
 M4ID: 30006163

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 16.7 1.88 3.67
 sd: 1.68 0.0444 1.21

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 16.7 1.88 3.67 4.27 18
 sd: NA NA NA NA NA

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	211.73	165.87	169.87
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	7.86	3.52	3.52

MAX_MEAN: 16.2 MAX_MED: 16.3 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-(2-Ethoxyethoxy)ethanol

CHID: 21941 CASRN: 111-90-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G18

M4ID: 30006617

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	6.73	1.28	2.6
sd:	0.906	0.116	1.41

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	6.73	1.28	2.6	3.43	6.86
sd:	0.906	0.116	1.41	1790	10900

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	181.92	143.45	147.45
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	4.63	2.3	2.3

MAX_MEAN: 6.43 MAX_MED: 7.41 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Propoxur
 CHID: 21948 CASRN: 114-26-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F08
 M4ID: 30006267

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 5.39 1.06 4.48
 sd: 0.618 0.0817 3.69

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 5.65 1.08 3.85 2.35 16.8
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	177.73	131.46	135.15
PROB:	0	0.86	0.14
RMSE:	4.28	2.05	2.05

MAX_MEAN: 6.97 MAX_MED: 6.96 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde

CHID: 21969 CASRN: 121-33-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M24

M4ID: 30006467

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	6.42	0.429	1.9
sd:	0.622	0.181	0.981

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	6.64	0.454	1.77	2.34	9.83
sd:	0.669	0.171	0.897	0.106	26.6

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	197.03	146.86	149.64
PROB:	0	0.8	0.2
RMSE:	5.76	2.42	2.45

MAX_MEAN: 8.4 MAX_MED: 8.91 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-(Butan-2-yl)phenol
 CHID: 22331 CASRN: 89-72-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K15
 M4ID: 30006140

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	11	1.79	2.5
sd:	2.06	0.103	1.01

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	11	1.79	2.5	3.94	5.67
sd:	2.06	0.103	1.01	25300	87600

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	192.41	151.65	155.65
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	5.6	2.55	2.55

MAX_MEAN: 10.1 MAX_MED: 11.5 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Phenol red

CHID: 22408 CASRN: 143-74-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A06

M4ID: 30006389

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.89	-3.7	6.96
sd:	0.368	241	1680

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.89	-3.69	7.33	3.71	17.9
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	206.23	142.92	146.92
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	6.64	2.37	2.37

MAX_MEAN: 8.49 MAX_MED: 8.28 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: E-Cinnamic acid
 CHID: 22489 CASRN: 140-10-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B01
 M4ID: 30006754

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 4.46 -3.68 6.89
 sd: 0.289 372 2620

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 4.46 -3.69 6.92 3.2 11.7
 sd: 0.289 418 2930 31000 402000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	187.48	122.68	126.68
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	4.82	1.59	1.59

MAX_MEAN: 5.67 MAX_MED: 6.74 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Pentaerythritol tetranitrate

CHID: 23430 CASRN: 78-11-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F02

M4ID: 30006273

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	17.2	2.29	0.851
sd:	10.6	0.565	0.378

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	17.2	2.29	0.851	4.29	16.9
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	185.22	148.07	152.07
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	5.07	2.58	2.58

MAX_MEAN: 10.4 MAX_MED: 10.5 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Butylate
 CHID: 23936 CASRN: 2008-41-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B05
 M4ID: 30006366

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 7.99 1.38 0.3
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 9.69 1.92 0.3 2.4 16.1
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	177.57	135.44	139.05
PROB:	0	0.86	0.14
RMSE:	4.25	1.91	1.9

MAX_MEAN: 6.61 MAX_MED: 7.53 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dicamba
 CHID: 24018 CASRN: 1918-00-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A10
 M4ID: 30006385

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 7.75 -3.52 0.3
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 7.75 -3.52 0.3 4.09 4.37
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	215.87	151.85	155.85
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	7.76	2.5	2.5

MAX_MEAN: 10.6 MAX_MED: 10.9 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2,6-Dimethylphenol
 CHID: 24063 CASRN: 576-26-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A19
 M4ID: 30006760

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 10.2 -3.04 0.3
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 10.9 -2.46 0.3 2.32 17.9
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	229.32	175.54	177.65
PROB:	0	0.74	0.26
RMSE:	9.74	3.74	3.66

MAX_MEAN: 12.3 MAX_MED: 13.1 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Diphenamid
 CHID: 24072 CASRN: 957-51-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B12
 M4ID: 30006359

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 13.9 1.94 0.678
 sd: 4.36 0.408 0.169

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 13.9 1.94 0.678 4.18 5.29
 sd: 4.36 0.408 0.169 6580 18600

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	195.48	142.64	146.64
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	5.74	2.85	2.85

MAX_MEAN: 10.4 MAX_MED: 9.98 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Isopropalin

CHID: 24157 CASRN: 33820-53-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N12

M4ID: 30006455

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	9.89	0.507	1.24
sd:	0.677	0.156	0.449

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	9.89	0.507	1.24	3.68	6.52
sd:	0.677	0.156	0.449	8680	42400

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	218.08	149.08	153.08
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	8.16	2.65	2.65

MAX_MEAN: 10.4 MAX_MED: 9.99 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-[2-(2-Ethoxyethoxy)ethoxy]ethanol

CHID: 24368 CASRN: 112-50-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J02

M4ID: 30006177

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	9.87	2.04	3.05
sd:	3.62	0.156	2.17

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	9.87	2.04	3.05	4.29	6.17
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	155.94	124.68	128.68
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	3.36	1.64	1.64

MAX_MEAN: 7.8 MAX_MED: 8.6 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Butanal oxime

CHID: 24664 CASRN: 110-69-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A12

M4ID: 30006767

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	12	-3.69	6.92
sd:	0.68	386	2700

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	12	-3.62	6.83	3.81	4.9
sd:	0.68	197	1460	708	2290

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	247.49	174.85	178.85
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	13.11	3.94	3.94

MAX_MEAN: 15.5 MAX_MED: 14.9 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dihexyl phthalate

CHID: 25068 CASRN: 84-75-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H12

M4ID: 30006599

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	13.4	0.873	1.13
sd:	1.72	0.159	0.492

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	14.9	0.981	0.946	2.33	17.9
sd:	3.2	0.261	0.419	0.0173	13.3

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	227.34	161.42	163.89
PROB:	0	0.77	0.23
RMSE:	9.65	3.03	3.07

MAX_MEAN: 14 MAX_MED: 15.9 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Diisobutyl ketone
 CHID: 25080 CASRN: 108-83-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D12
 M4ID: 30006695

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 15.4 1.69 0.314
 sd: 7.31 1.35 0.163

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 15.4 1.69 0.314 4.29 4.24
 sd: 7.31 1.35 0.163 3160 6700

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	212.59	165.35	169.35
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	7.48	3.49	3.49

MAX_MEAN: 9.96 MAX_MED: 10.7 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 3-(Dimethylamino)propylamine

CHID: 25102 CASRN: 109-55-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K01

M4ID: 30006538

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	10.6	1.89	5.05
sd:	0.902	0.0306	1.68

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	10.6	1.89	5.05	3.29	8.06
sd:	0.902	0.0306	1.68	1270	10400

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	183.07	133.39	137.39
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	4.94	1.91	1.91

MAX_MEAN: 10.6 MAX_MED: 10.6 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-Ethylhexyl diphenyl phosphate
 CHID: 25300 CASRN: 1241-94-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G17
 M4ID: 30006618

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	13.3	0.624	1.52
sd:	0.749	0.0892	0.484

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	14.1	0.664	1.34	2.34	18
sd:	1.01	0.0952	0.428	0.019	9.72

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	230.98	153.93	155.25
PROB:	0	0.66	0.34
RMSE:	10.21	3.19	2.91

MAX_MEAN: 15.2 MAX_MED: 14 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Linoleic acid

CHID: 25505 CASRN: 60-33-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C08

M4ID: 30006723

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	7.24	-3.7	6.72
sd:	0.833	331	2230

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	7.99	-3.7	0.3	2.37	9.54
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	223.25	185.6	189.57
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	9.06	4.52	4.54

MAX_MEAN: 11.4 MAX_MED: 12.8 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-Ethoxyaniline

CHID: 25864 CASRN: 156-43-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A09

M4ID: 30006386

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	7.06	-3.7	0.805
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	8.11	-3.7	0.3	2.3	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	217.37	170.77	172.33
PROB:	0	0.68	0.32
RMSE:	8.13	3.57	3.32

MAX_MEAN: 11.3 MAX_MED: 12 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Triethylene glycol bis(2-ethylhexanoate)

CHID: 26564 CASRN: 94-28-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F03

M4ID: 30006272

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	11.9	1.18	1.1
sd:	1.5	0.161	0.388

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	15.6	1.49	0.826	2.34	17.9
sd:	6.55	0.524	0.32	0.0163	11.3

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	210.66	128.87	131.39
PROB:	0	0.78	0.22
RMSE:	7.37	1.72	1.7

MAX_MEAN: 11.9 MAX_MED: 12.8 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Bis(2-ethylhexyl) maleate

CHID: 27094 CASRN: 142-16-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L03

M4ID: 30006512

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	12.7	1.69	0.61
sd:	7.47	0.896	0.302

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	17.3	2.07	0.578	2.33	17.8
sd:	13.2	1.05	0.209	0.0208	15.4

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	196.11	140.31	142.91
PROB:	0	0.79	0.21
RMSE:	5.93	2.28	2.23

MAX_MEAN: 10.3 MAX_MED: 9.16 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Diisooctyl adipate

CHID: 27388 CASRN: 1330-86-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A13

M4ID: 30006766

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	8.32	-3.7	1.07
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	8.38	-3.7	0.989	2.4	11.6
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	224.11	149.28	153.16
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	8.84	2.49	2.51

MAX_MEAN: 11.3 MAX_MED: 11.4 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Diisodecyl hexanedioate
 CHID: 27924 CASRN: 27178-16-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B24
 M4ID: 30006347

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	7.68	0.105	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	7.86	0.219	0.3	3.87	4.71
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	205.94	177.27	181.27
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	7	4.17	4.17

MAX_MEAN: 8.81 MAX_MED: 7.15 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dodecylbenzene sulfonate triethanolamine(1:1)

CHID: 27932 CASRN: 27323-41-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C01

M4ID: 30006346

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	14.2	2.8	0.3
sd:	16.3	2.22	0.147

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	11.3	2.3	0.3	4.01	17.8
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	179.32	131.1	135.66
PROB:	0	0.91	0.09
RMSE:	4.59	2.03	2.07

MAX_MEAN: 9.99 MAX_MED: 8.73 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1-Hexadecanol

CHID: 27991 CASRN: 36653-82-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H08

M4ID: 30006219

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	11.7	1.83	1.88
sd:	2.57	0.144	0.635

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	11.7	1.83	1.88	4.28	3.75
sd:	2.57	0.144	0.635	1340	2590

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	142.08	107.25	111.25
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	4.97	2.09	2.09

MAX_MEAN: 10.6 MAX_MED: 10.6 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dinp branched

CHID: 28665 CASRN: 68515-48-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H03

M4ID: 30006608

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.29	0.478	0.884
sd:	2.49	0.956	1.06

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.29	0.481	0.881	4.3	16.8
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	135.43	98.42	102.42
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	4.26	1.75	1.75

MAX_MEAN: 7.21 MAX_MED: 7.21 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-(Phenylmethylene)-heptanal
 CHID: 29157 CASRN: 122-40-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J24
 M4ID: 30006539

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 8.87 2 8
 sd: 1.48 0.0319 4.19

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 15 2.05 8 2.32 8.83
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	166.54	143.53	147.26
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	3.94	2.29	2.28

MAX_MEAN: 9.12 MAX_MED: 8.57 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Methylionone
 CHID: 29214 CASRN: 1335-46-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P17
 M4ID: 30006402

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 8.9 2.02 4
 sd: 3.89 0.179 5.73

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 8.9 2.02 4 3.65 5.61
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	187.02	176.65	180.65
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	4.99	3.99	3.99

MAX_MEAN: 8.28 MAX_MED: 7.99 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Glyceryl stearate
 CHID: 29304 CASRN: 11099-07-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D02
 M4ID: 30006705

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 12 1 0.3
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 14.4 1.45 0.3 2.42 2.86
 sd: 29.5 7.14 1.01 0.325 10.9

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	159.44	131.98	134.97
PROB:	0	0.82	0.18
RMSE:	6.9	3.9	3.88

MAX_MEAN: 9.84 MAX_MED: 10.4 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Silica

CHID: 29677 CASRN: 7631-86-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J17

M4ID: 30006546

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	12.4	1.97	5.37
sd:	1.83	0.0439	2.87

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	12.4	1.97	5.37	4.27	2.67
sd:	1.84	0.0439	2.87	958	1360

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	186	151.88	155.88
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	5.43	2.65	2.65

MAX_MEAN: 12.1 MAX_MED: 12.3 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 8:2 Fluorotelomer alcohol

CHID: 29904 CASRN: 678-39-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E02

M4ID: 30006297

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	15.9	1.78	0.588
sd:	5.13	0.505	0.177

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	15.9	1.78	0.588	3.65	6.88
sd:	5.13	0.505	0.177	2770	14200

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	203.89	145.83	149.83
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	6.62	2.44	2.44

MAX_MEAN: 11.9 MAX_MED: 12.5 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dipentyl phthalate
 CHID: 31131 CASRN: 131-18-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N20
 M4ID: 30006063

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 7.39 0.941 2.08
 sd: 0.501 0.0945 0.728

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 9.88 1.02 1.84 3.49 0.327
 sd: 28.6 0.327 0.765 5.07 2.63

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	193.3	125.68	129.44
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	5.44	1.66	1.65

MAX_MEAN: 7.97 MAX_MED: 8.1 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Ethalfluralin

CHID: 32386 CASRN: 55283-68-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M22

M4ID: 30006085

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	14.6	0.993	1.23
sd:	1.04	0.0915	0.27

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	14.6	0.993	1.23	3.93	6.62
sd:	1.04	0.0915	0.27	21300	86200

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	226.86	126.26	130.26
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	9.6	1.67	1.67

MAX_MEAN: 14.2 MAX_MED: 15.1 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Triclopyr

CHID: 32497 CASRN: 55335-06-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E06

M4ID: 30006677

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	13.5	1.34	0.322
sd:	32.1	6.81	0.982

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	13.5	1.25	0.42	2.34	16.8
sd:	8.67	1.43	0.329	0.0256	14

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	208.41	156.67	159.15
PROB:	0	0.78	0.22
RMSE:	6.92	2.87	2.86

MAX_MEAN: 9.36 MAX_MED: 10.8 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Acibenzolar-S-methyl

CHID: 32519 CASRN: 135158-54-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A11

M4ID: 30006768

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	7.96	-3.7	7.27
sd:	0.658	303	2200

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	8.15	-3.63	7.91	2.3	17.9
sd:	0.7	318	2700	0.0503	677

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	173.14	131.56	134.2
PROB:	0	0.79	0.21
RMSE:	9.16	3.65	3.44

MAX_MEAN: 11.7 MAX_MED: 11.7 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Etridiazole

CHID: 32547 CASRN: 2593-15-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E08

M4ID: 30006291

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	16.7	1.79	0.808
sd:	6.65	0.498	0.311

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	16.7	1.79	0.808	4.21	4.14
sd:	6.65	0.498	0.311	1540	3360

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	208.31	151.8	155.8
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	7.19	2.65	2.65

MAX_MEAN: 12.5 MAX_MED: 12.7 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Fenitrothion
 CHID: 32613 CASRN: 122-14-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091018
 M4ID: 30006041

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	9.42	1.34	2.77
sd:	1.29	0.107	1.57

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	16.1	1.7	1.44	2.3	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	200.17	153.77	155.26
PROB:	0	0.68	0.32
RMSE:	6.58	2.76	2.55

MAX_MEAN: 12.6 MAX_MED: 13.4 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Pyridate
 CHID: 32639 CASRN: 55512-33-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E13
 M4ID: 30006286

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.62	1.18	2.91
sd:	1.37	0.278	2.52

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	7.12	1.3	2.21	2.31	16.4
sd:	2.7	0.355	2.27	0.0356	54.7

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	188.68	179.27	182.21
PROB:	0.01	0.81	0.19
RMSE:	5.14	4	4.05

MAX_MEAN: 5.46 MAX_MED: 8.87 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 0.99

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: N-Ethylperfluorooctanesulfonamide
 CHID: 32646 CASRN: 4151-50-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D04
 M4ID: 30006703

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 6.48 -3.7 6.63
 sd: 0.958 300 1990

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 13.7 0.945 0.3 2.3 11.9
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	218.92	192.04	197.56
PROB:	0	0.94	0.06
RMSE:	8.6	5	5.42

MAX_MEAN: 10.7 MAX_MED: 11.7 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-Amino-1,2,4-triazole
 CHID: 33058 CASRN: 584-13-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P24
 M4ID: 30006011

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	10.7	1.91	8
sd:	1.15	0.0261	5.78

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	14.2	1.95	5.75	2.35	10.1
sd:	26	0.296	11	0.105	44.9

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	190.04	153.05	156.48
PROB:	0	0.85	0.15
RMSE:	5.43	2.74	2.73

MAX_MEAN: 10.5 MAX_MED: 10.4 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Aldicarb sulfoxide
 CHID: 33161 CASRN: 1646-87-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E16
 M4ID: 30006667

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	16.4	1.62	0.3
sd:	7.3	1.31	0.176

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	16.4	1.62	0.3	4.29	3.6
sd:	7.29	1.31	0.176	658	1190

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	216.23	170.71	174.71
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	7.96	3.78	3.78

MAX_MEAN: 11.3 MAX_MED: 11.5 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Haloperidol

CHID: 34150 CASRN: 52-86-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A14

M4ID: 30006765

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	12.5	-3.7	7.09
sd:	0.986	285	2020

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	12.7	-3.45	8	2.28	18
sd:	0.993	67	715	0.0472	40.6

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	249.4	199.04	200.65
PROB:	0	0.69	0.31
RMSE:	13.53	6.8	5.85

MAX_MEAN: 17.4 MAX_MED: 18.6 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Buprofezin
 CHID: 34401 CASRN: 69327-76-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091003
 M4ID: 30006056

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 17.2 1.83 1.77
 sd: 9.47 0.347 1.03

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 17.2 1.83 1.77 3.52 6.06
 sd: 9.47 0.347 1.03 923 4620

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	213.46	192.45	196.45
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	8.4	5.08	5.08

MAX_MEAN: 15.3 MAX_MED: 16.3 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Cyhalofop-butyl

CHID: 34503 CASRN: 122008-85-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E21

M4ID: 30006662

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	8.69	-3.65	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	9.47	-2.86	0.3	2.32	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	226.57	195.38	198.93
PROB:	0	0.85	0.15
RMSE:	9.58	5.21	5.12

MAX_MEAN: 11.9 MAX_MED: 14.1 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Desmedipham

CHID: 34518 CASRN: 13684-56-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M14

M4ID: 30006477

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	12.6	1.75	3.47
sd:	2.29	0.0861	2.16

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	14.1	1.79	2.94	2.35	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	204.8	169.94	173.89
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	6.9	3.38	3.37

MAX_MEAN: 11.4 MAX_MED: 13.3 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Isazofos

CHID: 34676 CASRN: 42509-80-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I18

M4ID: 30006185

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	17.5	2.01	0.961
sd:	10.1	0.542	0.384

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	17.5	2.01	0.961	3.38	11.4
sd:	10.1	0.542	0.385	70400	709000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	194	141.8	145.8
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	5.88	2.09	2.09

MAX_MEAN: 11.5 MAX_MED: 11.7 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Fluazifop-P-butyl
 CHID: 34855 CASRN: 79241-46-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F09
 M4ID: 30006266

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	6.45	1.24	3.35
sd:	0.779	0.101	2.48

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	14.5	1.85	1.2	2.3	17.9
sd:	9.49	0.496	0.448	0.0235	464

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	186.24	145.99	147.71
PROB:	0	0.7	0.3
RMSE:	5.1	2.45	2.33

MAX_MEAN: 9.24 MAX_MED: 11.2 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Chloridazon
 CHID: 34872 CASRN: 1698-60-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E04
 M4ID: 30006295

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 15.2 2.14 0.705
 sd: 7.08 0.545 0.218

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 15.2 2.14 0.705 4.3 18
 sd: NA NA NA NA NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	190.82	150.4	154.4
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	5.49	2.6	2.6

MAX_MEAN: 10.5 MAX_MED: 10 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Pyrimethanil

CHID: 34877 CASRN: 53112-28-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P04

M4ID: 30006031

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	17.8	1.75	4.74
sd:	1.85	0.0474	2.25

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	17.8	1.75	4.74	4.29	17.4
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	227.59	180.64	184.64
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	10.22	4.37	4.37

MAX_MEAN: 20.2 MAX_MED: 20.8 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Thymo1
 CHID: 34972 CASRN: 89-83-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E13
 M4ID: 30006670

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 8.57 1.24 2.57
 sd: 0.712 0.0897 1.29

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 8.99 1.27 2.23 2.35 17.8
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	195.6	135.95	139.6
PROB:	0	0.86	0.14
RMSE:	5.9	2	1.98

MAX_MEAN: 10.7 MAX_MED: 9.34 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Chlorpyrifos oxon
 CHID: 38666 CASRN: 5598-15-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B10
 M4ID: 30006361

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 8.57 0.0187 1.13
 sd: 0.912 0.319 0.819

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 8.57 0.0187 1.13 4.1 5.91
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	215.93	170.32	174.32
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	7.92	3.49	3.49

MAX_MEAN: 10.6 MAX_MED: 11.3 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Butyl benzoate

CHID: 40694 CASRN: 136-60-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B15

M4ID: 30006356

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	10.7	1.82	1.38
sd:	3.71	0.264	0.537

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	10.7	1.82	1.38	3.86	2.11
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	180.37	129.44	133.44
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	4.68	1.73	1.73

MAX_MEAN: 8.94 MAX_MED: 8.6 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-Cyclohexylcyclohexanone
 CHID: 40721 CASRN: 92-68-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F12
 M4ID: 30006647

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 16.6 1.5 0.73
 sd: 10.4 0.863 0.51

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 16.6 1.5 0.73 4.29 12.1
 sd: NA NA NA NA NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	218.46	172.66	176.66
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	8.52	3.96	3.96

MAX_MEAN: 13 MAX_MED: 12.2 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-tert-Butyl-4-methoxyphenol
 CHID: 40788 CASRN: 121-00-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B02
 M4ID: 30006369

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 16.4 1.59 0.3
 sd: 6.45 1.16 0.165

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 16.4 1.59 0.3 4.3 4.13
 sd: 6.48 1.16 0.164 2140 4350

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	217.51	164.32	168.32
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	8.07	3.65	3.65

MAX_MEAN: 10.8 MAX_MED: 12.7 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Pyridoxine hydrochloride
 CHID: 40792 CASRN: 58-56-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078009
 M4ID: 30006434

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 9.97 1.78 6.96
 sd: 2.08 0.0918 5.45

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 15.7 1.89 4.28 2.32 10.7
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	211.15	193.57	197.06
PROB:	0	0.85	0.15
RMSE:	7.51	5.19	5.14

MAX_MEAN: 11.9 MAX_MED: 11.7 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: (4Z)-4-Decenal

CHID: 41514 CASRN: 21662-09-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K09

M4ID: 30006530

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	15	1.75	4.51
sd:	2.55	0.0603	3.52

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	15	1.75	4.51	4.19	18
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	219.65	176.09	180.09
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	9.01	3.9	3.9

MAX_MEAN: 16.3 MAX_MED: 14.3 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Isobornyl propanoate
 CHID: 42062 CASRN: 2756-56-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L11
 M4ID: 30006120

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 16.4 2 4.11
 sd: 2.13 0.0504 1.78

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 16.4 2 4.11 3.58 5.92
 sd: 2.13 0.0504 1.78 2230 10400

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	197.75	158.26	162.26
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	6.45	2.9	2.9

MAX_MEAN: 15.5 MAX_MED: 15.7 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: N-Methyldioctylamine

CHID: 42209 CASRN: 4455-26-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091010

M4ID: 30006049

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.75	1.82	8
sd:	1.95	0.121	10.1

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	6.29	1.82	8	4.3	0.472
sd:	18.9	0.147	11.2	11.3	7.19

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	201.5	197.33	201.35
PROB:	0.1	0.79	0.11
RMSE:	9.51	8.47	8.47

MAX_MEAN: 17.5 MAX_MED: 7.02 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 0.9

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Clove leaf oil

CHID: 44175 CASRN: 8000-34-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C09

M4ID: 30006722

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	8.42	1.01	8
sd:	0.474	0.0255	8.91

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	14.6	1.07	3.38	2.22	0.43
sd:	30.6	0.126	2.1	4.25	1.12

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	202.81	135.61	136.42
PROB:	0	0.6	0.4
RMSE:	6.41	2	1.92

MAX_MEAN: 9.08 MAX_MED: 9.37 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1-(6-tert-Butyl-1,1-dimethyl-2,3-dihydro-1H-im

CHID: 44536 CASRN: 13171-00-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M21

M4ID: 30006086

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	6.54	1.5	1.64
sd:	1.02	0.13	0.574

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	8.76	1.71	1.27	2.34	15
sd:	5.6	0.489	0.645	0.0362	16.6

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	167.62	106.52	109.73
PROB:	0	0.83	0.17
RMSE:	3.7	1.19	1.18

MAX_MEAN: 6.38 MAX_MED: 7.05 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Triallyl trimellitate

CHID: 44901 CASRN: 2694-54-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H11

M4ID: 30006216

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	7.01	1.36	2.11
sd:	1.2	0.201	1.28

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	10	1.65	1.39	2.33	17
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	190.9	158.39	161.91
PROB:	0	0.85	0.15
RMSE:	5.23	3.07	3.07

MAX_MEAN: 8.49 MAX_MED: 7.73 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Besonprodil

CHID: 47270 CASRN: 253450-09-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E02

M4ID: 30006681

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.52	-3.7	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	7.28	0.246	0.3	2.32	17.9
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	186.02	143.89	147.81
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	4.8	2.17	2.2

MAX_MEAN: 6.73 MAX_MED: 7.11 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: SSR150106
 CHID: 47362 CASRN: NOCAS_47362
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E15
 M4ID: 30006668

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 12.1 2.8 0.3
 sd: 24.6 4.9 0.24

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 9.75 2.3 0.309 3.71 5.81
 sd: 14.3 3.62 0.239 1420 5900

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	194.17	175.81	179.91
PROB:	0	0.89	0.11
RMSE:	9.4	7.8	7.84

MAX_MEAN: 24.6 MAX_MED: 26.2 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Igepal CO-890

CHID: 47708 CASRN: NOCAS_47708

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J08

M4ID: 30006555

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	17.7	2.34	0.544
sd:	12.7	1.03	0.177

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	17.4	2.3	0.554	2.96	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	194.09	151.39	155.42
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	5.68	2.66	2.66

MAX_MEAN: 10.7 MAX_MED: 9.42 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: PharmaGSID_48507

CHID: 48507 CASRN: NOCAS_48507

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I13

M4ID: 30006190

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	13.9	1.91	3.21
sd:	2.61	0.075	1.35

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	13.9	1.91	3.21	4.29	3.2
sd:	2.61	0.075	1.35	862	1440

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	200.12	164.2	168.2
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	6.39	3.12	3.12

MAX_MEAN: 13 MAX_MED: 14.3 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: HMR1171 trifluoroacetate (1:1)

CHID: 48522 CASRN: NOCAS_48522

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M08

M4ID: 30006483

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	9.44	1.69	2.08
sd:	2.36	0.156	1.23

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	16.4	1.98	1.57	2.34	6.97
sd:	20.6	0.645	0.914	0.105	24.4

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	191.37	156.82	159.88
PROB:	0	0.82	0.18
RMSE:	5.52	2.75	2.73

MAX_MEAN: 9.01 MAX_MED: 7.47 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2,4-D Butyl ester

CHID: 20443 CASRN: 94-80-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H13

M4ID: 30006598

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	13.8	1.62	1.62
sd:	2.74	0.172	0.497

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	19	1.84	1.39	2.34	13.2
sd:	10.6	0.378	0.459	0.0364	14.7

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	207.73	153.63	156.27
PROB:	0	0.79	0.21
RMSE:	7.26	2.61	2.56

MAX_MEAN: 12.5 MAX_MED: 12.4 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 15 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 6-Methylquinoline

CHID: 20887 CASRN: 91-62-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C06

M4ID: 30006725

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	15	1.38	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	19	1.95	0.3	2.34	17.9
sd:	23.9	3.63	0.305	0.0335	18.5

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	219.05	171.56	174.73
PROB:	0	0.83	0.17
RMSE:	8.35	4.33	4.32

MAX_MEAN: 11.5 MAX_MED: 10.1 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 15 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 3,4-Dimethylphenol
 CHID: 24062 CASRN: 95-65-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E15
 M4ID: 30006284

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	13.6	1.67	1.18
sd:	3.94	0.267	0.367

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	19.2	1.93	1.06	2.34	13.7
sd:	14	0.556	0.323	0.0513	19.8

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	201.71	143.95	147.11
PROB:	0	0.83	0.17
RMSE:	6.74	2.31	2.23

MAX_MEAN: 13.3 MAX_MED: 14 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 15 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Diisononyl cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylate

CHID: 47395 CASRN: 166412-78-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B03

M4ID: 30006368

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	15.2	1.87	0.3
sd:	9.35	1.61	0.115

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	18.2	2.3	0.3	2.76	17.7
sd:	14	1.92	0.111	97.5	3500

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	206.74	152.12	155.58
PROB:	0	0.85	0.15
RMSE:	7.14	2.95	2.9

MAX_MEAN: 15 MAX_MED: 14.4 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 15 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2,3,6-Trimethylphenol

CHID: 22187 CASRN: 2416-94-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G11

M4ID: 30006624

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	12	1.76	4.12
sd:	1	0.0315	1.73

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	26.1	2.04	1.84	2.38	2.71
sd:	11.4	0.155	0.55	0.0881	3.63

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	198.97	127.83	130.9
PROB:	0	0.82	0.18
RMSE:	6.9	2.36	2.31

MAX_MEAN: 15.1 MAX_MED: 12.1 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 16 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 3,7-Dimethyl-3-octanol

CHID: 29110 CASRN: 78-69-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F13

M4ID: 30006646

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	17.3	1.89	3.1
sd:	2.69	0.0646	1.3

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	23.9	1.99	2.65	2.33	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	204.22	150.3	153.29
PROB:	0	0.82	0.18
RMSE:	7.46	2.46	2.41

MAX_MEAN: 16 MAX_MED: 15.9 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 16 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Tepra loxydim
 CHID: 34252 CASRN: 149979-41-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C09
 M4ID: 30006338

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 16.4 2.8 0.348
 sd: 46.8 5.97 0.332

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 62 2.21 3.71 2.88 18
 sd: 17.4 0.0842 0.964 4290 113000

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	210.32	192.83	193.9
PROB:	0	0.63	0.37
RMSE:	12.79	10.69	8.52

MAX_MEAN: 31.1 MAX_MED: 41.3 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 16 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Pentyl butyrate

CHID: 41604 CASRN: 540-18-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A04

M4ID: 30006775

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	25.1	0.749	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	14	-3.7	5.94	2.98	16.8
sd:	1.53	250	1480	6840	154000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	262.18	224.48	225.04
PROB:	0	0.57	0.43
RMSE:	17.28	9.01	8.21

MAX_MEAN: 21.5 MAX_MED: 19.2 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 18 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-Naphthylamine
 CHID: 20921 CASRN: 91-59-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G06
 M4ID: 30006629

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 21.6 1.24 0.953
 sd: 2.53 0.154 0.22

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 21.6 1.24 0.953 3.6 6.2
 sd: 2.53 0.154 0.22 924 4390

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	242.67	147.19	151.19
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	12.51	2.72	2.72

MAX_MEAN: 20.3 MAX_MED: 20.8 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Acenaphthylene

CHID: 23845 CASRN: 208-96-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A06

M4ID: 30006773

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	23.2	0.519	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	19.8	-0.286	0.3	3.17	9.26
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	254.25	189.65	193.41
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	14.66	5.23	5.09

MAX_MEAN: 19.2 MAX_MED: 19.9 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Clodinafop-propargyl
 CHID: 32354 CASRN: 105512-06-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B04
 M4ID: 30006367

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 21.2 1.53 0.504
 sd: 5.44 0.483 0.129

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 21.2 1.53 0.504 4.3 7.06
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	230.94	154.04	158.04
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	10.09	3.49	3.49

MAX_MEAN: 15.4 MAX_MED: 16.3 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dibutyl nonanedioate
 CHID: 44815 CASRN: 2917-73-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A02
 M4ID: 30006393

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 22.1 0.642 0.3
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 20 0.142 0.3 2.44 7.54
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	247.95	169.7	172.54
PROB:	0	0.8	0.2
RMSE:	13.19	3.85	3.76

MAX_MEAN: 18 MAX_MED: 17.6 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Zamifenacin

CHID: 47257 CASRN: 127308-82-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B24

M4ID: 30006731

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	21.5	1.37	0.33
sd:	6.35	0.827	0.116

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	21.5	1.3	0.416	2.36	10.6
sd:	4.94	0.507	0.124	0.0766	13.3

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	237.08	175.46	177.36
PROB:	0	0.72	0.28
RMSE:	11.15	4.61	4.65

MAX_MEAN: 16.8 MAX_MED: 17 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: (E)-Anethole
 CHID: 20087 CASRN: 4180-23-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D05
 M4ID: 30006702

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 28.2 2.03 1.28
 sd: 7.95 0.211 0.462

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 28.2 2.03 1.28 2.92 18
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	223.29	170.54	174.54
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	9.65	3.46	3.46

MAX_MEAN: 20.5 MAX_MED: 19.7 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-Chloro-1,2-diaminobenzene

CHID: 20283 CASRN: 95-83-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M06

M4ID: 30006101

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	17.9	1.77	2.49
sd:	3.03	0.0874	1.06

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	32.3	2.02	1.88	2.32	17.7
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	222.93	172.82	175.81
PROB:	0	0.82	0.18
RMSE:	9.76	3.82	3.81

MAX_MEAN: 19.1 MAX_MED: 16.5 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Diethylene glycol
 CHID: 20462 CASRN: 111-46-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F18
 M4ID: 30006641

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 21.8 1.49 1.11
 sd: 4.03 0.211 0.302

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 26.6 1.67 0.994 2.35 17.6
 sd: 11.3 0.42 0.281 0.0227 15.8

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	236.92	163.34	166.26
PROB:	0	0.81	0.19
RMSE:	11.57	3.23	3.2

MAX_MEAN: 20.7 MAX_MED: 20.6 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-Phenylphenol
 CHID: 21151 CASRN: 90-43-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N03
 M4ID: 30006080

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 19.8 1.73 2.91
 sd: 2.03 0.0569 1.55

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 27.9 1.86 2.22 2.33 17
 sd: 31.8 0.468 1.46 0.0301 44

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	229.73	168.15	169.6
PROB:	0	0.67	0.33
RMSE:	10.69	3.36	3.21

MAX_MEAN: 19.9 MAX_MED: 20.7 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Octanoic acid
 CHID: 21645 CASRN: 124-07-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P07
 M4ID: 30006412

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	24.9	1.98	1.99
sd:	6.81	0.151	0.769

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	28.7	2.03	1.98	2.37	14.5
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	220.84	174.74	178.54
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	9.3	3.81	3.8

MAX_MEAN: 20.2 MAX_MED: 19.4 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Disulfoton

CHID: 22018 CASRN: 298-04-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B23

M4ID: 30006348

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	31.3	1.73	0.531
sd:	9.88	0.558	0.151

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	31.3	1.73	0.532	3.27	2.67
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	245.83	168.45	172.44
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	13.35	3.4	3.4

MAX_MEAN: 21.1 MAX_MED: 20.7 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Warfarin
 CHID: 23742 CASRN: 81-81-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B07
 M4ID: 30006748

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 32.3 2.23 0.577
 sd: 17.1 0.778 0.2

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 32.3 2.23 0.577 3.99 4.58
 sd: 17.1 0.778 0.2 8320 16800

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	230.76	174.25	178.25
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	10.75	4.06	4.06

MAX_MEAN: 19.3 MAX_MED: 15.8 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Terbaci1

CHID: 24317 CASRN: 5902-51-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K05

M4ID: 30006534

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	30.1	2.08	1.34
sd:	6.13	0.136	0.209

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	30.1	2.08	1.34	4.3	11.8
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	219.83	127.05	131.05
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	9.64	2.03	2.03

MAX_MEAN: 21.5 MAX_MED: 21.3 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 3-(Methylthio)propanal
 CHID: 27528 CASRN: 3268-49-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A20
 M4ID: 30006375

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 32.8 2.33 0.306
 sd: 14 1.16 0.115

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 32.8 2.3 0.314 3.96 5.21
 sd: 15.2 1.2 0.112 2150 6740

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	240.53	181.45	185.46
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	12.09	4.46	4.45

MAX_MEAN: 20.2 MAX_MED: 17.1 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2'-Acetonaphthone

CHID: 41389 CASRN: 93-08-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G22

M4ID: 30006613

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	35.1	2.16	0.791
sd:	21.3	0.632	0.25

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	35.1	2.16	0.791	3.98	6.92
sd:	21.3	0.632	0.25	68000	279000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	231	179.73	183.73
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	11.01	4.07	4.07

MAX_MEAN: 21.6 MAX_MED: 21.3 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-Dodecylmorpholine
 CHID: 42171 CASRN: 1541-81-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A23
 M4ID: 30006372

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 22.3 1.15 0.3
 sd: 60.9 8.5 1.06

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 23.1 1.18 0.3 3.53 0.972
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	244.27	197.92	201.73
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	12.96	5.48	5.45

MAX_MEAN: 17.7 MAX_MED: 19.6 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: CI-1044
 CHID: 47291 CASRN: NOCAS_47291
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G08
 M4ID: 30006627

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	22.4	2.04	1.27
sd:	6.99	0.213	0.403

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	22.4	2.04	1.27	3.86	5.12
sd:	6.99	0.213	0.403	968	3180

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	207.03	155.85	159.85
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	7.44	2.8	2.8

MAX_MEAN: 16.1 MAX_MED: 17.7 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Benzyloctyl adipate
 CHID: 47528 CASRN: 58394-64-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B14
 M4ID: 30006357

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 23.8 1.84 0.415
 sd: 19.3 1.76 0.269

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 23.8 1.84 0.415 3.48 9.57
 sd: 19.3 1.75 0.268 34500 279000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	229.55	179.88	183.88
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	10.07	4.15	4.15

MAX_MEAN: 15.6 MAX_MED: 14.4 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Azinphos-methyl

CHID: 20122 CASRN: 86-50-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B19

M4ID: 30006736

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.21	-3.7	6.5
sd:	0.821	320	2080

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	7.33	-3.7	0.3	1.89	17
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	206.5	190.6	168.79
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	6.7	5.36	3.41

MAX_MEAN: 9.74 MAX_MED: 9.75 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Eugenol
 CHID: 20617 CASRN: 97-53-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K17
 M4ID: 30006522

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 6.25 1.27 8
 sd: 0.884 0.141 28.3

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 7.81 1.3 7.72 2.17 3.95
 sd: 2.08 0.0633 42.9 0.141 3.45

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	186.12	161.83	161
PROB:	0	0.4	0.6
RMSE:	4.95	3.01	2.72

MAX_MEAN: 7.54 MAX_MED: 8.18 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Finasteride

CHID: 20625 CASRN: 98319-26-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D22

M4ID: 30006301

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.997	2.8	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4	-3.7	7.74	1.7	18
sd:	0.535	645	5010	0.0303	89.2

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	180.9	186.82	161.1
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	4.52	4.53	3.18

MAX_MEAN: 5.96 MAX_MED: 5.02 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone
CHID: 20856 CASRN: 872-50-4
SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A23
M4ID: 30006756

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	7.41	-3.68	7.5
sd:	0.53	323	2470

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	7.85	-3.69	6.85	2.29	18
sd:	0.465	170	1180	0.0163	19.8

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	215.42	157.51	150.02
PROB:	0	0.02	0.98
RMSE:	7.7	2.82	2.42

MAX_MEAN: 10.1 MAX_MED: 9.68 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Nitrofen

CHID: 20970 CASRN: 1836-75-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N22

M4ID: 30006061

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.4	0.237	1.91
sd:	0.596	0.229	0.83

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	12.3	0.79	1.26	1.82	0.922
sd:	22.1	0.858	0.681	1.6	1.14

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	186.68	141.56	135.55
PROB:	0	0.05	0.95
RMSE:	4.94	2.12	1.82

MAX_MEAN: 7.44 MAX_MED: 7.51 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Disulfiram
 CHID: 21322 CASRN: 97-77-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G21
 M4ID: 30006614

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 4.01 2.77 0.3
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 7.25 0.994 8 1.94 14.6
 sd: 2.49 0.0985 23.6 0.0631 18.5

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	189.92	195	188.66
PROB:	0.34	0.03	0.64
RMSE:	5.51	5.34	4.5

MAX_MEAN: 5.89 MAX_MED: 9.39 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 0.66

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: p-Cresol

CHID: 21869 CASRN: 106-44-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A07

M4ID: 30006772

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	9.94	-3.58	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	11.2	-2.41	0.3	2.3	9.77
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	233.86	180.49	180.01
PROB:	0	0.44	0.56
RMSE:	10.6	4.2	3.85

MAX_MEAN: 13.4 MAX_MED: 13.6 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Resmethrin

CHID: 22253 CASRN: 10453-86-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H03

M4ID: 30006224

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	6.6	0.94	8
sd:	0.937	0.239	29.9

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	8.49	0.981	2.94	2.03	18
sd:	1.28	0.113	2.23	0.0374	19.8

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	193.6	168.04	156.37
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	5.61	3.41	2.61

MAX_MEAN: 9.12 MAX_MED: 9.11 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Amitraz
 CHID: 23871 CASRN: 33089-61-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D08
 M4ID: 30006315

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	7.55	0.69	3.44
sd:	0.938	0.12	3.01

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	16.4	1.04	1.65	1.91	1.48
sd:	6.97	0.222	0.775	0.232	0.608

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	205.88	166.92	157.05
PROB:	0	0.01	0.99
RMSE:	6.86	3.24	2.62

MAX_MEAN: 11.3 MAX_MED: 11.5 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Carboxin

CHID: 23951 CASRN: 5234-68-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C16

M4ID: 30006331

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	9.9	0.988	8
sd:	0.733	0.0427	17.6

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	11	0.996	3.88	2.33	4.45
sd:	1.13	0.0543	4.06	0.0506	5.16

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	214.69	160.14	155.72
PROB:	0	0.1	0.9
RMSE:	7.79	3.01	2.7

MAX_MEAN: 12.6 MAX_MED: 13.4 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Fenamiphos
 CHID: 24102 CASRN: 22224-92-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C08
 M4ID: 30006339

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 7.25 -0.539 0.3
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 12.8 1.07 0.479 2.04 3.95
 sd: 4.28 0.636 0.161 0.0621 1.38

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	197.45	158.39	137.33
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	5.82	2.89	2.23

MAX_MEAN: 8.87 MAX_MED: 8.57 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-Tert-Butyl-5-methylphenol
 CHID: 26529 CASRN: 88-60-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C05
 M4ID: 30006342

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 7.99 1.27 4.3
 sd: 0.471 0.0433 2.21

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 8.45 1.29 3.71 2.29 17.8
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	186.64	122.31	116.75
PROB:	0	0.06	0.94
RMSE:	5.11	1.76	1.42

MAX_MEAN: 9.34 MAX_MED: 8.75 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol
 CHID: 26602 CASRN: 96-76-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C24
 M4ID: 30006707

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.95e-07 2.79 2.12
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 14.2 0.479 0.3 1.74 13.2
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	237.88	243.88	232.92
PROB:	0.08	0	0.92
RMSE:	11.81	11.81	10.32

MAX_MEAN: 12.4 MAX_MED: 12.6 BMAD: 2.23
 COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 0.92
 FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Glyceryl monooleate

CHID: 27875 CASRN: 25496-72-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P22

M4ID: 30006013

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.81	0.672	1.78
sd:	0.79	0.199	1.05

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	7.38	0.899	1.11	2.27	9.3
sd:	1.61	0.283	0.603	0.0769	24.5

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	187.9	151.43	148.24
PROB:	0	0.17	0.83
RMSE:	5.02	2.71	2.42

MAX_MEAN: 8.8 MAX_MED: 7.73 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-Methylpent-3-en-2-one

CHID: 29170 CASRN: 141-79-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A03

M4ID: 30006776

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	7.9	-3.7	6.19
sd:	0.627	276	1710

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	8.32	-3.7	1.28	2.26	10.7
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	225.86	175.72	170.22
PROB:	0	0.06	0.94
RMSE:	9.37	4.15	3.7

MAX_MEAN: 12.6 MAX_MED: 10.2 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Fenofibrate

CHID: 29874 CASRN: 49562-28-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H05

M4ID: 30006606

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	7.02	0.248	2.32
sd:	0.495	0.143	0.948

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	14.8	0.82	0.91	1.87	1.17
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	199.89	144.07	137.95
PROB:	0	0.04	0.96
RMSE:	6.08	2.59	1.97

MAX_MEAN: 9.68 MAX_MED: 8.44 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Perfluorononanoic acid
 CHID: 31863 CASRN: 375-95-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C02
 M4ID: 30006345

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.98	-3.7	7.09
sd:	0.582	274	1940

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.2	-3.64	8	1.97	18
sd:	0.606	426	3610	0.0399	13.8

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	202.75	178.31	177.92
PROB:	0	0.45	0.55
RMSE:	6.36	5.22	4.23

MAX_MEAN: 8.34 MAX_MED: 8.64 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Icaridin

CHID: 34227 CASRN: 119515-38-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A07

M4ID: 30006388

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	6.15	-3.7	6.68
sd:	0.647	257	1720

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	6.73	-3.7	5.46	2.17	4.36
sd:	0.655	89.3	487	0.114	2.7

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	210.42	168.48	163.54
PROB:	0	0.08	0.92
RMSE:	7.23	3.33	2.91

MAX_MEAN: 8.65 MAX_MED: 8.51 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Codlelure
 CHID: 35288 CASRN: 33956-49-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I01
 M4ID: 30006586

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 3.73 0.994 8
 sd: 1.03 0.0922 11.6

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 6.22 1.04 8 1.95 17.8
 sd: 0.824 0.0635 9.38 0.0279 10.1

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	178.64	174.09	156.2
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	4.51	4.49	3.23

MAX_MEAN: 6.52 MAX_MED: 6.71 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dibutyl decanedioate
 CHID: 41847 CASRN: 109-43-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E03
 M4ID: 30006680

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	6.19	1.13	1.3
sd:	1.37	0.288	0.825

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	10.8	1.72	0.777	2.28	10.3
sd:	8.37	0.916	0.498	0.0904	48.5

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	179.2	148.04	147.57
PROB:	0	0.44	0.56
RMSE:	4.38	2.49	2.34

MAX_MEAN: 7.03 MAX_MED: 7.47 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: C.I. Disperse Orange 37

CHID: 44538 CASRN: 13301-61-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D23

M4ID: 30006300

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.39	-0.456	1.3
sd:	0.904	0.669	1.16

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	13.6	1.21	0.509	1.89	17.8
sd:	8.38	1.08	0.268	0.015	15.4

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	186.54	172.86	144.57
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	4.95	3.84	2.17

MAX_MEAN: 8.35 MAX_MED: 8.79 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Darbufelone mesylate

CHID: 47246 CASRN: 139340-56-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E01

M4ID: 30006298

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	8.59	1.32	2.08
sd:	1.17	0.108	0.759

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	14.3	1.66	1.26	2.26	6.63
sd:	4.08	0.227	0.331	0.0422	5.34

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	190.16	140.08	120.64
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	5.5	2.14	1.44

MAX_MEAN: 10.6 MAX_MED: 10.8 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: GW473178E methyl benzene sulphonate

CHID: 47313 CASRN: 263553-33-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C13

M4ID: 30006334

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.81	1.26	3.82
sd:	0.706	0.077	4.62

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	10.5	1.66	1.13	2.3	17.8
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	176.55	136.6	132.57
PROB:	0	0.12	0.88
RMSE:	4.26	2.04	1.79

MAX_MEAN: 7.94 MAX_MED: 8 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: SR125047
 CHID: 47342 CASRN: NOCAS_47342
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F01
 M4ID: 30006658

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.02	1.1	3.63
sd:	0.672	0.107	2.47

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	10.7	1.63	1.22	2.01	18
sd:	11.3	0.845	0.759	0.0181	17.6

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	167.9	143.93	123.88
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	3.8	2.64	1.48

MAX_MEAN: 7.46 MAX_MED: 8.33 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Grinstad Soft-N-Safe
 CHID: 47394 CASRN: NOCAS_47394
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078008
 M4ID: 30006435

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 7.59 0.748 2.99
 sd: 0.958 0.147 1.75

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 9.12 0.858 2.21 2.18 3.05
 sd: 2.08 0.177 1.17 0.146 2.06

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	204.81	166.91	166.14
PROB:	0	0.4	0.6
RMSE:	6.91	3.42	3.25

MAX_MEAN: 10.6 MAX_MED: 8.28 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Acid Yellow 11

CHID: 47451 CASRN: 6359-82-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A13

M4ID: 30006382

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	6.72	-3.7	1.46
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	8	-3.7	0.3	2.22	4.97
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	218.74	187.68	187.35
PROB:	0	0.46	0.54
RMSE:	8.48	4.66	4.3

MAX_MEAN: 11.6 MAX_MED: 10.3 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Adipic acid, polypropyleneglycol, laurate

CHID: 47527 CASRN: 66456-53-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L08

M4ID: 30006507

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	7.83	1.09	1.41
sd:	1.35	0.177	0.66

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	9.99	1.33	1.01	2.29	17
sd:	3.55	0.399	0.454	0.0185	20.6

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	155.27	118.72	116.25
PROB:	0	0.23	0.77
RMSE:	4.91	2.29	2.11

MAX_MEAN: 8.76 MAX_MED: 8.76 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4,4'-Sulfonylbis[2-(prop-2-en-1-yl)phenol]

CHID: 47598 CASRN: 41481-66-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I05

M4ID: 30006198

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	9.37e-08	2.47	7.93
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	14.7	1.31	8	1.91	18
sd:	2.39	0.0432	17.8	0.0184	10.5

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	216.98	222.98	202.12
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	8.42	8.42	6.19

MAX_MEAN: 14.4 MAX_MED: 15.5 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2,4,6-Trichlorophenol
 CHID: 21386 CASRN: 88-06-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F06
 M4ID: 30006653

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	6.56	-0.722	1.34
sd:	1.23	0.557	1.48

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	18.2	0.793	0.432	1.85	4.06
sd:	11.8	1.36	0.305	0.102	2.13

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	214.1	197.26	175.99
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	7.81	5.6	3.73

MAX_MEAN: 12.8 MAX_MED: 12.5 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 29 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Flavone

CHID: 22048 CASRN: 525-82-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G11

M4ID: 30006240 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	16.7	1.46	2.5
sd:	2.89	0.139	0.892

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	29.4	1.8	1.62	2.28	17.7
sd:	13.8	0.282	0.525	0.011	11.9

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	241.91	202.79	194.48
PROB:	0	0.02	0.98
RMSE:	18.09	12.81	14.03

MAX_MEAN: 32.9 MAX_MED: 20.6 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 29 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Mifepristone
 CHID: 23322 CASRN: 84371-65-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B01
 M4ID: 30006370

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	10.4	-2.25	0.536
sd:	1.18	0.772	0.267

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	25.4	0.348	0.302	1.82	1.79
sd:	11.6	1.3	0.108	0.119	0.641

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	235.48	191.39	164.79
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	11.01	5.19	3.03

MAX_MEAN: 17 MAX_MED: 18.2 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 29 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Carbosulfan
 CHID: 23950 CASRN: 55285-14-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A15
 M4ID: 30006380

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	16.8	0.525	1.05
sd:	1.55	0.157	0.349

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	27.6	1.13	0.657	2.28	2.2
sd:	9.9	0.494	0.193	0.0953	0.866

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	244.38	174.23	163.77
PROB:	0	0.01	0.99
RMSE:	12.71	3.76	3.14

MAX_MEAN: 19.8 MAX_MED: 19.5 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 29 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8; 12

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Acetyl tributyl citrate

CHID: 26446 CASRN: 77-90-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H16

M4ID: 30006595

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	9.2	0.254	1.71
sd:	0.996	0.231	0.792

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	19.7	0.868	1.04	1.95	1.06
sd:	12.7	0.49	0.463	0.456	0.591

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	221.08	176.99	173.27
PROB:	0	0.13	0.87
RMSE:	8.68	4.02	3.61

MAX_MEAN: 12.8 MAX_MED: 14.2 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 29 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 7-(Dimethylamino)-4-methylcoumarin
 CHID: 41422 CASRN: 87-01-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D20
 M4ID: 30006687

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	14.4	0.343	0.632
sd:	2.92	0.362	0.512

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	22.5	1.07	0.535	2.19	3.05
sd:	6.97	0.533	0.203	0.0725	1.03

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	234.24	183.35	168.66
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	10.74	4.39	3.39

MAX_MEAN: 16.5 MAX_MED: 16.7 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 29 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Diphenylmercury(II)
 CHID: 42130 CASRN: 587-85-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E12
 M4ID: 30006671

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 13.6 2.42 0.3
 sd: 7.82 1.24 0.13

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 18.4 1.04 1.3 1.74 3.55
 sd: 10.1 0.388 1.11 0.104 1.18

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	209.1	204.51	181
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	7.26	6.41	4.16

MAX_MEAN: 13.5 MAX_MED: 15.2 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 29 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Melengestrol acetate

CHID: 48184 CASRN: 2919-66-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C15

M4ID: 30006716

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	10.2	-1.6	0.372
sd:	1.61	0.985	0.217

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	22.1	0.888	0.312	2.03	2.6
sd:	8.87	1.13	0.131	0.0871	0.961

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	227.31	179.53	165.54
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	9.57	4.08	2.96

MAX_MEAN: 14.7 MAX_MED: 16.4 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 29 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1,1-Bis(3,4-dimethylphenyl)ethane

CHID: 29223 CASRN: 1742-14-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B16

M4ID: 30006739

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	20.5	0.49	0.47
sd:	6.33	0.578	0.37

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	27.5	1.1	0.404	2.49	2.24
sd:	11.6	0.922	0.17	0.176	2.68

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	253.7	186.69	185.69
PROB:	0	0.38	0.62
RMSE:	14.57	5.84	5.66

MAX_MEAN: 18.8 MAX_MED: 18.1 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 31 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Pendimethalin

CHID: 24245 CASRN: 40487-42-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P20

M4ID: 30006015

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	25.6	1.05	2.02
sd:	1.26	0.0494	0.492

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	27	1.08	1.81	2.36	12.5
sd:	1.74	0.0577	0.45	0.151	33.4

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	263.5	166.94	168.67
PROB:	0	0.7	0.3
RMSE:	17.68	3.31	3.25

MAX_MEAN: 25.9 MAX_MED: 27.4 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 37 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: N-Phenyl-1,4-benzenediamine
 CHID: 25895 CASRN: 101-54-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I08
 M4ID: 30006579

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 23.8 1.96 6.33
 sd: 1.43 0.0163 4.05

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 28.8 2.01 2.79 2.39 13.2
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	218.88	153.67	155.97
PROB:	0	0.76	0.24
RMSE:	9.82	2.68	2.68

MAX_MEAN: 23.5 MAX_MED: 23.9 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 37 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Benzyl butyl phthalate

CHID: 20205 CASRN: 85-68-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P16

M4ID: 30006019

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	75.4	1.54	1.74
sd:	2.76	0.0346	0.143

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	75.4	1.54	1.74	4.3	11.6
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	310.88	180.74	184.74
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	40.55	4.36	4.36

MAX_MEAN: 71.3 MAX_MED: 72.2 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 3-Chloro-1,2-propanediol

CHID: 20664 CASRN: 96-24-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I09

M4ID: 30006194

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	95.9	-1	1.57
sd:	2.4	0.0609	1.17

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	102	-0.951	1.05	3.1	0.934
sd:	6.89	0.106	0.438	0.871	0.999

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	361.53	234.77	234.86
PROB:	0	0.51	0.49
RMSE:	87.12	10.32	9.53

MAX_MEAN: 102 MAX_MED: 108 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: beta-Hexachlorocyclohexane

CHID: 20685 CASRN: 319-85-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H10

M4ID: 30006217

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	27.1	0.46	3.08
sd:	1.38	0.171	2.75

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	27.1	0.46	3.08	3.62	12.8
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	279.92	198.91	202.91
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	22.88	5.64	5.64

MAX_MEAN: 31.3 MAX_MED: 30.8 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4,4'-Oxydianiline
 CHID: 21094 CASRN: 101-80-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G10
 M4ID: 30006625

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	69.4	1.97	8
sd:	2.1	0.00591	0.872

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	69.4	1.97	8	4.28	5
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	274.44	174.3	178.3
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	27.56	3.9	3.9

MAX_MEAN: 72 MAX_MED: 68.7 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: EPN

CHID: 22174 CASRN: 2104-64-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078010

M4ID: 30006433

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	29.6	1.09	2.15
sd:	1.18	0.044	0.398

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	30.5	1.11	2.03	2.38	16.1
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	271.56	168.35	171.97
PROB:	0	0.86	0.14
RMSE:	20.27	3.44	3.44

MAX_MEAN: 30.3 MAX_MED: 32.1 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Triphenylethylene

CHID: 22320 CASRN: 58-72-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K06

M4ID: 30006149

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	76.6	0.881	3.18
sd:	1.95	0.0227	0.397

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	77.4	0.885	3.14	2.38	16.6
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	333.36	208.88	212
PROB:	0	0.83	0.17
RMSE:	56.52	8.9	8.93

MAX_MEAN: 79.5 MAX_MED: 79.9 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2,4-Dihydroxybenzophenone

CHID: 22406 CASRN: 131-56-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D24

M4ID: 30006299

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	136	1.56	1.98
sd:	5.23	0.0435	0.203

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	136	1.56	1.98	4.24	17.9
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	347.35	215.8	219.8
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	75.35	8.79	8.79

MAX_MEAN: 130 MAX_MED: 128 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4,4'-Diaminobiphenyl methane
 CHID: 22422 CASRN: 101-77-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P18
 M4ID: 30006401

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 52.2 1.93 3.83
 sd: 4.37 0.0303 1.32

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 52.2 1.93 3.83 3.54 17.9
 sd: NA NA NA NA NA

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	267.09	195.26	199.26
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	21.93	5.37	5.37

MAX_MEAN: 50 MAX_MED: 47.8 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Phenolphthalin
 CHID: 22439 CASRN: 81-90-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N05
 M4ID: 30006078

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 49.1 1.91 3.57
 sd: 2.62 0.0196 0.523

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 61.5 1.97 3.16 2.34 17.9
 sd: 9.7 0.0434 0.422 0.00747 8.28

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	262.73	167.18	169.86
PROB:	0	0.79	0.21
RMSE:	20.09	3.22	3.16

MAX_MEAN: 47.2 MAX_MED: 45.9 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Butralin

CHID: 32337 CASRN: 33629-47-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C17

M4ID: 30006330

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	30.5	1.03	1.52
sd:	2.75	0.0866	0.422

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	30.5	1.03	1.52	4.05	17.8
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	274.99	186.24	190.24
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	21.91	5.18	5.18

MAX_MEAN: 38.6 MAX_MED: 44.1 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Clomazone

CHID: 32355 CASRN: 81777-89-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P09

M4ID: 30006026

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	30.5	1.85	2.82
sd:	3.95	0.0516	1.01

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	44	1.98	2.26	2.33	18
sd:	116	0.95	2.1	0.0496	99.9

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	245.63	180.85	183.41
PROB:	0	0.78	0.22
RMSE:	14.29	4.37	4.33

MAX_MEAN: 29.8 MAX_MED: 27 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Octylparaben
 CHID: 47957 CASRN: 1219-38-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B02
 M4ID: 30006753

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 104 1.38 1.59
 sd: 6.27 0.0633 0.257

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 104 1.38 1.59 3.9 16
 sd: NA NA NA NA NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	335.28	230.06	234.06
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	60.34	9.85	9.85

MAX_MEAN: 103 MAX_MED: 101 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-Aminoanthraquinone
 CHID: 20068 CASRN: 117-79-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D15
 M4ID: 30006692

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	216	1.09	1.03
sd:	27.3	0.154	0.258

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	216	1.09	1.03	3.92	15.3
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	386.2	262.13	266.13
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	137.4	17.79	17.79

MAX_MEAN: 225 MAX_MED: 250 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Azobenzene
 CHID: 20123 CASRN: 103-33-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C12
 M4ID: 30006719

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 68.7 1.93 0.855
 sd: 19.5 0.302 0.182

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 68.7 1.93 0.854 2.81 16.1
 sd: 19.5 0.302 0.182 236 7310

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	281.57	203.7	207.7
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	24.81	6.36	6.36

MAX_MEAN: 47.7 MAX_MED: 48.3 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Pentaerythritol dibromide

CHID: 20164 CASRN: 3296-90-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I12

M4ID: 30006575

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	148	1.71	0.975
sd:	14	0.105	0.0903

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	148	1.71	0.975	3.55	6.54
sd:	14	0.105	0.0904	761	3950

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	337.68	201.71	205.71
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	62.91	6.2	6.2

MAX_MEAN: 117 MAX_MED: 119 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-tert-Butylphenol

CHID: 20221 CASRN: 98-54-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B22

M4ID: 30006733

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	133	1.35	0.945
sd:	14.7	0.141	0.185

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	133	1.35	0.945	3.39	12.6
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	347.1	237.17	241.17
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	72.24	10.6	10.6

MAX_MEAN: 114 MAX_MED: 119 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Carbofuran

CHID: 20249 CASRN: 1563-66-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P06

M4ID: 30006413

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	124	1.89	1.1
sd:	14	0.108	0.124

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	124	1.89	1.1	4.16	18
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	318.8	209.81	213.81
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	47.63	7.73	7.73

MAX_MEAN: 95.5 MAX_MED: 93.2 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Cupferron

CHID: 20352 CASRN: 135-20-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D16

M4ID: 30006691

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	58.4	1.84	1
sd:	13.2	0.213	0.212

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	58.4	1.84	1	3.35	7.8
sd:	13.2	0.213	0.212	904	6670

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	276.07	203.3	207.3
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	22.79	6.23	6.23

MAX_MEAN: 42.5 MAX_MED: 47.1 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Ethylene glycol

CHID: 20597 CASRN: 107-21-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D22

M4ID: 30006685

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	35.3	1.57	0.531
sd:	9.23	0.467	0.171

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	35.3	1.57	0.533	2.69	6.55
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	257.94	184.81	188.81
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	16.08	4.46	4.46

MAX_MEAN: 25.3 MAX_MED: 24.5 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1,2-Diphenylhydrazine
 CHID: 20710 CASRN: 122-66-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C15
 M4ID: 30006332

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	32.7	1.68	1.37
sd:	3.61	0.0978	0.244

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	42.3	1.86	1.27	2.34	17.5
sd:	14.4	0.232	0.23	0.0157	10.6

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	252.03	163.95	165.29
PROB:	0	0.66	0.34
RMSE:	15.51	3.57	3.3

MAX_MEAN: 30.3 MAX_MED: 30.5 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Propham

CHID: 20766 CASRN: 122-42-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A10

M4ID: 30006769

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	43	1.29	0.387
sd:	14.2	0.806	0.176

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	43	1.24	0.465	2.35	16.3
sd:	12.2	0.57	0.182	0.0635	23.5

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	276.5	208.84	211.88
PROB:	0	0.82	0.18
RMSE:	21.69	6.57	6.52

MAX_MEAN: 30.8 MAX_MED: 34 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Nitrilotriacetic acid
 CHID: 20939 CASRN: 139-13-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A22
 M4ID: 30006757

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 111 1.62 0.687
 sd: 21.4 0.273 0.142

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 111 1.62 0.687 4.3 5.6
 sd: 21.4 0.273 0.142 125000 343000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	324.3	227.69	231.69
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	49.18	9.2	9.2

MAX_MEAN: 82.3 MAX_MED: 84.2 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: N-Nitrosodibutylamine
 CHID: 21026 CASRN: 924-16-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J15
 M4ID: 30006164

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 35.5 1.97 2.2
 sd: 6.61 0.101 0.807

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 36.2 1.97 2.43 2.37 18
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	238.1	159.39	163.14
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	13.07	2.97	2.91

MAX_MEAN: 29.6 MAX_MED: 30.1 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Phenothiazine
 CHID: 21126 CASRN: 92-84-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D19
 M4ID: 30006688

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 66.1 1.68 0.848
 sd: 18.1 0.318 0.206

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 72.4 1.76 0.825 2.36 17.2
 sd: 40.7 0.61 0.27 0.0869 33.5

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	289.84	189.61	192.61
PROB:	0	0.82	0.18
RMSE:	28.23	5.04	4.92

MAX_MEAN: 47.9 MAX_MED: 49.1 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Propyl gallate
 CHID: 21201 CASRN: 121-79-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B12
 M4ID: 30006743

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 67 1.76 0.812
 sd: 14.5 0.262 0.174

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 67 1.76 0.812 3.22 14.1
 sd: 14.5 0.262 0.174 35100 552000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	289.49	209.19	213.19
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	27.94	6.84	6.84

MAX_MEAN: 50.6 MAX_MED: 52.2 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Octanal

CHID: 21643 CASRN: 124-13-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E18

M4ID: 30006665

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	55	1.47	0.955
sd:	5.33	0.115	0.136

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	58.1	1.52	0.935	2.36	18
sd:	9.24	0.176	0.147	0.024	9.45

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	288.64	170.5	172.59
PROB:	0	0.74	0.26
RMSE:	27.32	3.87	3.62

MAX_MEAN: 45.9 MAX_MED: 46.2 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dimethyl sulfoxide
 CHID: 21735 CASRN: 67-68-5
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B11
 M4ID: 30006360

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	93.8	2.3	1.12
sd:	39.4	0.306	0.233

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	93.8	2.3	1.12	3.27	14.9
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	269.76	202.3	206.3
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	24.85	8.56	8.54

MAX_MEAN: 64.9 MAX_MED: 72.7 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-Methyl-2,4-pentanedio1

CHID: 21885 CASRN: 107-41-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H07

M4ID: 30006604

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	43.4	2.14	1.44
sd:	16.3	0.244	0.378

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	45.1	2.15	1.46	2.42	12
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	233.8	154.91	158.83
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	12.68	3.31	3.3

MAX_MEAN: 29.5 MAX_MED: 27.9 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Phenyl salicylate

CHID: 21957 CASRN: 118-55-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L19

M4ID: 30006496

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	40.9	1.89	1.21
sd:	10.6	0.218	0.314

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	42	1.89	1.27	2.36	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	247.49	172.98	176.64
PROB:	0	0.86	0.14
RMSE:	14.71	4.02	3.95

MAX_MEAN: 27.5 MAX_MED: 29.5 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Benzophenone
 CHID: 21961 CASRN: 119-61-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D18
 M4ID: 30006689

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	110	1.46	0.864
sd:	10.5	0.119	0.115

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	129	1.64	0.775	2.37	15.5
sd:	30.8	0.29	0.14	0.0184	8.65

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	331.27	201.74	202.77
PROB:	0	0.63	0.37
RMSE:	55.59	6.75	6.31

MAX_MEAN: 94.2 MAX_MED: 91.1 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Diphenylamine

CHID: 21975 CASRN: 122-39-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J18

M4ID: 30006545

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	38.4	1.94	1.77
sd:	6.63	0.113	0.475

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	41.6	1.97	1.83	2.37	15.6
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	246.88	168.04	171.69
PROB:	0	0.86	0.14
RMSE:	14.92	3.78	3.66

MAX_MEAN: 31 MAX_MED: 30.4 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-Phenoxyethanol

CHID: 21976 CASRN: 122-99-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C22

M4ID: 30006709

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	84.2	1.73	0.847
sd:	15.2	0.21	0.163

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	84.2	1.73	0.847	4.02	5.07
sd:	15.2	0.21	0.163	4600	12900

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	302.91	208.52	212.52
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	35.14	6.5	6.5

MAX_MEAN: 61.8 MAX_MED: 64.5 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-Hexyloxyaniline
 CHID: 22288 CASRN: 39905-57-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P02
 M4ID: 30006417

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 38.1 1.76 1.91
 sd: 4.01 0.0634 0.619

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 38.1 1.76 1.91 4.3 8.64
 sd: NA NA NA NA NA

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	260.45	183.54	187.54
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	17.8	4.25	4.25

MAX_MEAN: 33.4 MAX_MED: 34.3 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Vinclozolin

CHID: 22361 CASRN: 50471-44-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F22

M4ID: 30006253

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	40.3	2.03	1.01
sd:	13	0.289	0.231

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	40.3	2.03	1.01	4.3	3.61
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	241.68	158.2	162.2
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	13.17	2.88	2.88

MAX_MEAN: 27.1 MAX_MED: 25.7 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Diphenolic acid
 CHID: 22436 CASRN: 126-00-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L13
 M4ID: 30006118

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 99.9 1.87 1.31
 sd: 8.64 0.0699 0.14

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 99.9 1.87 1.31 3.22 8.17
 sd: 8.64 0.0699 0.14 765 6620

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	307.39	186.29	190.29
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	39.26	5.02	5.02

MAX_MEAN: 79.1 MAX_MED: 77.4 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Polydimethylsiloxane

CHID: 23833 CASRN: 9016-00-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A12

M4ID: 30006383

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	67.4	2.04	1.01
sd:	14.1	0.184	0.167

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	67.4	2.04	1.01	3.05	11.6
sd:	14.1	0.184	0.167	615	9510

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	271.8	181.36	185.36
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	21.89	4.35	4.35

MAX_MEAN: 47.5 MAX_MED: 46.3 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Benz(a)anthracene
 CHID: 23902 CASRN: 56-55-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K02
 M4ID: 30006153

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	57	1.95	2.04
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	57	1.9	3.17	2.37	12
sd:	19.2	0.104	0.844	0.0176	14.2

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	131.44	88.15	90.78
PROB:	0	0.79	0.21
RMSE:	17.33	3.21	2.71

MAX_MEAN: 47.5 MAX_MED: 47.5 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Cypermethrin
 CHID: 23998 CASRN: 52315-07-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N09
 M4ID: 30006458

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 62.6 1.83 0.865
 sd: 19.7 0.342 0.187

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 62.6 1.83 0.865 3.09 9.43
 sd: 19.7 0.342 0.187 245 2910

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	282.76	191.51	195.51
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	25.62	5.51	5.51

MAX_MEAN: 50.2 MAX_MED: 48.3 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Ethion
 CHID: 24086 CASRN: 563-12-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E19
 M4ID: 30006664

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 44.1 1.68 0.439
 sd: 27.9 1.34 0.252

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 44.1 1.6 0.507 2.5 3.68
 sd: 18.8 0.757 0.191 0.409 8.03

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	266.99	192.83	195.31
PROB:	0	0.78	0.22
RMSE:	18.8	5.41	5.12

MAX_MEAN: 27.4 MAX_MED: 26.5 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Benzyl salicylate

CHID: 24598 CASRN: 118-58-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F07

M4ID: 30006652

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	61.3	1.73	1.35
sd:	6.58	0.091	0.196

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	68.1	1.77	1.34	4.1	0.582
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	284.19	188.65	192.5
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	26.78	5.71	5.68

MAX_MEAN: 50.1 MAX_MED: 54.5 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Butyl glycidyl ether

CHID: 24691 CASRN: 2426-08-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B09

M4ID: 30006362

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	103	1.28	1.12
sd:	5.56	0.0652	0.121

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	111	1.35	1.04	2.38	17.5
sd:	31.6	0.3	0.317	0.109	38.6

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	335.39	194.48	198.11
PROB:	0	0.86	0.14
RMSE:	59.28	5.54	5.43

MAX_MEAN: 95.4 MAX_MED: 99.8 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Troclosesene

CHID: 24993 CASRN: 2782-57-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A19

M4ID: 30006376

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	60.3	2.1	0.578
sd:	57.2	1.47	0.373

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	60.3	1.92	0.748	2.33	17.6
sd:	32	0.582	0.255	0.0235	15.2

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	269.63	214.9	217.32
PROB:	0	0.77	0.23
RMSE:	20.61	7.69	7.41

MAX_MEAN: 33.6 MAX_MED: 36.7 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dicyclopentadiene

CHID: 25023 CASRN: 77-73-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E04

M4ID: 30006679

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	53.3	2.47	0.535
sd:	37.5	1	0.176

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	47.7	2.3	0.567	2.87	15.3
sd:	37.8	1.08	0.195	525	13800

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	250.46	203.88	208.08
PROB:	0	0.89	0.11
RMSE:	15.29	7.11	7.11

MAX_MEAN: 25.8 MAX_MED: 27.1 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Triphenyl phosphite
 CHID: 26252 CASRN: 101-02-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H17
 M4ID: 30006210

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	45.6	1.95	1.54
sd:	7.14	0.103	0.432

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	45.6	1.93	2.22	2.37	14.2
sd:	14.2	0.126	0.833	0.0221	13.8

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	251.99	155.09	158.85
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	16.24	2.73	2.68

MAX_MEAN: 35.5 MAX_MED: 34.4 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-(Phenylmethylene)octanal

CHID: 26684 CASRN: 101-86-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J16

M4ID: 30006547

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	60	1.98	1.68
sd:	12.1	0.13	0.522

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	60	1.98	1.68	4.29	3.62
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	266.63	176.06	180.06
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	20.78	3.85	3.85

MAX_MEAN: 46.3 MAX_MED: 46 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: (2Z)-3,7-Dimethylocta-2,6-dien-1-ol

CHID: 26728 CASRN: 106-25-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B18

M4ID: 30006737

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	113	0.733	0.786
sd:	7.55	0.105	0.141

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	113	0.733	0.786	4.28	5.67
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	352.02	229.6	233.6
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	76.06	9.27	9.27

MAX_MEAN: 114 MAX_MED: 117 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-(2H-Benzotriazol-2-yl)-4-methylphenol

CHID: 27479 CASRN: 2440-22-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F15

M4ID: 30006644

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	41.4	1.64	1.15
sd:	6.84	0.158	0.223

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	49.2	1.78	1.07	2.35	17
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	266.21	170.61	173.74
PROB:	0	0.83	0.17
RMSE:	19.39	3.62	3.55

MAX_MEAN: 34.6 MAX_MED: 34.2 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Nilutamide

CHID: 34165 CASRN: 63612-50-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L06

M4ID: 30006509

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	96.9	2.35	8
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	74.2	-0.455	5.2	-0.153	11.2
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	253.08	253.06	263
PROB:	0.5	0.5	0
RMSE:	22.74	22.5	22.73

MAX_MEAN: 50.8 MAX_MED: 76.1 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 0.5

FLAGS: 16; 11; 10

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Cinmethylin

CHID: 34456 CASRN: 87818-31-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F20

M4ID: 30006639

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	50	1.84	0.825
sd:	14.8	0.343	0.207

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	50	1.84	0.828	3.96	1.46
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	266.27	188.27	192.27
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	19.24	5.19	5.18

MAX_MEAN: 34.8 MAX_MED: 34.6 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dinotefuran

CHID: 34549 CASRN: 165252-70-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K08

M4ID: 30006147

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	63.5	2.05	1.06
sd:	39.4	0.538	0.446

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	88.7	-0.168	8	0.229	5.55
sd:	333	3.82	178	2.89	43.6

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	294.72	260.64	296.43
PROB:	0	1	0
RMSE:	35.41	29.13	30.69

MAX_MEAN: 59.6 MAX_MED: 80.6 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-Bromo-4-hydroxyacetophenone

CHID: 34576 CASRN: 2491-38-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D07

M4ID: 30006316

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	35.7	2.04	1.49
sd:	6.47	0.116	0.362

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	35.7	2.04	1.49	3.89	8.91
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	230.84	160.03	164.03
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	11.42	2.81	2.81

MAX_MEAN: 27.4 MAX_MED: 26.8 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Penoxsulam
 CHID: 34803 CASRN: 219714-96-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C18
 M4ID: 30006713

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 117 1.26 0.715
 sd: 17.3 0.223 0.156

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 129 1.4 0.662 2.35 17.6
 sd: 29.3 0.343 0.155 0.0275 13.6

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	339.99	225.17	227.12
PROB:	0	0.73	0.27
RMSE:	63.16	8.72	8.43

MAX_MEAN: 95.7 MAX_MED: 91.5 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Morin hydrate

CHID: 40776 CASRN: 654055-01-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C19

M4ID: 30006328

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	68.4	2.04	1.77
sd:	14.3	0.112	0.534

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	68.4	2.04	1.77	4.01	5.48
sd:	14.3	0.112	0.534	3370	10800

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	266.45	183.42	187.42
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	21.28	4.36	4.36

MAX_MEAN: 50.4 MAX_MED: 53.8 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Benzyl cinnamate
CHID: 41663 CASRN: 103-41-3
SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B20
M4ID: 30006735

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	48.7	1.48	0.961
sd:	6.58	0.159	0.21

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	48.7	1.48	0.961	3.64	15.4
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	283.16	185.42	189.42
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	24.96	4.71	4.71

MAX_MEAN: 41.7 MAX_MED: 42.6 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Diphenyl phosphite

CHID: 41889 CASRN: 4712-55-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E20

M4ID: 30006279

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	97.2	1.08	0.908
sd:	5.73	0.0994	0.128

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	97.2	1.08	0.908	2.87	15.6
sd:	5.73	0.0994	0.128	361	9590

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	336.14	200.34	204.34
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	59.11	5.77	5.77

MAX_MEAN: 91 MAX_MED: 92.9 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1,2-Diphenylethanone
 CHID: 44430 CASRN: 451-40-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L20
 M4ID: 30006495

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 82.9 1.96 1.52
 sd: 14 0.114 0.298

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 82.9 1.94 1.7 2.36 17.9
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	287.57	187.87	191
PROB:	0	0.83	0.17
RMSE:	29.26	5.38	5.03

MAX_MEAN: 60.1 MAX_MED: 61 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Zenarestat
 CHID: 47296 CASRN: 112733-06-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L24
 M4ID: 30006491

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 39.7 1.96 2.36
 sd: 4.07 0.0491 0.468

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 42.5 1.99 2.35 2.37 17.8
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	239.91	151.37	154.96
PROB:	0	0.86	0.14
RMSE:	13.52	3.24	3.2

MAX_MEAN: 30 MAX_MED: 33.8 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: HMR1426
 CHID: 47338 CASRN: 262376-75-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B04
 M4ID: 30006751

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 38.7 1.93 0.595
 sd: 15.3 0.606 0.225

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 38.7 1.93 0.595 4.2 4.88
 sd: 15.3 0.606 0.225 14400 34800

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	256.07	205.09	209.09
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	15.82	7.16	7.16

MAX_MEAN: 25.7 MAX_MED: 24.5 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dexamethasone sodium phosphate
 CHID: 47429 CASRN: 2392-39-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H05
 M4ID: 30006222

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 55.7 2.21 1.07
 sd: 16.7 0.238 0.189

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 55.7 2.21 1.07 3.43 17.6
 sd: NA NA NA NA NA

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	247.07	164.28	168.28
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	15.31	3.86	3.86

MAX_MEAN: 35.7 MAX_MED: 32.6 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: C10-21 alkanesulfonic acids phenyl esters

CHID: 47526 CASRN: 91082-17-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B09

M4ID: 30006746

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	28.3	0.972	0.874
sd:	3.23	0.168	0.255

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	42.8	1.51	0.618	2.48	2.24
sd:	28.6	0.899	0.251	0.154	2.96

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	265.78	178.89	178.93
PROB:	0	0.5	0.5
RMSE:	18.33	4.12	3.86

MAX_MEAN: 28.7 MAX_MED: 27.8 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: PharmaGSID_48509

CHID: 48509 CASRN: NOCAS_48509

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B15

M4ID: 30006740

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	106	1.87	0.967
sd:	14.8	0.144	0.129

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	106	1.87	0.967	3.36	12
sd:	14.8	0.144	0.129	39900	444000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	309.63	207.01	211.01
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	40.41	6.8	6.8

MAX_MEAN: 79.5 MAX_MED: 76.6 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Pyriproxyfen
 CHID: 32640 CASRN: 95737-68-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G21
 M4ID: 30006230

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	20.2	0.864	1.91
sd:	0.984	0.0474	0.37

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	22.3	0.929	1.52	2.32	17.8
sd:	1	0.0456	0.247	0.00601	4.57

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	253.22	146.55	131.97
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	14.88	2.58	2.07

MAX_MEAN: 23.1 MAX_MED: 23.7 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 46 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-Amino-5-azotoluene
CHID: 20069 CASRN: 97-56-3
SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F22
M4ID: 30006637

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	52.7	0.605	8
sd:	9.34	0.057	17.9

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	84.6	0.719	3	1.9	18
sd:	6.45	0.052	0.954	0.0106	14.3

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	320.25	302.31	244.21
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	48.34	32.75	11.49

MAX_MEAN: 92.2 MAX_MED: 91 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Butylparaben

CHID: 20209 CASRN: 94-26-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B17

M4ID: 30006354

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	138	0.717	3.36
sd:	10.7	0.0861	1.35

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	184	0.897	2.37	2.04	3.4
sd:	10.7	0.0388	0.371	0.0313	0.434

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	367.75	312.06	247.91
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	102.11	43.41	15.49

MAX_MEAN: 170 MAX_MED: 167 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Catechol

CHID: 20257 CASRN: 120-80-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M18

M4ID: 30006089

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	37.9	1.15	3.87
sd:	1.86	0.0346	0.722

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	54.5	1.24	2.88	2.32	1.1
sd:	11.1	0.0405	0.393	0.161	0.447

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	284.4	185.45	156.94
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	25.54	4.67	2.79

MAX_MEAN: 43.7 MAX_MED: 43 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: o,p'-DDD
 CHID: 20372 CASRN: 53-19-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K19
 M4ID: 30006520

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 60.7 0.631 8
 sd: 3.6 0.0906 24.2

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 76.2 0.754 2.43 1.99 5.81
 sd: 4.35 0.0385 0.428 0.0156 1.35

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	318.91	267.19	214.94
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	45.32	23.53	8.55

MAX_MEAN: 74.3 MAX_MED: 76.3 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane
 CHID: 20375 CASRN: 50-29-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E17
 M4ID: 30006282

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	27.5	0.789	2.97
sd:	2.13	0.073	0.848

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	37.1	0.933	2.1	2.08	3.89
sd:	2.51	0.0438	0.369	0.03	0.938

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	269.64	215.41	182.23
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	20.13	9.2	6.37

MAX_MEAN: 35.3 MAX_MED: 34.6 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dehydroepiandrosterone

CHID: 20379 CASRN: 53-43-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D18

M4ID: 30006305

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	96	-0.918	6.95
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	128	-0.316	1.02	1.99	2.33
sd:	7.12	0.101	0.178	0.0368	0.492

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	359.09	295.1	243.05
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	85.51	29.35	11.25

MAX_MEAN: 120 MAX_MED: 124 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2,6-Dinitrotoluene
CHID: 20528 CASRN: 606-20-2
SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J06
M4ID: 30006557

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	33.7	2.7	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	108	0.419	5.74	1.19	12.9
sd:	14.7	0.213	6.17	0.424	47.2

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	307.71	305.18	226.39
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	47.31	43.58	8.65

MAX_MEAN: 108 MAX_MED: 107 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Endosulfan
 CHID: 20560 CASRN: 115-29-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G03
 M4ID: 30006248

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 26.5 0.966 8
 sd: 1.5 0.0709 14.7

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 34.2 0.991 3.24 2.15 2.08
 sd: 3.6 0.0415 0.852 0.0651 0.597

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	267.26	192.05	167.35
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	19.05	5.59	3.3

MAX_MEAN: 30.3 MAX_MED: 31.7 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-Hexylresorcinol

CHID: 20699 CASRN: 136-77-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A03

M4ID: 30006392

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	19.1	0.0213	7.99
sd:	8.8	0.298	93.2

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	68.2	0.112	8	1.31	18
sd:	4.49	0.432	30.7	0.0139	34.8

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	301.16	301.69	249.18
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	35.83	30.48	14.19

MAX_MEAN: 70 MAX_MED: 71.9 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Picloram

CHID: 21160 CASRN: 1918-02-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K18

M4ID: 30006137

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	86.5	1.07	1.44
sd:	1.68	0.0234	0.102

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	91.7	1.12	1.27	2.38	15.5
sd:	3.45	0.039	0.113	0.0115	3.67

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	332.85	164.23	163.77
PROB:	0	0.44	0.56
RMSE:	56.25	3.45	3.49

MAX_MEAN: 82.8 MAX_MED: 87.4 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2,2',6,6'-Tetrachlorobisphenol A

CHID: 21770 CASRN: 79-95-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K15

M4ID: 30006524

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	46.9	2.8	7.99
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	57.4	0.782	8	1.62	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	284.24	290.24	241.23
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	27.82	27.82	11.18

MAX_MEAN: 57.4 MAX_MED: 57.1 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2,2-Bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)-1,1,1-trichloroethane

CHID: 22325 CASRN: 2971-36-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B06

M4ID: 30006365

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	53.3	-0.926	7.97
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	62.9	-0.463	1.25	2	5.82
sd:	2.34	0.0856	0.205	0.0204	1.41

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	322.43	268.53	211.02
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	46.34	22.61	6.62

MAX_MEAN: 66.1 MAX_MED: 65.6 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 5alpha-Dihydrotestosterone

CHID: 22364 CASRN: 521-18-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C11

M4ID: 30006336

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	99.4	-0.581	1.63
sd:	3.71	0.116	0.351

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	103	-0.53	1.5	2.33	17.3
sd:	3.75	0.0964	0.255	0.00991	6.43

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	362.76	256.8	250.18
PROB:	0	0.04	0.96
RMSE:	89.6	15.14	12.53

MAX_MEAN: 116 MAX_MED: 121 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Progesterone

CHID: 22370 CASRN: 57-83-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M06

M4ID: 30006485

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	14.5	0.548	8
sd:	4.42	0.327	42.9

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	41.5	0.904	1.17	1.77	6.15
sd:	18.9	0.391	0.643	0.0661	1.91

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	259.79	255.26	215.7
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	16.99	14.71	7.36

MAX_MEAN: 31 MAX_MED: 30.4 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Bisphenol B
 CHID: 22442 CASRN: 77-40-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P10
 M4ID: 30006025

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 57.5 -0.989 7.72
 sd: 13.2 2.06 1440

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 106 -0.779 2.22 1.7 18
 sd: 4.56 0.181 1.7 0.00652 22.1

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	344.06	333.35	253.27
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	69.07	50.91	13.3

MAX_MEAN: 113 MAX_MED: 116 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-Dodecylphenol

CHID: 22508 CASRN: 104-43-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A11

M4ID: 30006384

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	31.7	-0.961	6.99
sd:	9.29	4.2	745

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	72.8	-0.287	1.08	1.7	18
sd:	8.08	0.192	0.394	0.019	36.2

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	317.23	312.38	265.16
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	44.36	35.81	16.72

MAX_MEAN: 68.1 MAX_MED: 78.5 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-Ethylhexylparaben
 CHID: 22525 CASRN: 5153-25-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L11
 M4ID: 30006504

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 22.7 2.47 0.3
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 107 0.467 1.14 1.65 17.9
 sd: 20.3 0.235 0.452 0.183 67.8

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	322.75	328.14	269.88
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	50.67	48.93	17.21

MAX_MEAN: 94.5 MAX_MED: 91.1 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 3,3'-Dimethylbenzidine
 CHID: 24059 CASRN: 119-93-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G09
 M4ID: 30006242

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 36.9 1.06 3.88
 sd: 2.24 0.0403 1.36

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 47.4 1.17 2.49 2.13 3.07
 sd: 4.52 0.0526 0.473 0.0408 0.617

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	281.44	213.66	172.22
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	24.6	9.11	3.46

MAX_MEAN: 43 MAX_MED: 42.4 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 6-Hydroxy-2-naphthyl disulfide

CHID: 25429 CASRN: 6088-51-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D13

M4ID: 30006310

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	108	1.43	2.64
sd:	3.73	0.0382	0.365

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	141	1.52	2.26	2.81	0.812
sd:	55.8	0.074	0.273	0.322	0.969

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	339.39	200.24	198.99
PROB:	0	0.35	0.65
RMSE:	65.11	5.97	5.91

MAX_MEAN: 107 MAX_MED: 110 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2-Naphthalenol

CHID: 27061 CASRN: 135-19-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K10

M4ID: 30006529

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	68	1.35	5.02
sd:	2.79	0.0307	2.44

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	86.2	1.44	2.95	2.4	1.67
sd:	32.5	0.109	0.817	0.149	1.73

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	316.59	222.3	208.14
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	45.04	9.53	7.05

MAX_MEAN: 79.1 MAX_MED: 72.8 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Dodecylphenol

CHID: 27926 CASRN: 27193-86-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B19

M4ID: 30006352

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	30.3	2.8	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	67	-0.211	1.17	1.36	11.7
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	306.86	311.58	243.02
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	37.69	35.79	11.54

MAX_MEAN: 67.5 MAX_MED: 69.2 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Fenhexamid

CHID: 32549 CASRN: 126833-17-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E20

M4ID: 30006663

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	77.3	1.15	3.41
sd:	6.24	0.0539	0.978

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	113	1.3	2.29	2.05	5.36
sd:	13.1	0.0673	0.521	0.0236	1.8

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	322.38	274.02	235.28
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	50.39	25.53	11.54

MAX_MEAN: 95.3 MAX_MED: 101 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-Nonylphenol

CHID: 33836 CASRN: 104-40-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F10

M4ID: 30006265

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	19.9	0.573	8
sd:	4.71	0.194	47

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	38.4	0.843	1.54	1.91	18
sd:	4.57	0.113	0.464	0.0122	7.03

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	270.36	262.16	219.87
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	20.39	17.35	8.76

MAX_MEAN: 36.2 MAX_MED: 35.4 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 1-Hydroxypyrene

CHID: 38298 CASRN: 5315-79-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H20

M4ID: 30006591

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	44	2.8	7.99
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	44.1	1.03	8	1.74	16.8
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	272.67	278.67	238.58
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	22.98	22.98	10.67

MAX_MEAN: 44.3 MAX_MED: 42.1 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 2,2',4,4'-Tetrahydroxybenzophenone

CHID: 41306 CASRN: 131-55-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F11

M4ID: 30006264

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	114	0.741	2.22
sd:	3.08	0.0336	0.41

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	121	0.776	1.91	2.59	2.58
sd:	8.95	0.0531	0.407	0.352	3.63

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	359.38	235.24	232.54
PROB:	0	0.21	0.79
RMSE:	86.5	11.19	9.91

MAX_MEAN: 122 MAX_MED: 120 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 5HPP-33

CHID: 46970 CASRN: 105624-86-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N02

M4ID: 30006465

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	69.7	0.0489	8
sd:	4.52	0.184	29.8

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	92.5	0.131	4.17	2.07	1.33
sd:	7.13	0.19	5.74	0.0677	0.298

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	336.84	267.16	221.83
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	59.58	17.67	8.09

MAX_MEAN: 89.7 MAX_MED: 92.1 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: SR271425

CHID: 47347 CASRN: 155990-20-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J04

M4ID: 30006559

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	9.48	2.8	7.94
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	76.6	1.35	2.49	1.89	18
sd:	10.8	0.0827	0.716	0.0077	7.21

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	277.67	283.67	211.79
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	28.13	28.13	7.38

MAX_MEAN: 74.1 MAX_MED: 67.8 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-Butylphenol

CHID: 47425 CASRN: 1638-22-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M09

M4ID: 30006482

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	92.4	1.2	2.43
sd:	4.71	0.0388	0.376

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	108	1.3	1.83	2.32	17.5
sd:	6.02	0.0463	0.222	0.00491	4.77

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	335.55	226.95	205
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	60.03	9.55	6.98

MAX_MEAN: 96.4 MAX_MED: 107 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 3-Hydroxyfluorene

CHID: 47540 CASRN: 6344-67-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C20

M4ID: 30006711

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	84.6	1.03	3.71
sd:	6.34	0.0477	1.8

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	139	1.24	1.93	2.05	2.63
sd:	23.9	0.0883	0.363	0.0591	0.532

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	332.43	274.86	233.52
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	58.02	24.96	10.39

MAX_MEAN: 106 MAX_MED: 112 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: C.I. Acid Blue 74

CHID: 20190 CASRN: 860-22-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091019

M4ID: 30006040

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	48.2	1.76	1.7
sd:	3.74	0.0559	0.288

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	53.6	1.81	1.88	2.35	18
sd:	8.7	0.0834	0.37	0.00834	8.95

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	272.83	167.4	167.11
PROB:	0	0.46	0.54
RMSE:	22.14	3.43	3.18

MAX_MEAN: 41.8 MAX_MED: 42.4 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Thiabendazole
 CHID: 21337 CASRN: 148-79-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A05
 M4ID: 30006390

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 38.2 1.37 0.3
 sd: 28.2 2.27 0.208

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 39.2 1.24 0.401 2.34 6.04
 sd: 11.7 0.677 0.129 0.0838 13.7

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	266.72	195.97	191.69
PROB:	0	0.11	0.89
RMSE:	18.5	5.47	4.52

MAX_MEAN: 27.3 MAX_MED: 30.5 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 4-(2-Methylbutan-2-yl)phenol

CHID: 21771 CASRN: 80-46-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A18

M4ID: 30006761

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	129	0.163	0.67
sd:	9.9	0.147	0.205

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	181	0.734	0.49	2.32	2.05
sd:	34.1	0.352	0.0946	0.0538	0.563

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	365.85	266.84	240.28
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	94.99	19.04	10.31

MAX_MEAN: 134 MAX_MED: 131 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 3-Phenoxybenzenemethanol
 CHID: 27756 CASRN: 13826-35-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L22
 M4ID: 30006493

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 84.3 1.45 1.94
 sd: 5.8 0.0504 0.272

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 135 1.75 1.36 2.31 17.5
 sd: 21.9 0.114 0.149 0.00459 9.31

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	324.2	221.26	198.05
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	51.23	9.76	5.81

MAX_MEAN: 97.8 MAX_MED: 95.6 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: 17-Methyltestosterone
 CHID: 33664 CASRN: 58-18-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A14
 M4ID: 30006381

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 110 0.213 0.626
 sd: 8.91 0.173 0.135

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 154 0.817 0.474 2.61 1.13
 sd: 80.7 0.921 0.141 0.256 1

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	357.3	247.16	247.14
PROB:	0	0.5	0.5
RMSE:	82.46	13.03	12.44

MAX_MEAN: 107 MAX_MED: 104 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Fluroxypyr-meptyl
 CHID: 34303 CASRN: 81406-37-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A21
 M4ID: 30006374

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 34.5 1.34 0.3
 sd: 14.7 1.3 0.153

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 34.5 1.21 0.501 2.32 4.79
 sd: 8.57 0.455 0.188 0.0393 5.13

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	261.8	193.03	187.19
PROB:	0	0.05	0.95
RMSE:	16.93	5.17	4.59

MAX_MEAN: 25.4 MAX_MED: 25.9 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2490 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_LUC_Inactive_up)

NAME: Benodanil
 CHID: 41623 CASRN: 15310-01-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D15
 M4ID: 30006308

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 75.4 1.31 1.54
 sd: 4.2 0.0492 0.171

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 90.3 1.48 1.19 2.33 18
 sd: 7.45 0.0878 0.117 0.00444 3.33

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	316.76	181.32	155.14
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	43.9	5.04	2.79

MAX_MEAN: 75.5 MAX_MED: 73.7 BMAD: 2.23

COFF: 22.3 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: